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STUDIES REGARDING THE PRODUCTIVITY OF GRASSLANDS FROM AGROSILVOPASTORAL SYSTEM FROM GRECI VILLAGE, TULCEA COUNTY, ROMANIA

Teodor MARUȘCA¹, Daniyar MEMEDEMİN², Elena TAULESCU³,
Bogdan BĂJENARU⁴, Viorel ROȘCA⁵, Andreea C. ANDREOIU⁶

Abstract. *The most extensive agrosilvopastoral systems (ASPs) in Romania are found in Dobrogea where the climate is warmer, with less rainfall. Determination of agrochemical properties of the soil on the grasslands with trees revealed an increase of 40-100% of the fertilizing elements (N, P, K) compared to treeless grasslands. The participation of fodder species in the vegetal layer under trees is twice as high, the pastoral value more than 3 times and the fodder production more than 6 times higher than in the treeless grassland. Analyzes on feed quality showed an increase from 12 to 20% of crude protein and feed digestibility, from 38% in the open field to 65% under trees. Also, the optimal stocking rate for a 185-day grazing season is almost 1 Livestock Unit (LU) / ha under trees and 6 times lower on the treeless grassland. The results confirm the desirability of maintaining and expanding ASPs, in full accordance with global climate change approaches.*

Keywords: agrosilvopastoral system, floristic composition, permanent grassland productivity, feed quality

1. Introduction

The agro-forestry system for raising livestock, especially cattle, on meadows with rare trees, has been called "agrosilvopastoral system" (ASPs) or "silvopastoral system" or "agroforestry". The system is implemented mainly on poor quality or non-agricultural land and aims at extensive animal husbandry [5, 2, 16].

¹Assoc. Prof., Ph.D., Eng., Technical Director, Research and Development Institute for Grasslands Brasov, Romania, Corresponding Member of the Academy of the Romanian Scientists (e-mail: maruscat@yahoo.com).

²Lecturer, Ph.D., Eng., "Ovidius" University of Constanta, Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences, Romania (e-mail: daniyar_memedemin@yahoo.com)

³Researcher, MSc., Eng., Research and Development Institute for Grasslands Brasov, Romania (e-mail: taulescuelena@yahoo.com)

⁴Biol., Macinului Mountains National Park, Romania (e-mail: bogdan_bajenaru@yahoo.com)

⁵Director, Ph.D., Eng., Macinului Mountains National Park, Romania (e-mail: director.apnmm@gmail.com)

⁶Chemist, Ph.D. Stud., Research and Development Institute for Grasslands Brasov, Romania (e-mail: andreea.andreoiu@pajisti-grassland.ro)

At the national level, more in - depth research on these systems has been carried out recently by Marușca *et al.* [6, 9, 11, 12] and Mihăilă *et al.* [13].

The importance of this topic (ASPs) is also underlined by research projects and papers published worldwide [1, 3]. Researchers focus on maintaining, expanding and implementing ASPs with all the benefits they bring both economically and ecologically.

Advanced research are conducted mainly in Mediterranean countries with dry and hot climates and these include tree characteristics, grassland characteristics and improvement measures (fertilization, overseeding and reseeded), animal characteristics and stocking rate (for cattle, sheep, goats or pigs), environmental protection and biodiversity [14, 16, 4].

This paper presents an agrosilvopastoral system from northern Dobrogea, at the foot of the Macin Mountains, compared to a permanent treeless grassland nearby.

2. Materials and Methods

The case studies were carried out on Crucele area from Greci locality, Tulcea county. The wooded pasture (ASPs) has an area of 38.0 ha and is located at 120 m altitude.

The communal pasture Crucele of Greci village is located on a flat land and it has forest vegetation made up mainly of oriental hornbeam trees and different species of oak. Tree density, composition and arithmetic mean diameter are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. General data on ASPs with trees from Crucele

Species	Average composition per hectare		Average diameter (cm)
	Nr. of individuals	Percentage (%)	
<i>Carpinus orientalis</i>	182	59	23
<i>Quercus pubescens</i>	96	31	37
<i>Quercus pedunculiflora</i>	9	3	48
<i>Tilia argentea</i>	12	4	45
<i>Fraxinus ornus</i>	4	1	35
<i>Prunus mahaleb</i>	3	1	34
<i>Acer campestre</i>	1	1	48
TOTAL	307	100	X

Source: Own results.

Along with this ASPs, there are approximately 117 ha of treeless permanent grassland with production as priority function (PF).

In these two distinct locations, 5 floristic surveys were performed according to the Klapp - Ellenberg percentage method [7]. Soil and grass samples were also collected for laboratory analysis.

The productivity of treeless grassland and of the agrosilvopastoral system was evaluated according to the method based on floristic survey [7, 8].

The analyzes of the soil samples were performed at the Office of Pedological and Agrochemical Studies (OSPA) Braşov according to the usual methodology. Plant samples were evaluated in the laboratory of quality measurements from the Research - Development Institute for Grasslands Braşov, according to the Near Infrared Reflectance Spectroscopy (NIRS) method.

3. Results and Discussions

Soil agrochemical analyzes revealed a higher content of fertilizers in ASPs than in treeless grassland, as presented recently by Maruşca & Memedemin [10], with 40% more nitrogen (N), 70% more phosphorus (P) and almost double for potassium (K), (Table 2).

Table 2. Agrochemical soil values of ASPs and FP grasslands at 10 cm depth

Specification	Unit	ASPs	FP	Diff. +; -	%
pH reaction in H ₂ O	ind	6.7	6.6	- 0.1	99
Hydrolytic acidity (Ah)	me/100g	3.5	3.8	+ 0.3	109
Sum of bases (SB)	me/100g	22.7	28.5	+ 5.8	126
Base saturation (V)	%	86.6	88.2	+ 1.6	102
Humus	%	5.46	7.58	+ 2.12	139
Total Nitrogen (N)	%	0.273	0.380	+ 0.107	139
Mobile Phosphorus (P)	ppm	37.2	62.7	+ 25.5	169
Mobile Potassium (K)	ppm	192	378	+ 186	197

Source: Own results.

The other indicators, such as soil reaction (pH - slightly acid) and degree of base saturation (V - eubasic soil), have almost the same values, with 1-2% difference, being therefore very well correlated for both variants studied (ASPs and FP).

Soil trophicity, better under trees due to animal manure, and protection from sunlight in ASPs, positively influenced the floristic composition of the vegetal layer and the productivity of grasslands (Table 3), as shown also by Păcurar [15].

Table 3. Floristic composition, productivity and optimal stocking rate from FP and ASPs

Species	Participation %			%	Indices	
	FP	ASPs	Diff. + -		F	M
Cover	94.9	89.3	-5.6	94	x	x
Poaceae	51.8	61.3	+9.5	118	x	x
<i>Botriochloa ischaemum</i>	30.2	0.1	-30.1	0	3	0
<i>Festuca valesiaca</i>	13.4	0.1	-13.3	1	5	3
<i>Setaria viridis</i>	4.3	1.5	-2.8	35	6	3
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	2.7	2.9	+0.2	107	6	2
<i>Bromus secalinus</i>	0.6	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Stipa capillata</i>	0.4	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Bromus sterilis</i>	0.2	0.6	+0.4	300	3	0
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	-	40.1	x	x	9	8
<i>Hordeum murinum</i>	-	11.9	x	x	5	3
<i>Poa angustifolia</i>	-	3.6	x	x	7	5
<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	-	0.2	x	x	3	0
<i>Elymus repens</i>	-	0.2	x	x	6	7
<i>Setaria verticillata</i>	-	0.1	x	x	6	3
Fabaceae	4.0	9.2	+5.2	230	x	x
<i>Trifolium campestre</i>	3.5	8.3	+4.8	237	7	2
<i>Trifolium arvense</i>	0.5	0.9	+0.4	180	4	2
Other families	39.1	18.8	-20.3	48	x	x
<i>Filago arvensis</i>	12.5	3.7	-8.8	30	3	0
<i>Torilis arvensis</i>	4.1	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Eryngium campestre</i>	2.9	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Echium vulgare</i>	2.5	-	x	x	4	3
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	1.6	3.1	+1.5	194	6	4
<i>Berteroa incana</i>	1.6	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Chondrilla juncea</i>	1.4	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	1.4	0.1	-1.3	7	5	6
<i>Potentilla argentea</i>	1.2	0.6	-0.6	50	4	2
<i>Artemisia austriaca</i>	1.0	1.0	0	100	2	0
<i>Carduus nutans</i>	1.0	1.0	0	100	2	0
<i>Crepis foetida</i>	1.0	0.1	-0.9	10	3	0
<i>Caucalis platycarpus</i>	0.8	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Galium humifusum</i>	0.8	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Petrorhagia prolifera</i>	0.8	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Centaurea solstitialis</i>	0.6	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Cuscuta campestris</i>	0.6	0.1	-0.5	17	3	0
<i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i>	0.6	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Carthamus lanatus</i>	0.5	0.2	-0.3	40	3	0
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	0.5	0.2	-0.3	40	6	1
<i>Centaurea diffusa</i>	0.4	0.4	0	100	4	4
<i>Rosa canina</i>	0.4	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Daucus carota</i>	0.3	-	x	x	6	5
<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	0.1	-	x	x	7	6
<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	0.1	1.1	+1	1100	3	0

<i>Herniaria glabra</i>	0.1	-	x	x	3	0
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	0.1	1.2	+1.1	1200	5	3
<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	0.1	-	x	x	7	5
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	0.1	-	x	x	7	3
<i>Amaranthus albus</i>	-	0.8	x	x	3	0
<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	-	0.8	x	x	3	0
<i>Chenopodium album</i>	-	0.7	x	x	3	0
<i>Malva neglecta</i>	-	0.7	x	x	3	0
<i>Carpinus orientalis</i> (juv.)	-	0.6	x	x	3	0
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>	-	0.3	x	x	3	0
<i>Ballota nigra</i>	-	0.3	x	x	3	0
<i>Conyza canadensis</i>	-	0.3	x	x	3	0
<i>Euphorbia maculata</i>	-	0.2	x	x	1	0
<i>Fallopia dumetorum</i>	-	0.2	x	x	3	0
<i>Heliotropium europaeum</i>	-	0.2	x	x	3	0
<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	-	0.2	x	x	2	0
<i>Berteroa incana</i>	-	0.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Cirsium vulgare</i>	-	0.1	x	x	2	0
<i>Echium italicum</i>	-	0.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Lactuca serriola</i>	-	0.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Potentilla reptans</i>	-	0.1	x	x	3	0
<i>Vincetoxicum hirundinaria</i>	-	0.1	x	x	1	0
<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	-	0.1	x	x	2	0
Total species (nr.)	38	45	7	118	x	x
From wich: - fodder	16	16	0	100	x	x
- not fodder	22	29	7	132	x	x
Participation of fodder species	32.7	66.0	+33.3	202	x	x
Participation of harmful species	62.2	23.3	-38.9	37	x	x
Bare soil	5.1	10.7	+5.6	210	x	x
Pastoral Value (PV)	19.5	62.9	+43.4	323	x	x
Phytomass index	0.97	4.25	+3.3	443	x	x
Fodder production (GM t/ha)	1.8	11.2	+9.3	622	x	x
Optimum stocking rate for 185 grazing days	0.15	0.93	+0.78	620	x	x

Source: Own results.

Thus, non-valuable forage species such as *Botriochloa ischaemum* [10, 15] with 30% participation, *Filago arvensis* (12.5%), *Torilis arvensis* (4.1%), *Eryngium campestre* (2.9%) and other weeds from the treeless grassland were replaced in the ASPs by forage species such as *Lolium perenne* (40%), *Trifolium campestre* (8.3%), *Poa angustifolia* (3.6%) and other valuable species.

Finally, the participation from the vegetal layer of fodder species from ASPs is 2 times higher than in FP, the pastoral value is over 3 times higher and the production of green fodder and the optimal stocking rate are over 6 time higher.

For the plant samples collected from the ASPs and from the treeless grassland (FP), the following chemical parameters of feed quality were analyzed: crude protein (CP); crude fiber (CF); ash (ASH); fibrous fractions: acid detergent fiber (ADF), lignin detergent acid (LDA) and neutral detergent fiber (NDF); dry matter digestibility (DDM); digestibility of organic matter (OMD) (Table 4).

Table 4 presents information about each chemical component contained in the feed, analyzed independently. The average for each variant (FP and ASPs) and the differences between them are presented.

Table 4. The quality of the grassland fodder from FP and ASPs

Specification	FP	ASPs	Diff. +; -	%
CP	11.7	20.1	+ 8.4	172
ASH	7.4	10.8	+ 3.4	146
CF	40.0	29.9	- 10.1	75
ADF	45.0	35.7	- 9.3	79
LDA	6.6	3.8	- 2.8	58
NDF	74.8	61.7	- 13.1	82
DDM	38.1	65.1	+ 27.0	171
OMD	38.0	60.7	+ 22.7	160

Source: Own results.

In ASPs the crude protein content it is over 70% higher than in treeless grassland and the crude fiber 25% lower than in FP, which ultimately leads to 70% higher digestibility in ASPs than in FP.

All these data confirm the obvious superiority of the agrosilvopastoral systems [9 – 12] that must be maintained and expanded given the new trends in global warming.

Conclusions

- (1) The agrosilvopastoral system (ASPs) from Greci, located at the foot of the Măcin Mountains, is representative for northern Dobrogea.
- (2) The pastoral value of ASPs is 63 times higher, and the production of green fodder mass of 11 t / ha is 6 times higher than the nearby treeless meadow.
- (3) The results reveal the superior productivity of agrosilvopastoral systems that need to be maintained and expanded, as a complex ASPs can more easily overcome a period of global warming than a simple pastoral system with treeless grasslands.

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EVALUATION OF THE PRODUCTIVITY OF PERMANENT GRASSLANDS FROM LĂZĂRENILOR HILLS, BIHOR COUNTY, ROMANIA

Teodor MARUȘCA¹, Laviniu I.N. BURESCU²

Abstract. *The hilly grasslands from western Romania, located between the Apuseni Mountains and the Pannonian Plain, were less studied in terms of productivity, respectively pastoral value and green forage mass production. In this paper, the productivity of the grasslands was evaluated based on floristic surveys - performed between the years 2008 and 2011 in Lăzărenilor Hills area. The grasslands are located at altitudes ranging from 150 to 410 m, on flat land up to slopes of 30 degrees. The average vegetation cover is 87% with limits between 82-90%, comprising on average 54 cormophytes, the smallest number of species – 25, found in Caricetum brizoides and the largest comprising 115 species in Anthoxantho - Agrostietum capillaris. The highest pastoral value was 78.9 in Festucetum pratensis and below 5 in Caricetum brizoides, Caricetum hirtae, Juncetum effusi and Ventenato - Xeranthemetum cylindraceum, considered degraded in terms of forage quality and green mass production. The highest yield of 16-19 t/ha green mass was evaluated in Festucetum pratensis and Lolio - Plantagnetum repenti, which recorded an optimal loading with animals around 1.5 LU/ha in a season of 175 days of grazing. At the level of phytosociological alliances, the lowest productivity and grazing capacity were evaluated for Deschampsion caespitosae and Thero-Airion, with only 0.03-0.05 LU/ha. The data regarding the productivity of the grasslands are useful first of all for the elaboration of the pastoral arrangements and the proper management of the grasslands.*

Keywords: hilly grasslands, green mass production, pastoral value, loading with animals

2. Introduction

The evaluation of grasslands productivity is equally important as the knowledge of the vegetation in terms of the floristic composition of the grassy carpet [4, 10, and 17].

Until recently, the grass production of grasslands has been determined by mowing and weighing in protected areas, from where samples have been taken for quality chemical analyzes. As this classic method is more difficult to apply in the territory, a new method based on floristic survey has been developed to assess the productivity of grasslands [5].

¹Assoc. Prof., Ph.D., Eng., Senior Researcher, Research-Development Institute for Grasslands Brasov, Romania, Corresponding Member of the Academy of the Romanian Scientists (e-mail: maruscat@yahoo.com).

²Lecturer, PhD, Eng., University of Oradea, Department of Forestry and Forest Engineering, Oradea, Bihor County, Romania (e-mail: laviniuburescu@gmail.com).

Through this method, the productivity of some grasslands from different physical-geographical areas of our country have already been evaluated [6, 7, 8, 11, 12, 13, 15].

The present manuscript continues the evaluation for hilly grasslands, less studied so far, and will finally synthesize the results at the level of grassland habitats in the European sense for comparison and unitary description [14].

3. Materials and methods

In order to determine the productivity of the grasslands, the paper “Flora and vegetation of the Lăzăreni hills” was studied, authored by Laura Mariana Herman (2012), [3].

The author of the paper established the following practical phytocenotaxones:

- Cls. **MOLINIO - ARRHENATHERETEA** R. Tüxen 1937
- Ord. **MOLINIETALIA CAERULEAE** Koch 1926
- Al. **Agrostion stoloniferae**
 - 1. As. *Festucetum pratensis* Soó 1938
 - 2. As. *Caricetum hirtae* (non Soó 1927 nom. nud.) Dihoru 1975 em. Burescu 1999
 - Ord. **ARRHENATHERETALIA** R. Tüxen 1931
 - Al. **Cynosurion** R. Tüxen 1947
 - 3. As. *Anthoxantho - Agrostietum capillaris* Sillinger 1933
 - 4. As. *Trifolio repenti - Lolietum* Krippelová 1967, Resmeriňá et Pop 1967
 - Ord. **POTENTILLO- POLYGONETALIA** R. Tüxen 1947
 - Al. **Potentillion anserinae** R. Tüxen 1937
 - (Al. **Juncenion effusi** Westhoff et van Leeuwen ex Hejný et al 1979)
 - 5. As. *Juncetum effusi* Soó (1931) 1949
 - 6. As. *Junco inflexi - Menthetum longifoliae* Lohmeyer 1953
 - 7. As. *Holcetum lanati* Issler 1936 em Passarge 1964
 - Ord. **DESCHAMPSIETALIA CAESPITOSAE** Horvatić 1956
 - Al. **Deschampsion caespitosae** Horvatić 1930
 - 8. As. *Caricetum brizoidis* O. Rațiu 1966
 - Cls. **FESTUCO BROMETEA** Br.-Bl. et R. Tüxen in Br.-Bl. 1949
 - Ord. **FESTUCETALIA VALESIIACAE** Br.-Bl. et R. Tüxen in Br.-Bl. 1949
 - Al. **Festucion valesiaca** Klika 1931
 - 9. As. *Agrostio - Festucetum valesiaca* Borisavljevič et al. 1955
 - 10. As. *Poterio - Festucetum valesiaca* J. Danon 1964
 - 11. As. *Festucetum rupicola* Burduja et al. 1956
 - 12. As. *Botriochloetum (Andropogonetum) ischaemi* (Kristiansen 1937) Pop 1977
 - Cls. **KOELERIO - CORYNEPHORETEA** Klika in Klika et Novák 1941
 - Ord. **CORYNEPHORETALIA CANESCENTIS** Klika 1934

Al. *Thero - Airion* R. Tüxen ex Oberdorfer 1957

13. As. *Filagini - Vulpietum* Oberdorfer 1938

14. As. *Ventenato dubiae - Xeranthemetum cylindraceum* (Borza 1950) Sanda et al. 1988

Cls. *PLANTAGINETEA MAJORIS* R. Tüxen et Preising 1950

Ord. *PLANTAGINETALIA MAJORIS* Tüxen et Preising in R. Tüxen 1950

Al. *Lolio - Plantaginion* R. Tüxen 1947

15. As. *Lolio - Plantaginetum majoris* (Linkola 1921) Beger 1930 em Sissingh 1969

The statistical calculations were performed after the Braun-Blanquet appreciation scale with grades from “+ to 5” which was transformed into participation percentages, respectively coverage.

For the evaluation of the pastoral value (PV) the species from the surveys were assessed with quality indices F [1, 2, 5, 18 and 19].

Indices for forage value (F):

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|--|
| 1 = toxic for animals and humans; | 2 = harmful for animal products; |
| 3 = harmful grassy carpet; | 4 = poor forage value (ballast); |
| 5 = medium forage value (ex F1); | 6 = average forage value (ex F2); |
| 7 = good forage value (ex F3); | 8 = very good forage value (ex F4); |
| 9 = excellent forage value (ex F5); | X = species with unknown forage value. |

The pastoral value (PV) and the production of green forage (GM) were assessed after the method proposed by [5] and applied in previous manuscripts published in this journal [9, 16], therefore we won't detail it here again.

Based on these data, the optimal animal loading with animals or grazing capacity (GC) expressed in units of livestock (LU) per hectare is further determined according to the formula:

$$GC(LU/ha) = -\frac{GM(kg/ha)}{RdXGd} \quad (1)$$

where: Rd = daily requirements for grass for 1 LU, 65 kg, respectively 50 kg + 15 kg (30% - season climatic fluctuations and unconsumed remains); Gd = number of grazing days (season).

The evaluation of the optimal loading with animals was performed as follows:

Value LU/ha	Grassland assessment
0.01 - 0.20	Degraded (Degr.)
0.21 - 0.40	Very poor (VP)
0.41 - 0.60	Poor (P)
0.61 - 0.80	Mediocre (Med.)
0.81 - 1.20	Average (Av.)

1.21 - 1.60	Good (G)
1.61 - 2.00	Very good (VG)
Over 2.00	Excellent (Exc.)

4. Results and discussions

Any research considering the characterization of the vegetation in a certain territory, should first include the seasonal conditions specific to sites location. From this point of view, the Lăzărenilor Hills are located between the Apuseni Mountains and the Western Plain of Romania, with an altitude of 145 - 410 m, including from relatively flat lands to slopes with an inclination of 30 degrees on all exhibitions (Table 1).

Table 1) General data comprising the natural conditions and general vegetation cover of the grasslands from the Lăzărenilor Hills

No.	Plant species association	Altitude (m)	Exposure	Inclination (degrees)	Coverage with vegetation (%)
1.	<i>Festucetum pratensis</i>	160-270	E, SE, NE, NV	2-5	88
2.	<i>Caricetum hirtae</i>	180-270	E, SE, NV, NE	1-5	85
3.	<i>Anthoxantho - Agrostietum capillaris</i>	190-410	E, S, SE, NE, NV	4-18	90
4.	<i>Trifolio repenti - Lolietum</i>	160-280	Toate	7-18	90
5.	<i>Juncetum effusi</i>	150-270	Toate	1-8	87
6.	<i>Junco inflexi - Menthetum longifoliae</i>	150-210	N, NE, NV, E, S	2-8	83
7.	<i>Holcetum lanati</i>	150-300	E, S, V, NE	2-10	84
8.	<i>Caricetum brizoidis</i>	150-290	Toate	4-10	84
9.	<i>Agrostio-Festucetum valesiacae</i>	180-320	S, SV, V, E	7-10	90
10.	<i>Poterio - Festucetum valesiacae</i>	180-280	E, SE, S, V	1-15	82
11.	<i>Festucetum rupicolae</i>	150-270	Toate	1-9	84
12.	<i>Botriochloetum ischaemi</i>	240-290	S, V, NE	18-30	89
13.	<i>Filagini - Vulpietum</i>	190-290	S, E, V, NE	2-10	90
14.	<i>Ventinato dubiae - Xeranthemetum cylindraceum</i>	250-280	S, SV, V, NE, NV	2-10	88
15.	<i>Lolio - Plantaginetum majoris</i>	160-280	Toate	7-18	87
	AVERAGE	145-410	Toate	1-30	87

Source: Own results.

The most unfavorable stationer conditions are found in the association *Botriochloetum ischaemi* located on slopes with an inclination of 18-30 degrees and on eroded soils.

The average vegetation cover is 87%, considered quite good with a minimum of 82% in *Poterio - Festucetum valesiaca* and around 90% in several valuable associations.

Regarding the number of plant species (phytodiversity) in plant associations, an average of 54 taxa were found, respectively from 25 in *Caricetum brizoidis* up to 115 in *Anthoxantho-Agrostietum capillaris* (Table 2).

Another important element is the composition of the vegetation cover in plants with forage value and harmful plants.

Table 2) The phytodiversity and productivity of grasslands located in Lăzărenilor Hills

No.	Plant species association	No. of species	Coverage with vegetation		Pastoral value	Indices for forage green mass (GM)	Production	
			Forage	Harmful			GM/ha	%
Al. <i>Agrostion stoloniferae</i>								
1.	<i>Festucetum pratensis</i>	42	81.1	6.9	78.9	6.27	18.81	306
2.	<i>Caricetum hirtae</i>	36	5.5	79.5	3.5	0.31	0.56	9
Al. <i>Cynosurion</i>								
3.	<i>Anthoxantho - Agrostietum capillaris</i>	115	78,8	11,2	53,8	3,38	8,11	132
4.	<i>Trifolio repenti - Lolietum</i>	44	85,2	4,8	75,5	4,49	11,68	190
Al. <i>Potentillion anserinae</i> , Al. <i>Juncenion effusi</i>								
5.	<i>Juncetum effusi</i>	55	5.7	81.3	3.6	0.32	0.58	9
6.	<i>Junco inflexi - Menthetum longifoliae</i>	54	17.4	65.6	8.2	1.03	2.06	33
7.	<i>Holcetum lanati</i>	50	76.8	7.2	50.3	4.41	11.47	187
Al. <i>Deschampsion caespitosae</i>								
8.	<i>Caricetum brizoidis</i>	25	3,9	80,1	2,5	0,21	0,38	6
Al. <i>Festucion valesiaca</i>								
9.	<i>Agrostio - Festucetum valesiaca</i>	54	78.7	11.3	46.1	2.61	6.00	98
10.	<i>Poterio - Festucetum valesiaca</i>	70	71.3	10.7	39.0	2.13	4.69	76
11.	<i>Festucetum rupicolae</i>	79	74.8	9.2	40.3	3.52	8.80	143
12.	<i>Botriochloetum (Andropogonetum) ischaemi</i>	56	18.4	70.6	12.2	0.70	1.33	22

Continuation **Table 2.**

<i>Al. Thero – Airion</i>								
13.	<i>Filagini - Vulpietum</i>	49	7.8	82.2	6.6	0.34	0.61	10
14.	<i>Ventenato dubiae</i>	39	7.7	80.3	4.8	0.27	0.49	8
<i>Al. Lolio - Plantaginion</i>								
15.	<i>Lolio -Plantaginetum majoris</i>	37	82.0	5.0	74.6	5.77	16.73	272
	AVERAGE for plant species association	54	46.5	40.5	33.3	2.38	6.15	100

Source: Own results.

The most valuable associations, with the participation of forage species between 80 - 85% are: *Festucetum pratensis*, *Lolio - Plantaginetum majoris* and *Trifolium repenti - Lolietum*, with the highest pastoral value (75 - 79), the same associations recording also the highest forage green mass productions with values ranging between 12 - 19 t/ha.

The coverage with harmful vegetation (grasslands, animal products and toxic) with values around 80% is found in *Caricetum hirtae*, *Caricetum brizoidis*, *Juncetum effusi*, *Filagini - Vulpietum* and *Ventenato dubiae*, which print a pastoral value of only 3-7, with a green mass production of 0.4 – 0.6 t/ha, very weak.

At the level of phytocenological alliances that according to some authors are assimilated with grassland habitats, the highest pastoral value (PV) was found on *Lolio - Plantaginion* (75), followed by *Cynosurion* (65) and *Agrostion stoloniferae* (41) considered good to medium (Table 3).

Table 3) The productivity and optimal loading with animals of the studied grasslands in terms of phytosociological (habitat) alliances

No	Phytosociological alliances (habitat)	Pastoral value		Green mass production		Optimal loading UL/ha in 175 days	Coverage with vegetation (%)
		Ind.	%	t/ha	%		
1.	<i>Agrostion stoloniferae</i>	41.2	118	9.69	144	0.85	Average
2.	<i>Cynosurion</i>	64.7	186	9.90	147	0.87	Average
3.	<i>Potentillion anserinae</i>	20.7	60	4.70	70	0.41	Poor
4.	<i>Deschampsion caespitosae</i>	2.5	7	0.38	6	0.03	Degraded
5.	<i>Festucion valesiacae</i>	34.4	99	5.21	77	0.46	Poor
6.	<i>Thero - Airion</i>	5.7	16	0.55	8	0.05	Degraded
7.	<i>Lolio - Plantaginion</i>	74.6	214	16.73	248	1.47	Good
	AVERAGE	34.8	100	6.74	100	0.69	Poor-Mediocre

Source: Own results.

At the opposite pole we meet the alliances *Deschampsion caespitosae* and *Thero - Airion* with 3-6 PV index, 0.4 – 0.6 t/ha green forage mass, grasslands considered as degraded.

The optimal loading with animals in 175 days of grazing season at the most valuable alliances reached values between 0.9-1.5 LU/ha while on the degraded ones the values recorded ranged between of 0.03 – 0.05 LU/ha.

On average, on the grasslands from Lăzărenilor Hills, an index of 35 PV was evaluated with a production of 6.7 t/ha of green forage that allows a loading with animals of 0.7 UL/ha in a season of 175 days of grazing.

Conclusions

- (1). The hilly grasslands located on the west side of the country showed a high phytodiversity scoring between 25-115 plant species, with an average number of 54 cormophytes being identified in the study area.
- (2). The average pastoral value is 33, showing large differences between the grassland associations, with values between 2.5 for *Caricetum brizoidis* and 79 for *Festucetum pratensis*.
- (3). The highest forage green mass production of almost 10 t/ha and a loading with animals of 0.9 LU/ha was evaluated at the *Cynosurion* and *Agrostion stoloniferae* alliances.
- (4). The lowest production of 0.4 – 0.6 t/ha with a loading with animals of 0.03 – 0.05 LU/ha was found at *Deschampsion caespitosae* and *Thero – Airion*.
- (5). The average grazing capacity on Lăzărenilor Hills for the conservation of current biodiversity must not exceed 0.7 LU/ha in 175 days grazing season.

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STUDIES CONCERNING THE RESIDUAL EFFECT OF FERTILIZATION AND AMENDMENTS ON THE FLORISTIC COMPOSITION AND PRODUCTIVITY OF SUBALPINE GRASSLANDS

Teodor MARUȘCA¹

Abstract. *This manuscript aims to provide a first study on the effect of long-term (12 years) calcium amendment and chemical and organic fertilization (sheepfold) on the subalpine grasslands located in the Bucegi Mountains (at 1800 m altitude). The productivity of the improved grasslands was determined on the basis of floristic survey and specific pastoral indices. The results achieved highlighted increases in the pastoral value which doubled its value from 34 on control plot compared with the plots treated with amendment and fertilization. The green mass production increased threefold from 2.76 t/ha at the control plot compared to the calcium amended and chemically or organically fertilized plots. Our results evaluated a possible dairy milk production of 2,500 - 3,500 liters per hectare in a season of 85 days as a result of feeding animals with grass from the pasture, under the open sky. Calcium amendment and sheepfold treatments seemed to have the highest economic effect in the conditions specific to the subalpine floor of the Carpathians Mountains.*

Keywords: *Nardus stricta* grasslands, calcium amendments, chemical fertilization, sheepfold, dairy milk

5. Introduction

The subalpine grasslands found in the Romanian Carpathians, located at altitudes ranging between 1,600 - 1,800 m up to 2,000 - 2,200 m, and comprising an area of 200 - 250 thousand hectares, resulted mainly from the deforestation of spruce rarities (*Picea excelsa*) and juniper bushes (*Pinus mugo*) [1].

A large percentage of these grasslands comprise a degraded vegetation cover, caused mainly by the invasion of *Nardus stricta* non-valuable species, and thus require the application of improvement methods [12].

The most well-known methods for grassland improvement include the fertilization with chemical fertilizers and sheep folding, as well as calcium amendment used to correct the acid reaction of the soil [4, 5, 6, 7].

The reevaluation of some old data sets on the residual effect of fertilization and amendment was made through floristic survey and by establishing some pastoral

¹Senior Researcher, PhD, Eng. Research-Development Institute for Grasslands Brasov, Romania, Corresponding member of Academy of Romanian Scientists (e-mail: maruscat@yahoo.com).

coefficients for milk production for the subalpine floor [9, 10]. Thus, this manuscript provides for the first time a productivity assessment of the subalpine grasslands located on Bucegi Mountains (improved by fertilization and amendment) on the basis of floristic surveys and pastoral coefficients.

6. Material and methods

The studies were performed within the Mountain Research Base Blana-Bucegi, on a degraded subalpine *Nardus stricta* grassland, located at 1,800 m altitude, on the territory of Moroieni commune, Dâmbovița County.

The experimental design comprising a bi-factorial experience (2 x 3), 18 m²/plot/replicate includes:

Factor A: Calcium amendment

1. Control plot
2. Amended at 2/3 Ah (7,5 t/ha CaO)

Factor B: Fertilization

1. Control plot
2. Fertilized with 150 N + 50 P₂O₅ + 50 K₂O, three years consecutive
3. Sheepfold 5 nights/one adult sheep/m²/one time.

The correction of soil acidity through amendments and sheepfolds were performed in the spring of the year 1996. The treatments with chemical fertilizers were applied in the years 1996, 1997 and 1998 as follows: fertilization with phosphorus and potassium was done in autumn; fertilization with nitrogen was made in the spring. The capitalization of grassland production relied on grazing with dairy cows.

The floristic surveys were performed for all the experimental plots, comprising a period of 12 years (between the years 1997-2008). The floristic surveys were made after the KLAPP-ELEMBERG method.

Considering the large volume of collected data, the floristic surveys were grouped for 3 years, respectively the first 3 years (1997-1999) were used for assessing the immediate effect on grassland productivity while the following 3 years (2000 - 2008) were used for assessing the residual effect of the experimental factors studied. Due to the prolonged effect of amendments, sheep folding and even chemical fertilization, an assessment of productivity for the improved grassland was finally made considering the entire experimental period.

The evaluation of grassland productivity was made after a new method based on floristic surveys which scores some forage quality and green mass indices to the species found in the grassy carpet.

The optimal loading with animals was made on the basis of forage green mass production (GM), after the formula (1):

$$UL/ha = - \frac{GM(kg/ha)}{\text{Grazing period(days)} \times 65kg/head/day} \quad (1)$$

The production of dairy milk per ha was calculated considering the pastoral value (PV) multiplied with the pastoral coefficient - for subalpine grassland - for milk (51.24, statistically assured), comprising a period of 20 years.

7. Results and discussions

Soil agrochemical properties changed as a result of calcium amendments and sheep folding applied in the year 1996 and under the influence of chemical fertilization with NPK for 3 consecutive years (Table 1).

Table 4) Soil agrochemical composition on 15 cm layer, as influenced by amendments and fertilization applied to subalpine grasslands from Blana - Bucegi 2000

Specification	UM	Experimental plot								Difference A2-A1	
		A1 without amendments				A2 with amendments					
		Mt.	NPK	Org.	Average	Mt.	NPK	Org.	Average	+	%
pH in H ₂ O	Ind.	4.8	4.8	4.9	4.8	5.4	5.7	6.3	5.8	+1.0	121
VAh	%	25.7	26.6	30.0	27.4	51.7	60.7	85.3	65.9	+38.5	241
IN	%	14.04	14.4	14.25	14.1	13.71	13.82	11.66	11.06	-1.05	93
Humus	Ind.	3.61	3.73	4.27	3.87	7.09	8.39	9.94	8.47	+4.60	219
P ₂ O ₅	ppm	19.8	25.0	27.0	23.9	23.5	31.0	28.0	27.5	+3.6	115
K ₂ O	ppm	90	103	134	109	133	119	150	134	+25	123
Al ⁺³	me/ 100g	4.16	4.14	3.86	4.05	1.00	0.40	0	0.47	-3.68	12

Our results show that the amendment application increased soil reaction with a pH unit from 4.8 (very acid) to 5.8 (moderate acid). This treatment affected also the

degree of saturation with basis (V_{Ah}) which increased two times, and the P and K content which increased with 15-23% compared to the control plot, without amendment application. A very important indicator which in high amounts could be toxic for plants is the mobile aluminum. The results recorded in this experiment showed that the plots treated with amendments scored a lower mobile aluminum content, from 4.16 me/100 g soil on experimental plot 11 (control plot, without treatment) up to 0 me/100 g soil on experimental plot 23 (amended and sheep folded).

The results of floristic surveys highlighted 30 plant species important for the grassy carpet, including 12 plant species from *Poaceae* family, 1 from *Fabaceae* and 17 from other botanical families (Table 2).

The average data recorded during the first three experimental years highlighted a regression in *Nardus stricta* species, from 35.5% until 18.0% as a result of amendments, and until 1.6% as a result of chemical fertilization with NPK. In the same time our results pointed out that the application of amendments and sheep folding resulted in the disappearance of *Nardus stricta* species from the experimental plot.

Table 5) Floristic composition and productivity assessment of the ameliorated grassland in the first 3 experimental years (1997-1999) (% participation) Blana-Bucegi

Plant species	Indices		Experimental plot					
	F	M	Without amendments			Amended		
			11 (Ct.)	12 (NPK)	13 (sheepfold)	21 (Ct.)	22 (NPK)	23 (sheepfold)
<i>Poaceae</i>								
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	7	5	-	-	2.6	-	3.0	4.6
<i>Agrostis rupestris</i>	5	1	11.9	8.1	1.3	12.0	4.5	1.4
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	5	3	0.1	1.4	2.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
<i>Deschampsia caespitosa</i>	3	0	-	0.1	1.3	-	1.1	0.9
<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	4	3	4.3	2.3	0.9	2.6	0.5	1.4
<i>Festuca nigrescens</i>	7	5	1.1	5.1	26.0	1.3	12.1	17.6
<i>Festuca ovina</i>	5	4	6.2	23.5	6.5	8.8	7.0	2.3
<i>Nardus stricta</i>	3	0	35.5	1.6	1.3	18.6	0.1	-
<i>Phleum alpinum</i>	6	3	2.0	9.5	4.3	2.1	10.1	6.0
<i>Poa annua</i>	7	2	-	-	0.4	-	-	5.1
<i>Poa media</i>	5	2	10.0	32.4	12.1	11.6	13.7	10.2
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	8	6	-	-	9.9	5.5	5.0	3.7
<i>Fabaceae</i>								
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	8	5	3.6	0.5	11.2	15.1	20.1	23.2

Table 2 continuation

Plant species	Indices		Experimental plot					
	F	M	Without amendments			Amended		
			11 (Ct.)	12 (NPK)	13 (sheep folding)	21 (Ct.)	22 (NPK)	23 (sheep folding)
<i>Other botanical families</i>								
<i>Achillea stricta</i>	6	6	-	0.1	-	-	-	-
<i>Alchemilla xanthochlora</i>	6	2	.	.	0.4	.	.	.
<i>Campanula abietina</i>	3	0	0.6
<i>Campanula serrata</i>	3	0	0.1	.	0.9	0.5	1.0	1.0
<i>Cerastium fontanum</i>	3	0	0.1	0.1	1.7	0.5	3.0	2.3
<i>Geum montanum</i>	3	0	0.1	0.1	.	0.1	0.1	0.1
<i>Hieracium aurantiacum</i>	4	2	0.6	0.1	.	0.6	0.1	.
<i>Ligusticum mutellina</i>	7	1	8.1	10.4	10.8	17.5	13.2	13.0
<i>Luzula multiflora</i>	4	2	0.1	.	.	0.1	.	0.1
<i>Polygonum bistorta</i>	5	4	.	.	.	0.1	.	.
<i>Potentilla ternata</i>	3	0	10.4	4.5	3.9	2.7	5.1	2.8
<i>Ranunculus montanus</i>	1	0	0.1	0.1	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.5
<i>Stellaria graminea</i>	1	0	.	.	0.1	.	.	0.5
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	7	3	.	.	1.3	.	.	2.8
<i>Veratrum album</i>	1	0	0.1
<i>Veronica chamaedris</i>	3	0	.	.	0.4	.	.	0.1
<i>Viola declinata</i>	4	1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Forage species	x		53.0	93.4	90.0	77.4	89.5	91.7
Harmful species	x		47.0	6.6	10.0	22.6	10.5	8.3
Pastoral value	(ind)		34.0	56.6	66.6	53.9	65.5	70.0
Relative value	%		100	166	196	159	193	206
Forage production	GM t/ha		2.76	5.46	8.38	4.82	7.49	8.04
Relativ value	%		100	198	304	175	271	291

As showed in Table 2, some more rustic forage species such as: *Agrostis rupestris* and *Deschampsia flexuosa* showed significant decreases in their participation in the vegetation cover.

The fertilization with NPK seemed to be favoring the appearance of *Poa media*, *Festuca ovina* and *Phleum alpinum* species, whereas the sheep folding applied on a calcium amended grassland showed to have a positive effect on the appearance of *Trifolium repens*, *Festuca nigrescens*, *Poa pratensis*, *Agrostis capillaris* and *Ligusticum mutellina*, which are also the most valuable forage species found in subalpine grasslands. Our results showed that generally fertilization and amendment reduced the share of harmful species in the vegetation cover from approx. 47% to 7 -10%.

The amelioration treatments applied to grasslands seemed to be influencing the appearance of some harmful species such as *Deschampsia caespitosa*, *Cerastium fontanum* and *Veratrum album*.

The forage quality of the vegetation cover (expressed by the pastoral value) increased with 160 - 200% on the experimental plots fertilized with chemical and organically fertilizers, reaction found especially on the amended plots, compared with plot 11 (control) where the pastoral value was 34.

Following the same pattern, the average green forage mass production for the years 1997 - 1999 was estimated at 2.76 t/ha for the control plot (11) and increased with 175 - 300% on the fertilized plots, especially on plots with sheep folding.

The remaining effect expressed by the improvement factors for the next 9 years (2000 - 2008) - on sets comprising the averages for three years - is presented forward.

The evolution of the pastoral value on plots without amendments (10) decreased by 16% until the period 2006 - 2008 while on amended plots (20) remained almost constant even after 12 years from the application of calcium oxide (Table 3).

Table 6) The remaining effect of fertilization and amendments on the pastoral value of the ameliorated *Nardus stricta* subalpine grasslands

Experimental plot	1997-1999	2000-2002	2003-2005	2006-2008	Average	%
11	34.0	39.4	42.9	37.6	38.5	100
12	56.6	49.9	47.3	43.7	49.4	128
13	66.6	65.6	56.7	51.1	60.0	156
10 years average	52.4	51.6	49.0	44.1	49.3	x
Evoluția (%) →	100	98	94	84	x	x
21	53.9	61.8	55.1	58.5	57.3	100
22	65.5	66.7	57.0	62.2	62.9	110
23	70.0	69.9	65.6	70.0	68.9	120
20 years average	63.1	66.1	59.2	63.6	63.0	x
Evolution (%) →	100	105	94	101	x	x
Difference +,- ; 20 - 10	+ 10.7	+ 14.5	+ 10.2	+ 12.5	+ 13.7	x
Amendment effects (%)	120	128	121	144	128	x

The results recorded during the experimental period showed a constant effect of the amendment, which lead to increases from 20% in the first experimental stage (1997 -1999) up to 44% in the last experimental stage (2006 - 2008), compared to the results recorded on the experimental plots without amendments.

Analyzing the results achieved among the 12 experimental years we observed that the most effective treatment aiming to improve the pastoral value was amendment combined with sheep folding (plot 23) where we found an average PV of almost 70, very good for the natural conditions specific to the subalpine floor. A very similar effect of the treatments was noticed also for green mass production (Table 4).

Table 7) The remaining effect of fertilization and amendments on forage green mass production of the ameliorated subalpine grasslands

Experimental plot	1997-1999	2000-2002	2003-2005	2006-2008	Average	%
11	2.76	3.63	3.89	3.82	3.52	100
12	5.46	4.60	4.55	3.65	4.57	130
13	8.38	8.09	5.82	5.32	6.90	196
10 years average	5.53	5.44	4.75	4.26	5.00	x
Evoluția (%) →	100	98	86	77	x	x
21	4.82	7.44	5.15	6.83	6.06	100
22	7.49	7.82	7.32	6.69	7.33	121
23	8.04	8.93	8.38	8.18	8.38	138
20 years average	6.78	8.06	6.95	7.23	7.26	x
Evolution (%) →	100	119	103	107	x	x
Difference +,- ; 20 - 10	+ 1.25	+ 2.62	+ 2.20	+ 2.97	+ 2.26	x
Amendment effects (%)	123	148	146	170	145	x

A similar reaction of green mass production like that presented for the previous experimental stage was found also on the final experimental period stage. Thus, on the experimental plot without amendments (10) the green mass production decreased with 23% while on the plots amended (20) an increase with 7% was recorded, a fact less highlighted in the scientific literature.

Following the same pattern, we recorded a 12 years average GM higher than 8 t/ha for the amended and sheep folding plots (23), which seemed to be three times higher than the average GM reached on the control plot (11) during the years 1997 - 1999.

A final comparative analysis was made for the potential dairy milk production and for the optimal loading with animals (Table 5).

By applying the formulas presented in the Material and method section – formulas for calculating the grazing capacity and for the evaluation of dairy milk production - the importance of the calcium amendment for correcting soil acidity and the special effect of organic fertilization by sheep folding is highlighted once again.

Table 8) The grazing capacity and the dairy milk production recorded on the ameliorated subalpine grasslands Blana-Bucegi 1997- 2008

Improvement treatments plot	Grazing capacity for 85 days (UL/ha)	Dairy milk production l/ha
10. Without calcium amendments		
11 – unfertilized plot	0.64	1,970
12 – fertilized with chemical fertilizers N ₁₅₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂ kg/ha, for 3 consecutive years	0.83	2,530
13 – sheepfold 5 nights/1 sheep/m ²	1.25	3,070
10 years average	0.91	2,520
20. With amendments on 2/3 Ah (7,5 t/ha CaO)		
21 - unfertilized	1.10	2,940
22 – fertilized with NPK	1.33	3,220
23 - sheepfold	1.52	3,530
20 years average	1.32	3,230
Difference 20-10 +; -	+ 0.41	+ 720
(%)	145	128

As demonstrated by our results, the 12 years average for dairy milk production per hectare can be increased from 1,970 to 2,940 liters, which is translated in almost 1.000 liters/year, only by amendments and rational grazing, and thus justifying the economically advantages of these technological measures which expressed a long time effect.

Considering the same experimental period we observed that sheep folding applied on grasslands without amendments enhanced an extra 500 l/ha dairy milk production increase, while for the amended grassland the increase recorded was only with 300 l/ha dairy milk production. Comparing these results with those recorded for the fertilized plots we noticed that the fertilization with NPK seems to be less efficient on a long term basis, requiring a more frequently application of chemical fertilizers.

In the strategy developed for improving these subalpine grasslands with soils with extremely low supply in nutrients, we can cover for the beginning only 15 - 20% of the grassland surface by sheep folding, for the rest of the grassland being necessary to apply chemical fertilizers combined with amendments.

Conclusions

- (1) The subalpine grasslands from Carpathians Mountains showed to be low productive mainly because of soils high acidity, low supply with nutrients and irrational grazing.
- (2) The application of calcium amendment and of fertilization with chemical or organically fertilizers through sheep folding, resulted in significant improvements in the vegetation cover of grasslands dominated by *Nardus stricta*, improvement highlighted through the expansion of some valuable forage species like *Agrostis capillaris*, *Festuca nigrescens*, *Poa pratensis*, *Trifolium repens* and others.
- (3) The best results were reached on the experimental plots amended on 2/3 Ah (7.5 t/ha CaO), fertilized for 3 consecutive years with N₁₅₀ P₂₂ K₄₂ kg/ha or with sheep folding for 5 nights/1 sheep/m², treatments which delivered a loading with animals of 0.8-1.5 UL/ha for 85 grazing days and a 12 years average dairy milk production ranging between 2,500-3,500 l/ha, results translated as being very economic for the subalpine grasslands studied.

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DEVELOPING EUROPEAN MOUNTAIN ENTREPRENEURSHIP THROUGH EMPLOYMENT SUSTAINABILITY. REALITIES AND PERSPECTIVES 2030

Brîndușa COVACI¹, Radu BREJEA², Mihai COVACI³

Abstract. *Mountain entrepreneurship is a defining dimension of scientific research on the mountain economy. At European level, the general situation of mountain entrepreneurship is ensured through defining business coordinates, such as the population of active enterprises and the degree of employability in the mountain area. The fluctuations of the mentioned coordinates characterize the general picture of the mountain entrepreneurship. The paper presents the degree of employability in the mountain area, establishing what are the current realities and forecasts for 2030. The statistical data are taken from Eurostat and processed in SPSS, respectively Excel. The results of the study show that the economy of mountain areas, especially mountain entrepreneurship, has developed significantly in recent years. The perspectives for the year 2030 present the defining ascending mountain area both in terms of the indicators regarding the population of active enterprises, as well as those related to the degree of employability.*

Keywords: European mountain entrepreneurship, mountain employee, employment and sustainability, mountain industry, mountain services

8. Introduction

The development trends of mountain entrepreneurship are supported by the major investments made for this area, but also by ensuring the repopulation of mountain areas. At the level of the European Union, the mountain area is considered to have a special potential for organic farming and human health, the air-water-soil ecosystem of this area being less polluted than the other relief areas. This is also the reason why European countries have legislated on issues related to the mountain area, as no other country or group of countries outside Europe has specific mountain regulations. Europeans believe in the development of the economy through the sustainability of mountain science. In this context, mountain entrepreneurship, especially on employability, is a permanent subject of studies and applications for the public and corporate governance of European countries.

¹Assoc. Prof., PhD, & Senior Researcher, PhD student, Centre for Mountain Economy of the Romanian Academy & University of Oradea, Romania, (e-mail: covacibrindusa@gmail.com).

²Assoc. Prof., PhD, University of Oradea, Romania, Corresponding Member of the Academy of the Romanian Scientists, (e-mail: rbreja@yahoo.com).

³Assoc. Prof., PhD, Hyperion University, Bucharest, Romania, (e-mail: mihaicovaci@gmail.com).

The mountainous area implicitly presents a socio-economic, cultural, natural and technological handicap. Mountain dwellers often assume this fact, being economically poorer than the inhabitants of other geographical areas.

Literature review

The mountainous areas of the world, especially in Europe, are rich in resources and represent cultural and spiritual icons, being mental magnets for tourism. The mountainous area of the world has sources with huge potential for energy, food, mineral deposits, especially due to the less polluted ecosystem. The imperative question is if the mountains are so rich in resources, then why are people poorer economically? Some researchers believe that there is a direct relationship between mountain entrepreneurship and the poverty of a mountain area. This translates into the fragility of the mountain environment; population vulnerable to external influences due to socio-economic marginalization; solving problems related to industrial exploitation, especially mining; legal inconsistency and incorrect application of existing legislation [5].

One of the best sectors in terms of European employability is tourism. Mountain entrepreneurs, implicitly the inhabitants of this area, are urged to orient themselves towards this field of activity.

Currently, tourism is developing through the prism of a better selection of products and services. Tourism presents special opportunities in mountain resorts. The mountain environment presents ideal conditions for outdoor recreation, and especially for tourism, if the population, public governance and private government converge actions towards a common ideal, namely the protection of mountains. Most mountain tourists, coming from polluted and crowded urban environments, want to access traditional destinations with a strong natural character. In contrast to the environment in which they cohabit daily, tourists from mountain areas want to spend their holidays in a calm and pleasant atmosphere. This is the reason why mountain tourists often prefer ecological and traditional recreation and accommodation spaces. Some mountaineers prefer to provide additional costs to certain services, provided that they adequately satisfy their tourist desires. This leads to significant price increases, reconfusing the demand-supply ratio and the price system in mountain areas for the peak period of mountain tourism. Subsequently, the economic system is recovering. These rapid fluctuations unbalance the mountain economy of areas with strong tourist and entrepreneurial potential [2].

The main resource for the development of mountain rural tourism consists of beautiful natural landscapes, ecological environment, historical monuments, local culture, traditions, food, etc. The development of rural tourism is based on cultural and historical heritage, exotic natural landscapes, tasting of local dishes made from organic agricultural products, etc. In this context, a special role should be played by coherent tourism development programs for mountain regions,

applicable locally, regionally, nationally or internationally, with the aim of strengthening the mountain economy of certain localities, regions or countries [7]. Mountain regions vary in terms of natural, cultural, historical and functional resources, some of which are more attractive than others. However, the proper promotion of tourism and the coherence of public governance activities, as well as the involvement of the population and private governance can lead to the progress of the mountain economy of disadvantaged regions. In addition, activities that develop unique proposals for a particular region need to be synchronized with national promotion activities so as to create a strong regional or country brand [1]. The Mediterranean mountain regions of Europe are experiencing a sharp decline due to competition between the tourism sector and the agro-forestry-pastoral system, the latter being at an economic disadvantage. The problem should not be overlooked as pasture-based livestock systems are relevant to the role in the management and conservation of large agricultural lands of high natural value in Europe, implicitly for the whole Community ecosystem. The problem is all the more acute as, under the given conditions, young entrepreneurs either remain in the mountain area and no longer want to get involved in the agro-forestry-pastoral system, or abandon the mountains to carry out activities in rural areas with agro-tourism potential. higher or in urban areas. In recent years, there has been a reduction in the primary workforce, caused by a significant increase in entrepreneurial activities belonging to the secondary or tertiary sectors, in particular tourism [4].

At the level of the European mountain area, competition between the primary sector of the economy (agro-forestry-pastoral systems) and the tertiary sector (ie tourism), has contributed to increasing the socio-economic vulnerability of mountain regions, environmental changes with negative impact on the ecosystem, reconfiguration negative impact of the landscape and the social disintegration of certain areas [6].

Another problem of the mountainous area in the poorer European regions is gender segregation and equality. The disadvantage of women is still among the main disadvantages of mountain entrepreneurship. Certain occupations remain for women in the mentioned mountain areas more a desideratum than a reality. Under these conditions, the actors influencing the mountain areas concerned should bring concrete solutions for the promotion of female entrepreneurship [8].

9. Materials and methods

The indicators studied are Employees of enterprises established in year t and Persons employed in enterprises established in year t . According to Eurostat [3], *Employees of enterprises established in year t* covers all persons who carry out a productive activity within the production limit of national accounts. Employees are either internal employers (persons working for a resident institutional unit and

receiving remuneration as employees) or self-employed (persons who are the sole owners or co-owners of the enterprises in which they operate, with the exception of those unincorporated enterprises which are classified as quasi-corporations or transnational corporations). The concept of domestic employer implies that the employment of both residents and non-residents aims to align the activity to the demand of resident producers. *Persons employed in enterprises established in year t* is the indicator which defined as the total number of persons working in an economic unit (including owners who are gainfully employed, partners in enterprises who regularly work in the economic unit they own and employees of unpaid family), as well as people who work outside the business unit and are paid by it for various one-off services (for example, sales representatives, delivery staff, repair and maintenance teams). This excludes labor provided to the unit by other enterprises, persons performing repairs and maintenance in the economic unit under consideration, as well as those performing compulsory military service. Studied sectors refers to Industry, construction and services except insurance activities of holding companies (I1); Industry (except construction) (I2); Construction (I3); Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (I4); Transportation and storage (I5); Accommodation and food service activities (I6); Information and communication (I7); Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities except activities of holding companies (I8); Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and support service activities (I9); Education, human health and social work activities (I10); Arts, entertainment and recreation, other service activities (I11).

Data simulation, in SPSS and Excel, return models for each European studied countries. The results, validated statistically, return no errors. Parametric analysis under ANOVA has been used for current data and forecasting analysis for forecasts data.

10. Results and discussions

According to Eurostat [3], in 2014 – 2018 period, the European mountain entrepreneurship regarding the employment fluctuate considerable. In general, most of the indicators presented above increase, meaning that the unemployment has been reduced in the European mountain area.

Employees of enterprises established in year t represent in the European countries people which migrate from other countries or lowland area, respectively I1 increase in Bulgaria with 8.56%, Czechia 2.64%, Spain 12.89%, France 2.35%, Croatia 4.96%, Italy 9.99%, Austria 6.49%, Portugal 14.81%, Romania 8.32%, Slovakia 9.05%; I2 in Bulgaria with 3.20%, Czechia 7.23%, Spain 14.29%, France -1.59%, Croatia -1.53%, Italy 4.93%, Austria 6.91%, Romania 4.11%, Slovakia 12.51%; I3 in Bulgaria increase with 4.90%, Czechia -1.49%, Spain

22.60%, France 0.94%, Croatia 5.86%, Italy -0.93%, Austria 5.12%, Portugal 7.99%, Romania 1.96%, Slovakia 13.61%; I4 in Bulgaria with 1.35%, Czechia -0.01%, Spain 11.40%, France -1.63%, Croatia -4.17%, Italy 6.35%, Austria 4.29%, Portugal 13.35%, Romania 5.19%, Slovakia 7.22%; I5 in Bulgaria with 8.82%, Czechia 11.53%, Spain 15.37, France 9.80%, Croatia 4.87%, Italy 13.28%, Austria -100%, Romania 27.99%, Slovakia 10.24%; I6 in Bulgaria with 9.74%, Czechia 9.34%, Spain 25.05%, France 9.91%, Croatia 16.84%, Italy 33.38%, Austria 7.42%, Portugal 30.41%, Romania 19.12%, Slovakia 35.40%; I7 in Bulgaria with 40.10%, Czechia 18.53%, Spain 19.39%, France 19.93%, Croatia 6.32%, Italy 13.81%, Portugal 41.54%, Romania 36.40%, Slovakia 36.84%; I8 in Bulgaria with 5.40%, Czechia -6.92%, Spain -4.32%, France -1.43%, Croatia 20.07%, Italy 1.99%, Austria -3.03%, Portugal -4.90%, Romania 22.81%, Slovakia 20.92%; I9 in Bulgaria with 22.13%, Czechia 13.81%, Spain 12.53%, France 4.27%, Croatia 5.25%, Italy 18.28%, Austria 15.97%, Portugal 26.85%, Romania 6.05%, Slovakia 19.65%; I10 in Bulgaria with 7.13%, Czechia -27.33%, Spain -8.23%, France 4.09%, Croatia 16.85%, Italy in 18.33%, Austria 4.06%, Romania 42.90%, Slovakia -39.33%; I11 in Bulgaria with 24.78%, Czechia -6.14%, Spain 35.93%, France 11.68%, Croatia 21.01%, Italy 13.73%, Austria -0.42%, Portugal 20.85%, Romania 9.01%, Slovakia 29.34% [3].

Horizon models for 2030 (Appendix 1) present forecasts with significant linear ascension based on mountain entrepreneurship investments.

Table 1. Horizon 2030, *Employees of enterprises established in year t - number*

<i>Model</i>	<i>2020</i>	<i>2025</i>	<i>2030</i>
Bulgaria-Model_1	1,618,272	1,853,505	2,088,738
Czechia-Model_2	464,803	482,613	500,422
Spain-Model_3	7,571,317	8,628,934	9,686,551
France-Model_4	2,328,910	2,395,348	2,461,785
Croatia-Model_5	217,370	232,087	246,804
Italy-Model_6	5,364,702	5,992,517	6,620,331
Austria-Model_7	1,533,069	1,644,349	1,755,629
Poland-Model_8	503,631	570,376	637,121
Portugal-Model_9	710,567	816,192	921,818
Romania-Model_10	1,239,730	1,369,111	1,498,493
Slovakia-Model_11	715,858	801,036	886,213

Source: Eurostat, 2021.

Research results show that Bulgaria will increase employees from 1,618,272 (2020) to 2,088,738 (2030), Czechia from 464,803 (2020) to 500,422 (2030), Spain from 7,571,317 (2020) to 9,686,551 (2030), France from 2,328,910 (2020) to 2,461,785 (2030), Croatia from 217,370 (2020) to 246,804 (2030), Italy from 5,364,702 (2020) to 6,620,331 (2030), Austria from 1,533,069 (2020) to 1,755,629 (2030), Poland from 503,631 (2020) to 637,121 (2030), Portugal from 710,567 (2020) to 921,818 (2030), Romania from 1,239,730 (2020) to 1,498,493 (2030), Slovakia from 715,858 (2020) to 886,213 (2030) as presented in Table 1 [3].

Persons employed in enterprises established in year t variate in the studied period for all the countries, thus I1 in Bulgaria with 9.53%, Czechia -4.98%, Spain 10.97%, France 5.47%, Croatia 3.97%, Italy 5.83%, Austria 5.91%, Portugal 15.44%, Romania 7.50%, Slovakia 9.08%; I2 in Bulgaria with 3.48%, Czechia 1.94%, Spain 12.87%, France -0.72%, Croatia -2.25%, Italy 3.22%, Austria 6.64%, Romania 3.82%, Slovakia 11.57%; I3 in Bulgaria with 6.06%, Czechia -3.13%, Spain 13.41%, France 3.05%, Croatia 3.96%, Italy -4.82%, Austria 5.41%, Portugal 8.89%, Romania 2%, Slovakia 13.60%; I4 in Bulgaria with 2.94%, Czechia -10.84%, Spain 7.15%, France -0.03%, Croatia -5.77%, Italy 0.10%, Austria 3.63%, Portugal 11.43%, Romania 2.84%, Slovakia 0.96%; I5 in Bulgaria with 10.08%, Czechia 7.14%, Spain 11.24%, France 14.15%, Croatia 3.80%, Italy 9.65%, Austria 2.66%, Romania 25.41%, Slovakia 10.74%; I6 in Bulgaria with 9.79%, Czechia -2.64%, Spain 17.94%, France 8.52%, Croatia 12.83%, Italy 20.25%, Austria 4.43%, Portugal 30.33%, Romania 17.26%, Slovakia 24.19%; I7 in Bulgaria with 40.40%, Czechia -3.14%, Spain 20.32%, France 19.23%, Croatia 6.26%, Italy 11.94%, Austria 17.99%, Portugal 40.30%, Romania 28.32%, Slovakia 33.27%; I8 in Bulgaria with 7.71%, Czechia -32.44%, Spain 3.42%, France 5.63%, Croatia 20.90%, Italy 1.26%, Austria -3.05%, Portugal 2.50%, Romania 22.28%, Slovakia 42.15%; I9 in Bulgaria with 22.75%, Czechia -7.89%, Spain 13.46%, France 10.37%, Croatia 5.94%, Italy 13.12%, Austria 12.94%, Portugal 25.50%, Romania 4.17%, Slovakia 21.05%; I10 in Bulgaria with 7.57%, Czechia -25.18%, Spain -4.83%, France 10.03%, Croatia 15.51%, Italy 15.52%, Austria 6.75%, Romania 38.30%, Slovakia -35.69%; I11 in Bulgaria with 27.22%, Czechia -16.55%, Spain 31.33%, France 13.04%, Croatia 26.05%, Italy 8.45%, Austria 2.01%, Portugal 23.57%, Romania 19.67%, Slovakia 27.38% [8].

According to horizon 2030 (Appendix 2), forecasts values show that the European countries will invest significantly in mountain entrepreneurship, especially in resident employee. According to the results Bulgaria will increase persons employed from 1,775,258 (2020) to 2,149,679 (2030), Czechia from 595,262 (2020) to 543,514 (2030), Spain from 9,371,157 (2020) to 11,627,330 (2030), France from 3,553,038 (2020) to 3,997,635 (2030), Croatia from 241,831 (2020)

to 268,669 (2030), Italy from 7,713,383 (2020) to 8,845,947 (2030), Austria from 1,822,695 (2020) to 2,071,478 (2030), Poland from 642,247 (2020) to 764,701 (2030), Portugal from 917,129 (2020) to 1,198,265 (2030), Romania from 1,409,017 (2020) to 1,700,254 (2030), Slovakia from 971,323 (2020) to 1,196,374 (2030) as shown in Table 2 [3].

Table 2. Horizon 2030, *Persons employed in the population of births in t – number*

<i>Model</i>	2020	2025	2030
Bulgaria-Model_1	1,775,258	1,962,468	2,149,679
Czechia-Model_2	595,262	569,388	543,514
Spain-Model_3	9,371,157	10,499,244	11,627,330
France-Model_4	3,553,038	3,775,336	3,997,635
Croatia-Model_5	241,831	255,250	268,669
Italy-Model_6	7,713,383	8,279,665	8,845,947
Austria-Model_7	1,822,695	1,947,087	2,071,478
Poland-Model_8	642,247	703,474	764,701
Portugal-Model_9	917,129	1,057,697	1,198,265
Romania-Model_10	1,409,017	1,554,636	1,700,254
Slovakia-Model_11	971,323	1,083,848	1,196,374

Source: Eurostat, 2021.

According to the data presented in the results, the current values of the *Employees of enterprises established in year t* indicator in the mentioned sectors and countries increases considerably in 2014-2018 period.

Countries with important rising for this indicator, as Austria, Bulgaria, Italy, Portugal, Spain and Slovakia (Fig. 1) will sustain employment for non-residents or people which return in their original countries (still having other resident or citizenship).

Persons employed in enterprises established in year t indicator display increasing values for all sectors and countries mentioned, but differently from the other indicator this one has a slower growing in 2014-2018 period. Austria, Bulgaria, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Romania and Slovakia will increase the persons employed indicator significantly, while Czechia will decrease mountain employment (Fig. 2). Countries with increasing values will sustain employment for residents or people from lowland area or Romanian citizens which return in their original countries and do not have any more other resident or citizenship.

Supply-production-distribution chains should be shortened so that the end product reaches the best product/service in terms of transformation in value chains.

Fig. 1. Horizon 2040, Employees of enterprises established in year t;
 Source: Eurostat (2021).

Fig.2. Horizon 2040, Persons employed in enterprises established-year t ;
Source: Eurostat (2021).

11. Conclusions

- (1) Forecast values for *Employees in the population of births in t – number* and *Persons employed in the population of births in t – number* show that European presented countries invest significantly in mountain entrepreneurship, especially in employment. Integration of the primary with secondary and tertiary sectors, mainly with tourism by ensuring functional synergies.
- (2) The specific solutions required for the development of large producing farms converge towards the evolution from an agrarian system to an agro-pastoral-tourist one.
- (3) Regarding the small farms and individual producers, the impossibility of developing their own agro-pastoral-tourist system leads to the idea of the progress of the tourist system of the respective mountain area to which entrepreneurs can join.
- (4) Classic economic chains need to be transformed into value chains with the added potential of mountain sustainability.

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GASTRONOMIC BIOHARMONISM

Romulus GRUIA¹

Abstract. *The paper underlines the gastronomy orientation towards science and equilibrium, compulsory under the conditions of today's world changes and legitimate desires to improve food quality, with impact on increase of longevity. The idea of gastronomic bioharmonisation is approached, having as declared aim the increase of food health generating capacity. The multiple integration with its effects is analyzed at environment "macro" level, as well as at "micro" level of the body. The paper makes reference to biostructural processes of biochemical and genetic nature. There are analyzed aspects of nutrigenomics by emphasizing food impact focused on the body genetic heritage. The bioharmonisation processes emphasized in this study have as landmark the concept of integronic food applied for an approach of the techniques concerning personalized gastronomy. The solutions of the study linked to gastronomic bioharmonisation show that, in order to avoid the paradoxical situation (of disharmony) when people will eat quantitatively enough, but will be hungry by using "diluted" nutrient food (especially micronutrients), the approach of multiple integrations (integrionic alimentation) becomes necessary in order to harmonize the food quantity-quality ratio.*

Keywords: alimentation, bioharmonization, food, gastronomy, nutrigenomics

12. Introduction

THE BIOHARMONIZATION of the living systems and of the planetary system in its whole is the method that pursues optimized balance of alternation (vibration) of ergo-material structures of these systems (informationally encoded), between **DYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM** with steady tendency to reverse the trajectory to a certain systemic estate (namely the living system *homeorexia* and respectively *georexia* on a planetary scale) and the moments of previous **EQUILIBRIUM OF STATIC STATE**, at initial conditions (namely the *homeostasis* of living systems in general and especially of man and, respectively, *geostasis* at planetary scale). The game of oscillating interconnections of this "georexia-geostasis" dynamic of states *de facto* generates "systemic harmony". Given the living systems specific to the planetary model, we are speaking about the „**complex biologic harmony of the living Planet**”, what we have named briefly the **BIOHARMONISM** phenomenon. Thus, it becomes possible to rediscover the unitary, balanced and

¹Prof. Ph.D. Eng. Transilvania University, Faculty of Food and Tourism, Brasov, Romania, Corresponding Member of the Academy of the Romanian Scientists, Associated Member of the Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences "Gheorghe Ionescu-Sisesti" (e-mail: romulus.gruia@gmail.com).

harmonized way of the reality of the 3rd Millennium world, especially characterized by the convergence of the *Biologic Revolution* with the ubiquitous *Informational Age*. Another characteristic of the present epoch is the rationality of resource consumption in relation to (sustainable) mankind development. All these are elements of complexity, they are systemic directions, largely revealed in **The Bioharmonism Theory** [13].

Obviously the *General theory of bioharmonism*, appealing to a number of scientific, but also empiric observations, may be applied and may solve different disharmonies at the level of and system, on the exes from general to particular and vice versa. In this general context we consider that an important field, beneficiary of the bioharmonic approach, is the agri-food system and the food manner characterized by the integral dimension of the *act of eating*. In the present paper we propose a study that approaches the third step of the food act, namely, after agriculture and food industry, we are referring to certain aspects of bioharmonization in the specific field of gastronomy.

Gastronomy orientation towards science is not only sensory opportune (as before), but compulsory in the conditions of today's world changes on multiple plans and legitimate desire of improvement of life quality and increase longevity

2. Materials and Methods

The paper studies the topics from the perspective of objectives and also based on methodological principles.

From this perspective, the proposed OBJECTIVE refers to *gastronomic bioharmonization in order to increase food health generating capacity*.

METHODOLOGICALLY, a direction concerning „bioharmonization” that we are approaching in the paper is on the line of *integronic food concept*, as well as the solution based on the idea and techniques regarding *personalized gastronomy*.

3. Results and Discussions

In the act of eating, food is the carrier of „*utilities*” that assist or serve man by: entries of sustenance -**S**- (with plastic role and one of body growth and restoration), by energy [**E**] entries (energy brought by food being in fact an essential element of metabolism, but also of the energy necessary to the individual and society), as well as receiving information [**I**] (by food sensorial values and others). Otherwise said, for the body “machine” food constitutes providers of bioenergy, of constructive substances and of useful information coming through sensorial channels that ensures a psychological satisfaction of food needs.

In the idea of counteracting disharmonies, such as, for instance, metabolic decompensations are, practically there is combined nutrition with metabolism,

especially from **epigenetic** perspective (genes achieve their phenotypical effects, that is the perspectives at AND level), aspects that are directly or indirectly influenced by environment factors [14], especially through the **food profile** both at alimentary level and at the level of integration on the axes „*Man-Food-Environment*”. These ones are possible in the conditions when, in fact, man is an informationally open system, with self-regulation, self-reproduction and antientropic evolution, that processes exogenous and endogenous information [1, 2, 4, 9, 10, and 15].

3.1. Elements of Intergonic Alimentation Concept

In this context, starting from the idea of the relation between **nutrition and metabolism**, there may be analyzed the totality of biochemical and energetic transformations that take place in the body biostructures [17] by the complex process of nutrition, in relation to **multiple integration with emergent effect (integronic process)**: with environment factors and, respectively, with the body itself. The taken into consideration “actors” are the main biochemical groups of macro and micronutrients, having as a “common factor” energy, all these being in interconnection between them, but also with the environment. The natural result is **bioharmonization**, i.e. *nutritive equilibrium and emergent dynamics* [6] in order to maintain life, estimated and analyzed at level of FOOD MATRIX [18].

We are talking about a system of nutritional processes, of different types of food, of multiple integration, of metabolism, respectively about catabolism and anabolism that goes on through a succession of a number of chemical reactions: hydrolysis, hydrogenation, desiccation, decarboxylation, deamination, transamination, esterification, condensation, polymerization and others [3,18]. The direct connection between all these and between food and the disharmony by the stress phenomenon, as well as between alimentation and incidence of degenerative metabolic diseases become, in fact, “civilization diseases”, such as: cancer, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, rheumatism etc. [1, 3].

Thus, in the bioharmonism process, the **food nutritional profile** becomes necessary, which may be expressed by different **indicators**: of nutritional density, of thermal density, glycemic index or load, antioxidant score, atherogenic index, Alkaline or acidifying biochemical profile [18]. What we are emphasizing by this study is the fact that, in case of processed, composite or complex food (dishes or menus specific to gastronomy), nutritional profiles are completely modified and different face to the nutritional profiles of integral natural food. This fact presupposes another type of analyses, based on matrix structure with components of nutritional and environment factors.

The food matrix represents the means by which alimentation is structured and is defined from the perspective of nutritive integration and harmonization. At

the basis of **alimentary matrix** analyses nutritive factors are grouped in order to ensure life, respectively: proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, mineral salts and vitamins. If we take into account that these ones are formed from simpler substances, the number of compounds individually well characterized and necessary to the body raises to approximately 70 – 80, from which 23 – 25 amino acids, 20 fatty acids, 6 “oze” substances, 15 – 20 mineral elements, 12 – 13 vitamins [3, 11, 12]. There are nutritive factors that exist **NEITHER** in pure form **NOR** single in nature, but only in certain associations that constitute **food**.

It becomes thus extremely important to study these associations necessary to provide population with covering foods in terms of nutrients. Their *harmonization* may be therefore analyzed by the alimentary matrix specific to every type of food, matrix of ever larger complexity, beginning with agricultural food, then the composite industrial ones up to the most complex ones from gastronomy. We are referring to the **integroneic dynamics** of the food act processes, taking into account its nutritive, metabolic, genetic and ecologic components specific to complex systems such as avoiding pollution (the known example being linked to the high level of CO₂ that may increase crops with about 10 %, but that reduce nutritive elements with 5-10 %).

THE CONCEPT OF INTEGRONIC ALIMENTATION is the scientific demarche that studies integrate food systems (due to their coexistence) and processes of *multiple integration in the idea of dynamic equilibrium*, having in view epigenetic elements (phenotypic modifications due to the environment) and of alimentary profile at individual or population level, considering *synchronic and syncretic* the dynamics of the act of eating, based on *synergic* effects and finally on *emergent integration*, leading to food quality of a superior order [12].

Fig. 1. Action levels in integroneic alimentation, i.e. successive integrations in an emergent process, with emergence of new aspects of a superior order in the dynamics of nutrient metabolism (source: Own concept).

There may thus be defined a series of processes of nutritional bioharmonization: nutrition of holistic type, particularized nutrition and different impacts of the food process, by a unitary and coherent concept of integronic alimentation, which obviously has forms of manifestation both at super individual level and at organic level (Figure 1).

The connections between food biochemical elements in relation to the interaction between environment, food and body induce the idea of multiple systemic integration, forming what we might call an **integronic matrix** necessary in nutritive equilibrium in order to keep alive animal bodies, by harmonizing processes of fundamental metabolism. In other words, this matrix may have different (multiple) integration levels, both at super individual level, where it takes the complex form of the *environment-food-body integronic matrix* and at individual level, where it constitutes itself in an *organic alimentary matrix*. These ones indicate the fact that there have been registered major progresses in understanding system biology, in the impact of environment factors and especially of the nutritive ones upon the body, mainly of the complex interaction between its components: genome, transcriptome, proteome and metabolome [1, 5, 7, 16, 19, 20].

3.2. Biostructurality - component of the concept of gastronomic bioharmonization

Within the **concept of integronic alimentation** and of biostructurality, there may be observed that individual variations, as a result of the impact of integronic dynamics, are mainly completely given by environment [*E*], the genotype [*G*] practically remaining unchanged [8,15]. The nutritive equilibrium especially changes because temporary environment changes. Thus, the *environment-food-body integronic matrix* may be altered and sometimes ended with severe disharmonies because of a number of environment factors, among which those linked to the intensity of the activity, to age, gender, health estate, the size of the analyzed group and, of course, to the type of food considered are more important (example: agricultural or primary food, industrial food or resulting from processes specific to food industry, composite food or complex dishes or drinks).

In gastronomy, in order to harmonize all these elements, with impact on every body, it is known that making a **menu** corresponding to the principles of scientific alimentation in fact means to find the modality to cover the physiological requirements at super individual level for a certain category of consumers [12]. The menu is thus achieved by nutritive corresponding food products or preparations, varied ones, with psych sensorial characteristics that may attract the

consumer by *taste harmony*, with satiety power and that may prevent the onset of hunger for 4-5 hours. Menus are addressed to a human population, respectively either to a *type group* of consumers (for ex. school canteens, restaurant canteens), or to *adult* consumer with average physical effort, as reference type [11].

The amount of culinary preparations consumed daily must include all groups of food in certain proportions in order to achieve nutritive equilibrium. There may be made *isocaloric* substitutions (between the same group of food) and *isotrophin* ones (between food from different groups, but equivalent concerning the nutritive value). The *recommended* percentage weight for different groups of food in the daily necessary energy is given in Table 1 [12].

Table 1. The structure of daily necessary energy of a **type menu**, on groups of food and macronutrients

No.	Group of food	Weight in menu (%)	Carbohydrates (C)	Fats (F)	Proteins (P)
1	Cereals and abducted	35	35	-	-
2	Fats	18	-	18	-
3	Vegetables - fruit	17	17	-	-
4	Milk and dairy products	2	-	-	2
5	Meat and meat products	8	-	-	8
6	Sugar and sugar products	8	8	-	-
7	Eggs	2	-	-	2
TOTAL		90	60	18	12

It is observed, as are commendation of *bioharmonization on integronic principles* that the share between macronutrients should be of „**C.60-F.18-P.12**” form (from table) as a landmark, respectively a standard menu with 60 % carbohydrates, 18 % fats and 12 % proteins. In fact we find again the traditional diet: 60-30-10, with recommended limits towards: 50-30-20.

It is obvious that, in function of numerous known factors, the proportion in the “*macronutrient trinomial*” (being in a permanent dynamics) has as effect the fact that shares “*slip*” towards one or another of the previously given and considered landmarks. This variation is also in function of the requirements of the consumer target, it is in relation to micronutrients (vitamins and minerals), but especially in relation to food energy drifted from dishes recipes or to the convergence of dishes from the whole of a menu. This well-known variability imposes to make different *food matrixes*, as a „complex system” to cover the integronic dynamics of all nutritive requirements (Fig.2) [12].

Fig. 2. The matrix of the complementarity of „the macronutrient trinomial C-F-P”,
With integrated result of energetic dynamics specific to the given food ration

From Figure 2 it results the pyramid that lays at the calculation basis of the caloric ratio of recipes and menus, as well as the location of the recommended report (the zone marked with three lines). On the other hand, alimentation bioharmonization may have multiple directions of action and integration, in function of the sustained alimentary philosophy.

Among these there may be reminded the most known directions, both bioharmonized and disharmonized (unbalanced, unhealthy ones) from figure 2:

- the philosophy of balanced menus (diet): landmark 40-30-30 (dashed zone);
- avoiding “hard” carbohydrate and fat menus (triple line zone on black background);
- hypolipidic diets, with reduced fat (on grey background):

86-8-6	70-10-20	66-8-26	54-12-34	46-8-46	34-12-54	26-8-66	20-10-70
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- hypoglucidic diets with low carbohydrates (the underlined ones):

<u>6-88-6</u>	<u>6-68-26</u>	<u>6-48-46</u>	<u>6-28-66</u>	<u>6-8-86</u>
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There must be mentioned that the model becomes more complicated in case that it is taken into consideration the micronutrient group, which implies in fact further research.

3.3. Gastronomic bioharmonism aiming personalized feeding

As a result of latest research, it seems that alimentation, as a main environment factor, has a much bigger role than it was thought on the body. That is why a basic side of gastronomic engineering that is growing at present is to keep in mind the *food impact focused on the genetic patrimony* of the body. In our opinion, this problem represents the starting point or the deepest manner to explain the other concepts that lay at the basis of the scientific and technologic demarche of gastronomic engineering on the direction of the metabolism bioharmonization for every organism apart.

The roots of the relation between genetics and alimentation are to be found even from the classic ratio established between genotype and environment, in the sense that the feeding manner is decisive concerning the environment impact on the genotype. A number of “invisible” effects of the feeding manner are noted and their consequences on long term upon human genotype.

Taking into account the fact that any organism represents the result of the *interaction* between its hereditary basis and the environment conditions, and among the ones first of all alimentation, this premise allows to make a basic division of the phenotypic value. On this basis it is more correctly understood the genotype notion and the environment one that represents a landmark in personalized gastronomy. Thus, we remind that genotype *[G]* is all genes possessed by an individual and that determines the appearance of a certain character, and *environment [E]* represents all the conditions that influence and determine transformation of the genotype in phenotype *[P]*. Therefore, the genotype gives a certain value to the individual and, concomitantly, the environment produces a deviation of this value in one direction or another direction. From here also the formula known for its phenotypic value, but applied here to food impact: $P = G + E$ [8].

In the sense of those shown, the genetic body patrimony reacts and is depending on the **type and quality of the food consumed**, implicitly on their specific concentrated energy. The simplified relation refers to the fact that food with high caloric density lead to growth of the body entropy (degradation of the system energy, measure that indicates the degree of organization of the system, in fact disorganization of the body), which in principle represent the element that leads to the appearance of diseases.

Without entering into details of nutrigenomics, we are mentioning in this context that there may be achieved the control of the genetic expression by a *single nutrient*, component of food and, as a rule, this control is complex, exercising by *interconnections* between nutrients (ex: retinoid and fat acids), or between nutrients and hormones (ex.: thyroid hormone and fat acids). Taking into account *synergy, equilibrium or ingredient counteraction* from **complex food (dishes)** or even from **menus** (i.e. all dishes served at a meal, practically representing **unitary hypercomplex food**), bioharmonization has in view variants for healthy consumers, or variants of *diets* (recommended diet for health recovery and maintenance) for consumers with certain diseases. Because of these reasons, the approached problems are very complicated, but with an immense potential in the realm of research and applications in research from Gastronomic Engineering.

Conclusions

(1) It is observed the tendency of evolution of present food towards menus poor in nutrients, i.e. dishes and raw food lacking more and more nutritive quality, so adding nutritive supplements becomes necessary. In order to avoid the paradox situation when people will eat quantitatively enough, but will be hungry by using nutritive “diluted” food or dishes (especially in micronutrients), the idea of **integronic alimentation** lays conceptual bases for the harmonization of the quantity-quality proportion.

(2) **Gastronomic bioharmonization** aiming to increase food health generating capacity in essence is based on the concept of integronic alimentation (i.e. multiple integrations with emergent effect) that may then generate technologies that lead towards the bioharmonization of the relation of food production, both concerning the impact with nutritive equilibrium and satiety, and the impact with the environment, by avoiding pollution.

(3) Operationally, gastronomic bioharmonization may be made especially on the direction when environment really enters the food equation and has as target personalized feeding (genome level) through the **integronic matrix** of achieving nutritive equilibrium necessary to maintain quality life, by harmonizing the processes of fundamental metabolism in relation with multiple integration at population level, complementary to the intraorganic level one.

(4) **Food biostructurality** is a component of gastronomic bioharmonization both concerning food and raw materials in culinary production and the menu in its whole, practically leading to the achievement of a combined texture of the *macronutrient trinomial*, which constitutes food (as hypercomplex food) with major impact on metabolic equilibrium.

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INSECT POLLINATION ECONOMIC VALUE OF AGRICULTURAL OILSEEDS CROPS IN ROMANIA IN THE PERIOD 2010-2020

Agatha POPESCU¹

Abstract. *The purpose of this research was to quantify and study the dynamics of the insect pollination economic value, vulnerability rate to pollinators decline, production/consumption ratio and matrix value after pollination loss for Romania's oilseeds crops: sunflower and rape in the period 2011 and 2020. The dependence ratio taken into consideration was 30% for sunflower and 25% for rape and also the average annual producer's price of the seeds was used in Euro/ton. The formulas used in this study are adapted. The results confirmed that insect pollination service had a positive economic impact increasing oilseeds production value in the year 2020 by about Euro 204.96 million in case of sunflower and by Euro 68.85 million in case of rape, summing Euro 273.81 million. The vulnerability rate to pollination decline in oilseeds crops was 28.57% in the year 2020. Production/consumption ratio of oilseeds was higher than 1 in the period 2013-2018, reflecting that in general consumption needs are covered by internal production, imports being rarely required. The matrix value after the pollination loss was below 1 in almost all the years. Finally, insect pollination service, especially provided by bees is very important in Romania for obtaining production gains and a higher seed quality, for increasing farmers income, for maintaining biodiversity, the quality of environment factors and the balance in the ecosystems.*

Keywords: insect pollination economic value, vulnerability rate, oilseeds crops, Romania

13. Introduction

Oilseeds crops are more and more important for their role in human diet, animal feeding, processing industry, energetic sector and from an agronomic point of view [33, 43].

That is why the world oilseeds production increased reaching 600 million MT in 2020, of which soybeans 63.8%, rape seeds 11.7% and sunflower seeds 0.5% [51, 54].

At the world level the main producing countries of sunflower are Ukraine, Russian Federation, Argentina, China and Romania and of sunflower seeds are: Canada, India, China and EU.

¹Prof. Ph.D. Eng. Econ. University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Bucharest, Romania, Full Member of the Academy of the Romanian Scientists, Corresponding Member of the Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences "Gheorghe Ionescu-Sisesti" (e-mail: agatha_popescu@yahoo.com).

The EU is an important oilseeds producer. In 2019, it harvested 29.5 million tons, of which 15.3 million tons rape and turnip seeds (51.8%), and 10.3 million tons sunflower seeds (34.9%), the two crops together accounting for 86.7% in the total output.

Since 2015, Romania is the top producer of sunflower seeds in the EU [14, 41]. The main producers of rapeseeds are Germany, Poland, Czechia, Lithuania and Romania (the 5th position) [9].

The relationship between insect pollination and agricultural performance in the vegetal sector is a good example of applied bioeconomy. As long as 80% of plants are pollinated by insects, of which 77% benefit of bees pollination, it is obviously that pollination is very important in sustaining life on the Earth [5, 6].

Sunflower and rape are among the crops whose production depends on pollinator services which are performed 70-85% by melliferous bees, bumbles and butterflies.

But, we must not forget that Sunflower (*Heliantus annuus* L.) and rape (*Brassica napus* L. and *Brassica rapa* L.) are meliferous plants belonging to the nectar-pollenous category which could produce 30-130 kg honey/ha in case of sunflower and 30-100 kg/ha in case of rape, reflecting their high importance in beekeeping [1, 5].

Bees are the most important pollinator, they could pollinate about 130 agricultural crops, the dependence degree varying between 30% and 100% depending on plant species, hybrid, technologies, climate etc and the economic value is estimated at Euro 153 billion per year [50].

In addition, the bees produce high value products (honey, pollen, propolis, royal jelly, venom, wax etc) [27, 28, 29, 30, 32, 36, 39, 42] sustaining beekeepers' income and their families welfare [31, 37, 38].

Also, bees are considered a biosensor of the environment providing precious information about the quality of the environmental factors. More than this, bees give their contribution to the maintenance of biodiversity and ecosystems balance [50].

However, the population of bees and other insects is affected by many factors among which agriculture intensification decrease pollinator richness and abundance and this is the reason why it is needed to evaluate the effects on crop production [2].

Also, the plant protection measures based on treatments with neuro-systemic insecticides (neonicotinoides) could have a lethal or sub-lethal effect which diminish the number of bees or disturb their normal life and behavior [50].

For this reason, the EU Commission has a new approach regarding the future of pollinators and the need for monitoring as they have importance for nature and human well-being [8].

The economic impact of pollination in sunflower crop depends on hybrid (Dag, 2002) and the existence of highly self-fertile hybrids [3], agronomic practices [7], crop rotation, sunflower attractiveness, nectar production, climate factors [52], floret size [49], local factors, landscape and habitat [2, 21].

The dependence degree of crop production on pollination differs from a crop to another because there are many ways to evaluate the dependency rate and economic value of pollination. Various researchers used in their calculations agricultural production measured in kg or tons/ha, number of seeds per plant, seed oil content, weight of 1,000 seeds etc. [2, 10,11, 15, 18].

The degree of dependence on pollination for sunflower crop for seeds is about 30-50% which means that for one ha it is needed 1-2 bee families to fulfill this duty. In case of rape crop for seeds, pollination could assure 25-50% production gain which means that about 4-5 bee families have to offer their service for one ha [14, 22].

Other authors opine that the use of honey bees in sunflower cultivated areas could assure a high number of seeds per flower, germination rate, oil seeds content and reduce the number of mal-formed seeds [19, 20]. Tesfay (2009) proved that honey bees could grow sunflower yield by 385 the mass of seeds, by 385 germination rate and by 36% oil content [53]. INRA, 2019 sustained that bee pollination could boost the profitability of oilseed rape [17].

Due to the existence of wind pollination and autonomous self pollination, the dependence degree of pollination of rape production is still discussed and unclear [12, 13, 26].

Yield increases could vary between 18% and 74% depending on the crop due to the pollination service made by insects [4, 19].

In this context, the paper aimed to evaluate the economic impact of insects pollination on oilseeds production in Romania suing as example the main two oilseeds crops: sunflower and rape. The period of study was 2011 - 2020 and the main indicators utilized were: (a) cultivated area, production, yield, average annual producer's price, consumption; (b) economic value of oilseeds production due to insect pollination; (c) production/consumption ratio; (d) vulnerability rate to pollinators decline and (e) matrix value due to pollinators loss.

The paper is an original one in Romania as no other similar studies were approached on insect pollination economic value in oil seeds crop growing, except in fruit trees growing [47].

2. Materials and Methods

The data were provided by National Institute of Statistics and Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development for the period 2011-2020 regarding the following indicators: cultivated area with sunflower and rape, seeds production by crop, yield by crop, average annual price at the farm gate by crop and seeds consumption by crop.

They were mathematically and statistically processed using the following procedures:

- *Fixed basis index*, $I_{FB} = (X_n/X_1) \times 100$, where X_1 is the level of the indicator in the year 2011 and X_n the level of the indicator in the year 2020;

- *Dynamic analysis* of each indicator in the interval 2011-2020 reflected by trend line regression equation and coefficient of determination;

- *Economic value of seeds production by crop and for the two crops*, EV, using the formula:

$$EV = \sum_{i=1}^n Q_i \times P_i \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

where: i = crop type, i_1 = sunflower and i_2 = rape; Q_i = production (tons); P_i = average annual seed price by crop at the farm gate.

- *Insect pollination economic value*, IPEV, was calculated according to the formula used by Gallai et al, (2009) [11], but adapted to the present study for two crops at the level of a country.

$$IPEV = \sum_{i=1}^n Q_i \times D_i \times P_i \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

where: D_i = dependence ration of crop production on insect pollination. in this study, D_i was considered 30% for sunflower crop production and 25% for rape production.

- *Vulnerability rate* of the agricultural crops to pollination decline caused by climate change and other factors, VR%:

$$VR\% = (IPEV/EV) \times 100 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i \times D_i \times P_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i \times P_i} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

- *Comparison regarding production/consumption* by crop, $\frac{Q_i}{C_i}$,

$$\frac{Q_i}{C_i} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i - C_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n C_i} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

where: C_i = seeds consumption of crop i .

- *The matrix after total pollination loss* (M), according to the formula:

$$M = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i (1-D)_i - C_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n C_i} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

The results were graphically illustrated and tabled and also explained. Finally, the main conclusions were drawn.

3. Results and Discussions

Romania has a high agricultural potential both in vegetal and animal production. However, during the last decade, vegetal production represents more than 60% in agricultural output value. The main crops cultivated by Romania are cereals (maize, wheat, but also barley, oats and sorghum), oils seeds crops (sunflower, rape, soybean), and vegetables. Maize, wheat, and also sunflower and rape seeds, a part of vegetables are successfully traded mainly in the EU [34, 35, 40, 41, 44, 45, 46, 48].

3.1. Cultivated area with sunflower and rape

Romania is an important EU producer of sunflower and rape seeds as reflected by the cultivated area. In 2020, sunflower was harvested from 1,170 thousand ha by +17.58% more than in 2011.

The surface covered with sunflower ranged between the minimum 995 thousand ha in 2021 and 1,283 thousand ha, the maximum level reached in 2019 (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Dynamics of cultivated area with sunflower and rape, Romania, 2011-2020 (Thousand ha)
Source: Own design and calculation based on the data from [23].

In case of rape, in 2020, the harvested surface accounted for 343 thousand ha being by -12.73% smaller than in 2011. In the last decade, rape was cropped on the minimum surface of 105 thousand ha in 2012, followed by an increase in the next years and then reached the peak of 633 thousand ha in 2018. Then, it substantially dropped by 45% in 2019 and 54% in 2020 (Fig. 1).

3.2. Sunflower and rape seeds production

Romania has a high potential for producing sunflower and rape seeds and the production performance allows Romania to be situated on the 1st position in the EU for sunflower and on the 5th position for rape [41, 43].

Sunflower seeds production increased by 23.19% from 1,789 thousand tons in 2011 to 2,204 thousand tons in 2020. Production varied between 1,398 thousand tons in 2012, a year with a severe drought and the maximum production of 3,569 thousand tons achieved in 2019, In 2020, production was affected by drought and fell to 2,204 thousand tons (-38.3%).

In case of rape, seed production was 728 thousand tons in 2020, by -1.495 smaller than in 2011. Rape performance was deeply affected by the bad climate conditions in 2012, when it registered the minimum level of 158 thousand tons, and also it recorded low performances in 2015, only 919 thousand tons, in 2019 just 798 thousand tons and in 2020 only 728 thousand tons. However, the peak of seeds production was 1,672 thousand tons achieved in 2017 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Dynamics of sunflower and rape seeds production, Romania, 2011-2020 (Thousand tons)
Source: Own design and calculation based on the data from [23].

These crops like many others are particularly sensitive to weather and climate conditions. Spring frosts, summer droughts, heat waves, heavy rainfalls produced significant production losses and compromised seed quality with a deep impact on offer/demand ratio and market price.

For its sunflower seeds production, Romania passed on the top position in the EU and at present has 35% share in the EU sunflower seeds output.

In case of rape seeds production, the country is situated on the 7th position after Germany, France, Poland, Czechia, Lithuania and Hungary [9].

3.3. sunflower and rape seeds yield

The average production per surface unit increased in case of the both crops in the analyzed interval, with a substantial impact on total production. Yields were deeply influenced by the cultivated hybrids structure and their production potential, technologies applied and meteorological and hydrological factors [33].

In 2020, sunflower produced 1,883 kg seeds per ha, by +4.72% more than in 2011, while rape carried out 2,124 kg seeds per ha by +12.85% more.

In case of sunflower, yield varied between 1,310 kg/ha, the minimum level, in 2012, due to the severe drought and 3,041 kg/ha in 2018, a favorable year.

In case of rape, the maximum level accounted for 2,835 kg/ha in 2016 and the minimum performance of 1,496 kg/ha in 2012 (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Dynamics of sunflower and rape seeds yield, Romania, 2011-2020 (kg/ha)
Source: Own design and calculation based on the data from [23].

3.4. Average annual sunflower and rape seed producer's price

Seeds price level was determined by supply/demand ratio so that in the years with a higher production, the price was lower, while in case of the lower production, the price level was higher.

In case of sunflower seeds, the price in national currency ranged between RON 1.58/kg in 2011 and RON 1.5/kg in 2020. The highest price was RON 1.84/kg in 2012 and the lowest one RON 1.26/kg and also RON 1.29/kg in 2019. The price per kg rape seed varied between RON 1.34 in 2014 and RON 1.83 in 2012.

In 2020, a farmer received in average RON 1.5/kg sunflower seed and RON 1.83/kg rape seed, by -5.07% less in case of sunflower and in case of rape by +12.96% more than in 2011.

In this study, the calculation is made in Euro, so that the average price was recalculated according to the average exchange rate Euro/RON provided by National Bank of Romania.

In the period 2011-2020, the national currency "RON" registered a depreciation versus Euro which has deeply influenced the price levels in Euro per ton as used in this research.

In case of sunflower seeds, the average price at farm gate was Euro 310/ton in 2020, by -16.85% smaller than Euro 372.8 per ton in 2011.

In case of rape seeds, the average producer's price accounted for Euro 378.3/ton in 2020, being by =1.03% lower than in 2011 when its level was Euro 382.2 (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Dynamics of sunflower and rape seeds producer's price, Romania, 2011-2020 (Euro/ton)
Source: Own design and calculation based on the data from [23].

3.5. Sunflower and rape seed consumption

According to Food Balances provided by National Institute of Statistics, seed consumption increased for sunflower and declined a little for rape in 2019 versus 2011.

In 2019, sunflower seed consumption reached 1,809 thousand tons being by +91.835 higher than 943 thousand tons in 2011.

In case of rape seed consumption, in 2019 it was achieved 492 thousand tons compared to 498 thousand tons in 2011, meaning by -1.21 less (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Dynamics of sunflower and rape seed consumption, Romania, 2011-2020 (Thousand tons)
Source: Own design and calculation based on the data from [24, 25].

3.6. Economic value of sunflower and rape seed production

This indicator was determined based on seed production, Q_1 for sunflower and Q_2 for rape which was multiplied by average annual producer's price in Euro/ton, P_1 for sunflower and P_2 for rape.

Economic value of seed production, EV, taking into account the both crops, registered a slight increase of only + 0.95% in the period 2011-2020. In 2020, it accounted for Euro 958.4 million compared to Euro 949.3 million in 2011.

However, the peak of EV was Euro 1,452.6 million registered in 2017, while the minimum value of Euro 642.1 million was noticed in 2012, the most unfavorable year for these crops and not only (Table 1).

Table 1. Economic value of seed production, Romania, 2011-2020

	Seed production (Thousand tons)		Average annual seed price (Euro/ton)		Economic value of seed production (Euro million)		
	Q ₁ Sunflower	Q ₂ Rape	P ₁ Sunflower	P ₂ Rape	EV ₁ Sunflower	EV ₂ Rape	Total EV
2011	1,789	739	372.8	382.2	666.9	282.4	943.3
2012	1,398	158	412.9	410.7	577.2	64.9	641.1
2013	2,142	666	359.8	366.3	770.7	236.6	1,007.3
2014	2,189	1,059	283.5	301.5	620.6	319.3	939.9
2015	1,786	919	337.5	369.0	602.8	339.1	941.9
2016	2,032	1,293	336.2	346.6	683.1	451.0	1,135.1
2017	2,913	1,673	300.0	345.9	873.9	578.7	1,452.6
2018	3,063	1,611	283.6	309.4	868.7	498.5	1,367.2
2019	3,569	798	271.9	345.6	970.4	275.8	1,246.2
2020	2,204	728	310.0	378.3	683.2	275.4	958.4
2020/2011 %	123.19	98.51	83.15	98.97	102.4	97.52	100.95

Source: Own calculation based on the data from [23].

3.7. Insect pollination economic value

Insect pollination economic value, IPEV, for sunflower, rape and total oilseeds crops was calculated based on the economic value of seed production multiplied by production dependency ratio of insect pollination which was considered 30% for sunflower and 25% for rape.

In case of sunflower, the economic value of seed production, IPEV₁, achieved due to insect pollination increased from Euro 200.07 million in 2011 to Euro 204.96 million in 2020 that is by +2.44%. This was due to the ascending evolution of sunflower seed production, which had a positive impact and by the decline in seed price, which had a negative effect.

In case of rape, the economic value of pollination on seed production, IPEV₂, registered a slight decline of -2.48% from Euro 70.6 million in 2011 to Euro 68.85 million in 2020. This situation was also caused by the dynamics of production and price elasticity.

However, taking into account the economic value of insect pollination, ΣIPEV, on oilseeds crops, it was noticed a growth rate of +1.16% in the whole studied interval from Euro 270.67 million in 2011 to Euro 273.81 million in 2020.

Therefore, in 2020, the farmers cultivating sunflower and rape for seeds registered an additional income of Euro 273.81 million grace to the pollination service made by insects, especially by bees whose contribution is about 80% in normal conditions (Table 2).

Table 2. Insect pollination economic value, Romania, 2011-2020 (Euro million)

	IPEV ₁ - Sunflower	IPEV ₂ -Rape	ΣIPEV
2011	200.07	70.6	270.67
2012	173.16	15.22	189.38
2013	231.21	59.15	290.36
2014	186.18	79.82	266.00
2015	180.84	84.77	265.61
2016	204.93	113.00	317.93
2017	262.17	144.67	406.84
2018	260.61	124.62	385.23
2019	291.12	68.95	360.07
2020	204.96	68.85	273.81
2020/2011 %	102.44	97.52	101.16

Source: Own calculation, original results.

3.8. Vulnerability rate to insect pollination decline

A general phenomenon is pollination service decline due to the reduction in insect population caused by many factors among which could be considered the implementation of the modern technologies based on self pollinating hybrids, the use of plant protection treatments with neuro-systemic insecticides (neonicotinoides) and climate change.

For this reason, it is important to evaluate the vulnerability rate to insect pollination decrease, in this study for the first time in Romania with the example on oilseeds crops sunflower and rape.

Vulnerability rate, VR%, reflects the percentage of decline of the insect pollination economic value if pollination service is diminished.

The calculation proved that in case of oilseeds crops in Romania, in the period 2011-2020, vulnerability rate increased from 28.51% in 2011 to 28.57% in 2020. During this interval, it was registered the highest vulnerability rate accounting for 29.49% in the year 2012 considered an unfavorable year due to climate conditions (a long and severe drought). The lowest level of the vulnerability rate was 28%, recorded in 2017 and 2017 (Fig. 6).

In Europe, a study made by Holland et al (2020) on pollination limitation in four entomophilous crops (oilseed rape, sunflower, pears and pumpkin) showed that pollination service on crops is worsening due to the decline of pollinators in farmlands, but because the reduction in sunflower and rape production was just 8% and respectively 6%, it was considered that "yields in these crops were not severely pollination-limited" in the six European countries taken into consideration in this research [16].

Fig. 6. Dynamic of vulnerability rate of oils seeds crops to insect pollination decline in Romania, 2011-2020 (%)

Source: Own calculation, original results.

3.9. Comparison between production and consumption of oilseeds

In order to assess the total pollination loss due to the decline in pollinators number, it was needed to determine the difference between seed production and consumption, respectively: $Q_i - C_i$, and the ratio between production and consumption: Q_i/C_i .

The results showed that Q_i/C_i in case of rape crop had higher values compared to sunflower, because the consumption of rape seeds is smaller than the one of sunflower seeds, and this happened in the period 2014-2018.

Table 3. Comparison between production and consumption for oils seeds crops in Romania, 2011-2019

	$Q_i - C_i$		$\Sigma (Q_i - C_i)$	ΣC_i	$\frac{Q_i - C_i}{C_i}$		$\frac{\Sigma (Q_i - C_i)}{\Sigma C_i}$
	Sunflower	Rape			Sunflower	Rape	
2011	846	241	1,087	1,441	0.89	0.48	0.75
2012	765	-103	662	894	1.21	-0.39	0.74
2013	1,373	450	1,823	955	1.79	2.08	1.91
2014	934	997	1,931	1,317	0.74	16.08	1.47
2015	812	865	1,677	1,028	0.83	16.02	1.63
2016	1,479	1,269	2,748	577	2.67	52.87	4.76
2017	1,035	1,574	2,609	1,977	0.55	15.89	1.32
2018	1,268	1,166	2,434	2,240	0.71	2.62	1.09
2019	1,760	306	2,066	2,301	0.97	0.62	0.89

Source: Own calculation and original results based on the data from [24, 25].

Analyzing Q_i/C_i for the both oilseeds crops, the results were higher than 1 in the period 2013-2019 and especially in 2016, when this ratio was 4.76, the maximum value. In 2011, 2012 and 2019, this ratio was smaller than 1 (Table 3).

3.10. The matrix after total pollination loss

Taking into account Q_i/C_i values and the dependence degree on pollination, it was calculated the matrix after total pollination loss according to Gallai (2009) formula, adapted for oilseeds crops in Romania.

The results are presented in Table 4 and show that M value was below 1 in almost the whole analyzed period, except the year 2013 when M value was over 1 and the year 2016 when $M > 3$.

Therefore, the farmers have to be aware of the importance of insect pollination in sustaining crop production, product quality, biodiversity of cultivated crops and insects world.

Table 4. Matrix after total pollination loss

	$Q_i (1 - D)_i - C_i$ (Thousand tons)		$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i (1 - D)_i - C_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n C_i}$ (Thousand tons)	$\sum_{i=1}^n C_i$ (Thousand tons)	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i (1 - D)_i - C_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n C_i}$
	Sunflower	Rape			
2011	309.3	56.2	365.5	1,441	0.2536
2012	345.6	-142.5	203.1	894	0.2271
2013	730.4	283.5	1,013.9	985	1.0290
2014	277.3	732.25	1,009.55	1,317	0.7665
2015	276.2	635.25	911.45	1,028	0.8866
2016	869.4	945.75	1,815.15	577	3.145
2017	161.1	1,155.75	1,316.85	1,977	0.6660
2018	349.1	763.25	1,112.35	2,240	0.4965
2019	689.3	106.5	795.8	2,301	0.3458

Source: Own calculation and original results based on the data from [24, 25].

Conclusions

(1) This research proved the first time in Romania that insect pollination service has definitely a positive economic impact increasing oilseeds production value in the year 2020 by about Euro 204.96 million in case of sunflower and by Euro 68.85 million in case of rape.

Therefore, the farmers have to make use of insect pollination service for obtaining production gain, additional incomes, for preserving biodiversity and protecting environment quality.

(2) In 2020, the value of the production gain for the both oilseeds crops: sunflower and rape, due to insect pollination accounted for Euro 273.81 million.

(3) The vulnerability rate to pollination decline in oilseeds crops in Romania was 28.57% in the year 2020, which is an alarm bell for taking measures to sustain pollinators, farmers, beekeepers, biodiversity and ecosystems.

(4) The production/consumption ratio of oilseeds was over 1 in the period 2013-2018, which is a positive aspect reflecting that consumption needs were well covered by internal production, imports being required only in the year 2011, 2012 and 2019.

(5) The matrix value after the pollination loss was below 1 in almost the whole studied interval, except 2013 and 2016 when it was higher than 1.

(6) As a final conclusion, insect pollination service, especially the one provided by bees is very important in Romania for the sustainable development of oilseeds production, for obtaining production gains and a higher seed quality, for increasing farmers income and profitability of their business, for maintaining biodiversity, the quality of environment factors and the balance in the ecosystems and for strengthening the good relationships between agronomists and apiculturists for sustaining both the vegetal agriculture and beekeeping sector.

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THE AVAILABILITY FOR CONSUMPTION AND THE EXPENSES FOR PURCHASING AGRI-FOOD PRODUCTS IN ROMANIA IN THE PERIOD 2014-2019

Agatha POPESCU¹

Abstract. *The paper aimed to study the dynamics of the consumption of agri-food products per inhabitant in close relationship with the average annual expenses used for purchasing this type of goods using the primary data available in the data base of National Institute of Statistics for the period 2014-2019, and as methods for processing the data: fixed basis index, structural indices, regression equations, coefficients of determination and Bravais-Pearson coefficients of correlation. Consumption depends first of all on production which, in the period 2014-2019, increased in case cereals, meat (animal live weight at slaughter), fish, vegetal oil, fruits, and honey, but it declined in case of milk, eggs, potatoes, and vegetables. In 2019, a Romanian consumed in average: cereals 204.3 kg cereals, meat 77.7 kg, fish 7.8 kg, milk 252.2 kg, fruits 111.3 kg, vegetables 196.6 and honey 0.7 kg, but lees than before, only 241 eggs and 92.3 kg potatoes. In 2019, a Romanian spent in average Lei 3,338 for buying agri-food products, being by +42.4% more than in 2014. In 2019, the share of the agri-food products by category in the average annual total expenses was: cereals 16.8%, vegetables 7.8%, meat 6.6%, fruits 6%, fish 3.9%, eggs 1.7%, vegetable oil 1.7% and honey 0.8%. Average annual consumption of agro-food products and average annual expenses for purchasing this category of goods are strongly dependent of each other, as confirmed by the linear regression equations and coefficient of determination (higher than 0.7) for almost all the agri-food products, except vegetal oil and eggs. The values of correlation coefficients between consumption and expenses were higher than 0.75 for almost all the products reflecting a positive and strong relationship, except vegetal oil, where it was found a moderate and positive correlation. All these reflect a better assurance of food security and the improvement of the living standard of the population.*

Keywords: agri-food products, availability for consumption, expenses for purchasing, Romania

14. Introduction

Food security of the population imposes to assure an adequate nutrition level and healthy products to the society [2].

Agro-food products play an important role in human consumption due to their chemical composition, the amount and structure of nutrients like proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, enzymes, minerals, which give them special properties and

¹Prof. Ph.D. Eng. Econ. University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Bucharest, Romania, Full Member of the Academy of the Romanian Scientists, Corresponding Member of the Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences "Gheorghe Ionescu-Sisesti" (e-mail: agatha_popescu@yahoo.com).

qualities [3]. Food consumption contributes to the final consumption which is one of the factors determining GDP [26, 36].

That is why agriculture and food industry are important sectors of the economy, as they assure a large variety of agro-food products for the population well-being and also availabilities for export, stimulate external trade, contribute to the creation of jobs, and economic growth [3, 5].

Food consumption directly reflects the living conditions of the population. More than this, one of the indicators reflecting the living standard is the share of expenditures spent on food consumption in the total expenditures per person. However, if total income per person increases, the share of the expenditures for agro-food consumption declines in the total expenses for buying goods [1].

The living standard of the population is characterized by the following indicators: consumption of goods and services, expenditures per person, the structure of total consumption expenditures, average annual consumption per inhabitant of the main food products (meat, milk, vegetables, fruits), the daily consumption of protein, fats and calories per inhabitant, the quality of the consumed products and services, the share of food expenditure in total consumption expenditure [4].

The consumption of agri-food products is closely linked to the utilizable production, therefore it depends on the quantity of primary products obtained and processed.

Agricultural production in Romania has continuously increased registering a significant growth rate with a positive impact on the domestic, but also on the external market. However, there are a few cases of agri-food products when internal production was not able to cover the consumption requirements and imports were needed to complete the offer.

Summing the volume of production with the volume of imports for each product category and subtracting the volume of exports, the availability of supply was sufficient for assuring food security.

In consequence, the consumption of agri-food products in Romania increased year by year but with some structural changes depending on the tendencies in the modern consumer's behavior looking for improving his living style by assuring, among other things, a healthier diet.

Consumption increased not only in total absolute value, but also in terms of food consumption per inhabitant, which is a precious and recognized indicator reflecting the living standard in a country and facilitating the comparison with other states.

Of course, food consumption is just a component of total consumption of goods per a household or person and it is strongly connected not only to the volume, structure and quality of the offer, but also to the level of the average income per

family or person, consumption needs, education level, life environment (urban or rural) and other determinants.

In this context, the paper aimed to analyze the dynamics the consumption of agri-food products per inhabitant and year and the evolution of the average expenses per person destined for purchasing food in the period 2014-2019, for which National Institute of Statistics could offer primary data. Also, another purpose was to study the dependence degree of average expenses spent for buying agri-food products on consumption using mathematical modeling based on regression functions, coefficient of determination and Bravais-Pearson coefficient of correlation in order to establish the relational intensity and orientation between these two indicators.

2. Materials and Methods

The study is based on the data available at National Institute of Statistics for the period 2014-2019 regarding the following indicators: availability of agri-food products for consumption by category of product and average annual expenses for purchasing agri-food products spent by the population by product type.

The group of the basic agri-food products used in this study includes: (i) cereals and other products made of cereals in terms of grains equivalent, (ii) meat and meat preparations, (iii) fish, (iv) milk and dairy products in terms of milk equivalent 3.5%, (v) eggs, (vi) vegetal oil, (vii) fruits, (viii) potatoes, (ix) vegetables and (x) honey.

The data were processed using the following methods

- *Fixed basis index*, $I_{FB} = (X_n/X_1) \times 100$, where X_1 is the level of the indicator in the year 2014 and X_n the level of the indicator in the year 2019;

- *Descriptive statistics* in terms of mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation calculated for each indicator and by category of product;

- *Share of expenses for purchasing agri-food products* of each category in the total expenses;

- *Linear regression equation*, $Y = bx + a$, where Y is the dependent variable in terms of average annual expenses of the population for buying agri-food products and X is the independent variable in terms of availability of each category of agri-food products for consumption of the population.

- *Coefficient of determination*, R^2 , was used to show in what measure the variation of the dependent variable Y - "expenses" is determined by the variation of the independent variable x - "availability for consumption";

- *Bravais-Pearson's coefficient of correlation*, r , was calculated based on it well known formula. The statistical significance of the correlation coefficient was checked for P-value 5% ($P < 0.05$) which is the probability when $r = 0$ (null

hypothesis). If the probability is lower than the conventional P-value, r value could be considered significant.

The data were processed using Excel facilities, and the results were presented in tables and graphics, accompanied by the corresponding explains. Finally, the main conclusions were drawn.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Availability of agri-food products for consumption of the population

Romania has a high agricultural potential both in vegetal and animal production. Agriculture supplies the domestic market and also assures availability for export. Therefore, it is the key sector for assuring food security and also gives an important contribution to Gross Domestic Product and trade and payment balance [12, 36].

Among the basic agri-food products destined for the consumption of the population, there are cereals, meat and meat preparations, aquaculture products (fish, sea fruit etc), milk and dairy products, eggs, vegetal oil, fruits, potatoes, vegetables and honey.

Cereals availability

Cereals production registered an ascending trend so that in 2019, it reached 30.41 million tons, by 37.78% more than in 2014. However, the drought of the year 2019 and 2020 determined a decline of cereals production to 18.20 million tons in 2020.

Among cereals, maize and wheat are the most important for human consumption, and that is why Romania extended the cultivated area and made efforts for improving the crop technologies to grow the output [29].

Maize produced 17.43 million tons grains in 2019 compared to 11.98 million tons in 2014, meaning by 45.49% more. The highest production was 18.88 million tons registered in 2018, but since 2015 Romania is top producer of maize in the EU. In 2020, production declined to 10.15 million tons due to the drought and other extreme weather phenomena, this meaning a loss by 58.23% compared to the level achieved in 2019.

In 2019, the maize utilizable production accounted for 17.43 million tons, of which 13.62 million tons for internal use (78.16%) of which for human consumption 4,496.7 thousand tons that is 33%.

Wheat production accounted for 10.20 million tons in 2019, being by 35.75% higher than in 2014, but in 2020 it decreased by 62.29% compared to 2019 and reached only 6.41 million tons.

In 2019, the utilizable production of wheat was 10.20 million tons, of which the internal utilization accounted for 5.29 million tons (51.3%), and of which for human consumption 3,846.9 thousand tons, meaning 72.78%.

As a result, the availability of cereals and other products made of cereals, in grains equivalent accounted for 204.3 kg grains/inhabitant in 2019, being by 10% lower than in 2014. A slight declining trend was noticed in the period 2014-2019, when the maximum available amount of cereals for human consumption of 211.2 thousand tons was reached in 2015, while the minimum level was registered in 2019 (Table 1).

The reasons could be found in the reduction of food demand for bread and other bakery products in the last decade, on one side, due to the modern consumer desire to have a healthier diet, and, on the other side, due to the increased price for this category of products.

However, compared to the EU average bread consumption, 78 kg/capita per year, in Romania bread consumption is higher accounting for 82 kg/capita/year. New trends have appeared in bread consumption related to the consumer preference for high quality, sliced and packed bread despite that bread is still produced in a traditional way in many producing units.

Meat availability

Meat production, in terms of animal live weight at slaughter, registered a general increasing trend, so that in 2019 it reached 1,495 thousand tons compared to 1,316 thousand tons in 2014., meaning a surplus of +13.6%.

Pigs live weight at slaughter accounted for 512 thousand tons in 2019, being by -4.3% smaller than in 2014 when it accounted for 535 thousand tons. However, its maximum level was 588 thousand tons in 2016, but due to the pork crisis in Romania, the number of slaughtered pigs declined and pork production as well [18, 32, 33, 34].

Poultry live weight comes on the 2nd position having a volume of 672 thousand tons in 2019 compared to 488 thousand tons in 2014, and this means + 37.7% [10].

The live weight of slaughtered bovines accounted for 179 thousand tons in 2019, being by -2.72% smaller than in 2014 when it was 184 thousand tons. The peak of production, 206 thousand tons, was recorded in the year 2016, but since that time a more reduced number of bovines were slaughtered due to the decline in the livestock [19].

The live weight of the slaughtered sheep and goats increased year by year and reached the maximum level in 2019, 127 thousand tons compared to only 108 thousand tons in 2014, and this means a surplus of +17.59%.

Meat production structure points out that pork comes on the top position, because it is the traditional food in Romanians' consumption. The average consumption of pork per inhabitant and year being 38.5 kg, representing 49.5% of the total annual

consumption of 77.7 kg meat. Poultry meat comes on the 2nd position with an average consumption per capita of 27 kg, meaning 34.7% of total annual meat consumption. Beef is situated on the 3rd position with 9 kg in average consumed by a Romanian per year (11.6%) and mutton and goat meat accounts for 2.5 kg consumption/capita that is 3.2% of meat output.

The availability of meat and meat preparations in the period 2014-2019 increased by 27.585 from 60.9 kg/inhabitant in 2014 to 77.7 kg/capita in 2019, which is the maximum level so far (Table 1).

Fish availability

Fish production in Romania is still small, being below its potential, because the capacity of the fishing fleet is reduced, the productivity in the aquaculture farms is still low and marine aquaculture production is missing. Despite that, demand is higher and higher both for fish and aquaculture products. As production is not enough, about 80% of fish consumption is covered by import, especially from Spain, France, Italy, and Greece. In the country the most demanded fishes are carp and trout, and from the marine species: mackerel, salmon and tuna, and also sea fruits.

Fish and aquaculture has recorded an ascending trend year by year, and in 2016 reached 19.8 thousand tons and continued to grow to 22.7 thousand tons in 2017 and then to 20.5 thousand tons in 2018.

The availability of fish for consumption increased by 59.18% in the analyzed interval, from the minimum level accounting for 4.9 kg/inhabitant in 2014 to the maximum level of 7.8 kg/capita in 2019 (Table 1).

Milk availability

Milk production registered a declining trend from 46,615 thousand hl in 2014 to 42,113 thousand hl in 2019, meaning by 9.97% less. The highest contribution to total milk production is given by cow and buffalo milk, which accounted for 86% in 2014 and 84.7% in 2019, as the contribution of sheep and goats is increasing, but it has a small percentage.

The decline in milk production was caused by milk crisis meaning the reduction of the bovine livestock, mainly of dairy cows in close relationship with the negative impact of climate change on forage production and especially due to the low milk price offered by processors. For this reason, the internal demand for milk both for the consumption of the population and for milk processing industry was completed by imported milk [16, 22, 23, 35].

In consequence, the availability of milk and dairy products in milk equivalent 3.5% recorded a slight increase of 3.27% in the analyzed interval, from 244.2 kg/inhabitant in 2014 to 252.2 kg/capita in 2019 (Table 1).

Egg availability

Egg production registered a decreasing trend due to the diminished number of laying hens which are the main contributors to this sort of production. The increase of the price of the farm inputs as well as the import of eggs have diminished the interest of the poultry breeders for raising laying hens being much more oriented to poultry meat [9, 30].

As a result, in 2019, egg production in Romania accounted for 5,564 million pieces, being by -16.16% smaller than 6,636 million pieces in 2014. In 2020, it declined again to 5,428 million pieces.

As a consequence, the eggs availability for consumption of the population accounted for 241 pieces/inhabitant in 2019 being by -2.04% less than 246 pieces/capita in 2014 (Table 1).

Vegetal oil availability

Vegetal oil is the most preferred source of fats in the consumer diet. The vegetal oil is achieved by processing oil seeds especially coming from sunflower, but also from rape, soybean and maize [9, 28, 37, 38, 39]. But, the main contributor to vegetal oil is sunflower, and at present there are many processing plants and sunflower oil brands in Romania.

The dynamic of the sunflower seeds production has had a good impact both for producing oil for human consumption, for processing industry and also for export. In 2019, Romania harvested 3.57 million tons sunflower seeds compared to 2.18 million tons in 2014, meaning a surplus of 63.76%. In 2020, due to the long and terrible drought of the year 2020, sunflower seeds production declined to 2.2 million tons. Romania is top producer of sunflower seeds in the EU [13].

The production of sunflower oil accounted for 167.3 thousand tons in the year 2017 and 233.9 thousand tons in 2018, meaning a surplus of +39.9% compared to the previous year.

Availability of vegetal oil for consumption of the population increased by 5.79% in the period 2014-2019 from 13.8 kg/inhabitant in 2014 to 14.6 kg/capita in 2019 (+5.79%) (Table 1).

Fruit availability

Fruit production has slightly increased to meet the market demand, but even at present it does not entirely cover consumers' needs which justify the imports of apples, pear, water melons. Also, the exotic fruits are more and more present among the consumers' preferences: bananas, oranges, tangerines, pineapple, mango etc.

In 2019, Romania produced 1.49 million tons of fruits compared to 2014 when production was 1.30 million tons, therefore the actual surplus is +14.61%. However, the highest fruit production was 1.81 million tons, recorded in the year 2018. During the last years, the orchards were very much affected by various meteorological phenomena like freeze at blooming, strong rainfalls and winds etc.

In 2020, fruit production was higher than in 2019 and reached 1.60 million tons [15, 20].

Plums and apples are the main fruits produced in Romania [25]. In 2019, plums production accounted for 0.7 million tons being by 42.85% higher than in 2014 when it accounted for only 0.49 million tons. In 2020, Romania produced 0.78 million tons of plums, by 11.41% more than in 2018.

Apples were on the top position in 2014, but after that they passed on the 2nd position after plums, because Romanians like to use plums not only for the consumption as fresh fruit but mainly for producing a traditional plum brandy. In 2019, apple production was 0.5 million tons, almost equal to the one registered in 2014. The highest apple production was 0.64 million tons, achieved in the year 2018.

The share in total fruit production belongs to plums representing 48.75% of the total fruit production, and apples come on the 2nd position with a share of 34.37% in the year 2020.

Availability for fruits destined for the consumption of the population increased by +33.77% from 80.2 kg/capita in the year 2014 to 111.3 kg/capita in 2019 (Table 1).

Potatoes availability

Potatoes are also a basic food of high importance in the Romanians' diet. However, potatoes production could not keep pace with the market requirements due to the climate change in the cultivation area (extend of the drought) and also due to the competition with the invasion of potatoes on the internal market coming from import at sell at lower prices than the ones produced locally. In 2019, Romania produced just 2.63 million tons potatoes compared to 3.51 million tons in 2014, that is by -25.08% less [11].

Availability of potatoes for consumption in the year 2019 accounted for 92.3 kg/inhabitant compared to 100.8 kg/capita in 2014, meaning by -9.44% less (Table 1).

Vegetables availability

The production of vegetables varied from a year to another, but in general the trend was a declining one. In 2019, Romania carried out 3.53 million tons vegetables in comparison with 3.8 million tons in 2014, that is -8% loss. In 2018, it was achieved 3.8 million tons vegetables similar with the one recorded in 2014. In Romania there are cultivated tomatoes, cucumbers, egg plants, cabbage, cauliflower, onion, garlic and other vegetables, but the most important are tomatoes which are used not only for internal market, but also for export [14, 17, 21].

Tomatoes production registered 0.69 million tons in 2019 being by 2.89% smaller than in 2014, when it accounted for 0.71 million tons. In 2020, tomatoes production reached again 0.71 million tons.

Romania occupies the 8th position in the EU for tomatoes production after France, Portugal, Spain, Greece, Italy, Bulgaria and Poland. Internal requirements are not entirely covered by the domestic production, so that important amounts of tomatoes are imported from Turkey, Spain and Netherlands.

In 2019, the share of tomatoes in total vegetable production was 20.28%, but cabbage had 28%, onion 9.2% and green peppers 6%.

The requirements for vegetables in the domestic market increased due to the change in the behavior of the consumer thinking of a healthy diet.

In 2019, the consumption of vegetables per inhabitant was 196.6 kg, being by +7.49% higher than in 2014 when it accounted for 182.9 kg/capita (Table 1).

Table 1. Availability of agri-food products for the consumption of the population in Romania, 2014-2019 (kg/inhabitant/year)

	Cereals and other prod. in grains equiv.	Meat and meat prep.	Fish	Milk and dairy prod. in milk equiv. 3.5%	Eggs	Vegetal oil	Fruits	Potatoes	Vegetables	Honey
2014	207.0	60.9	4.9	244.2	246	13.8	80.2	100.8	182.9	0.3
2015	211.2	66.4	5.5	243.4	262	14.6	87.8	98.3	182.6	0.3
2016	208.4	68.6	5.9	246.3	267	14.3	96.0	95.5	178.4	0.4
2017	209.2	71.5	6.3	244.1	255	14.5	96.1	96.6	187.8	0.4
2018	205.4	76.2	6.7	250.7	236	14.7	110.8	95.5	202.1	0.6
2019	204.3	77.7	7.8	252.2	241	14.6	111.3	92.3	196.6	0.7
2019/2014 %	90.0	127.58	159.18	103.27	97.96	105.70	138.77	91.56	107.49	233.33
Mean	207.41	70.21	6.18	246.81	251.16	14.41	97.03	96.5	188.4	0.45
St. Dev.	2.44	6.28	1.00	3.74	12.18	0.33	12.35	2.87	9.15	0.16
CV %	1.17	8.94	16.18	1.51	4.84	2.29	12.72	2.97	4.85	35.55

Source: Own calculation based on the data from NIS, 2021 [6, 7].

Honey availability

Honey production recorded a high increase as honey is both required on the domestic market and also on the external one, especially in the Western EU countries grace to its high quality [27].

In 2019, Romania produced 25,269 tons honey compared to 18,040 tons in 2014, meaning a surplus of + 49.97%. The year 2019 was an unfavorable year for pickings and production was not as high like the peak of 30,177 tons registered in the year 2017. The year 2020 was favorable for beekeeping, and it was achieved 30,714 tons production, the highest level in the analyzed interval. Due to the financial support offer by the EU for beekeeping, the number of bee families increased and honey production per apiary as well [8, 24].

Even though honey production increased, internal consumption accounting for about 0.7 kg/inhabitant per year is still low compared to the quantity of honey consumed in average in the EU which is 2.5 kg/year/capita.

In 2019, average consumption of honey was 0.7 kg honey, by +133.33 more than in 2014, when it was used only 0.3 kg honey per capita (Table 1).

The values of the variation coefficients for average annual consumption of agri-food products per inhabitant reflect that in case of cereals and other products of cereals origin, in grains equivalent, milk and dairy products in milk equivalent 3.5%, vegetal oil, potatoes, eggs, vegetables, meat and meat preparations, where CV% had levels below 10%, the mean is representative because the data are homogenous. In case of fish and fruits, CV% had values between 10% and 20% reflecting that the data are relatively homogenous and the mean could be considered representative. In case of honey, CV was higher than 30% reflecting a larger variability and heterogeneity of the data and the mean is not considered representative.

3.2. Average annual expenses spent by the population for purchasing agri-food products

Consumption of agri-food products is closely related to the expenses for purchasing them, which in their turn depend on the average income per household, changes in consumer patterns and food price.

-Average annual expenses for buying cereals and products of cereals origin, reached Lei 561.48 per person in the year 2019, being by +26.97% higher than in 2014 (Table 2).

-An important increase of +29.33% was also registered in case of average annual expenses for buying meat and meat preparations in 2019, when a consumer spent Lei 221.16 compared to Lei 171 in the year 2014 (Table 2).

-In case of fish, a Romanian spent by +48.69% more money in 2019 when the average expense for buying this sort of food accounted for Lei 130.08 instead of only Lei 87.48 in the year 2014 (Table 2).

- In 2019, the average expense spent for purchasing milk and dairy products in equivalent milk 3.5% reached Lei 21.16/person, being by +29.33% higher than in 2014 (Table 2).

-Also, in 2019, for buying eggs, the average expense per person accounted for Lei 56.76 being by +41.19% over the level spent in 2014 (Table 2).

-For purchasing vegetal oil, the average expense registered a decline of -3.64% in 2019, when its level accounted for Lei 57.24 in comparison with Lei 59.4 in 2014 (Table 2).

-For buying fruits, in 2019, a Romanian spent Lei 202.32, while in 2014 he spent by 44.59% less (Table 2).

-Despite that the consumption of potatoes declined in the period 2014-2019, the average expense allotted for buying this product increased by +68.57% from Lei 42/person in 2014 to Lei 70.8 in 2019 (Table 2).

-The higher need for consuming vegetables determined consumers to allot more money for purchasing various products of this category like tomatoes, cucumbers, egg plants, cabbage, onion, garlic etc. In 2019, a Romanian spent in average Lei 259.44 compared to Lei 165.72 in the year 2014, meaning by +56.55% more.

-The highest growth in the expenses for buying food was recorded by honey, +102.77% in the analyzed interval. This was due to the more oriented behavior for consuming honey, which is a natural, high nutritive food, healthy, sweet, pleasant, a real medicine instead of refined sugar [27, 31].

In 2019, a Romanian spent in average Lei 26.28 for buying honey compared to only Lei 12.96 in 2014, that is more than double (Table 2).

Table 2. Average annual expenses spent by the population for buying agri-food products, Romania, 2014-2019 (Lei/person/year)

	Cereals and other prod. in grains equiv.	Meat and meat prep.	Fish	Milk and dairy prod. in milk equiv. 3.5%	Eggs	Vegetal oil	Fruits	Potatoes	Vegetables	Honey
2014	442.2	171.0	87.48	171.0	40.2	59.4	139.92	42.0	165.72	12.96
2015	443.52	178.2	94.68	178.2	41.64	54.36	146.07	38.04	166.8	15.96
2016	446.16	181.56	97.32	181.56	42.24	53.52	153.0	41.52	176.16	18.84
2017	469.80	194.4	108.12	192.24	51.12	54.6	171.8	42.22	196.56	21.00
2018	511.44	208.56	121.44	208.56	58.8	55.32	190.08	47.28	228.96	24.48
2019	561.48	221.16	130.08	221.16	56.76	57.24	202.32	70.8	259.44	26.28
2019/2014 %	126.97	129.33	148.69	129.33	141.19	96.36	144.59	168.57	156.66	202.77
Mean	479.1	192.48	106.52	192.12	48.46	55.74	167.36	46.97	198.94	19.92
St. Dev.	48.23	19.33	16.53	19.31	8.20	2.18	35.30	12.03	38.00	5.05
CV %	10.06	10.04	15.51	10.05	16.92	3.91	15.05	25.61	19.10	25.35

Source: Own calculation based on the data from NIS, 2021 [6, 7].

The values of the variation coefficients for the average annual expenses for buying agri-food products reflect that in case of vegetal oil, the data are homogenous and the mean is available because CV% is smaller than 10%. In case of cereals and other products of cereals origin, in grains equivalent, meat and meat preparations, milk and dairy products in milk equivalent 3.5%, fruits, fish, eggs and vegetables, the CV had values between 10% and 20% reflecting that the data are relatively homogenous and the mean could be accepted as being representative. In case of potatoes and honey, where the variation coefficient had values between 20% and 30%, the data used in this study are relatively heterogeneous and the mean is not representative.

3.3. The average annual total expenses for buying agri-food products

The average annual total expenses for purchasing agri-food products accounted for Lei 3,338.2 per person in the year 2019, being by +42.45 higher than in 2014, when it was Lei 2,344.2 (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Evolution of average annual total expenses for purchasing agrofood products, Romania, 2014-2019 (Lei/person/year)

Source: Own design based on the data from NIS, 2021.

The share of the average annual expenses for purchasing various agri-food products in the average total annual expenses reflects the importance of different basic food in human consumption.

The highest share of 18.8% in the year 2014, but 16.8% in the year 2019 belongs to cereals and products made of cereals, in grains equivalent. The decline of 2 pp is explained by the reduction of bread and other bakery products in the diet, consumers being interested to buy healthier products and also because the bakery products have a higher price than in the previous years.

On the 2nd position are vegetables whose share in the average total expense for purchasing them increased from 7.1% in 2014 to 7.8% in 2019, this means +0.7 pp. On the 3rd position is situated meat and meat preparations, and also milk and dairy products in milk equivalent 3.5%, whose share declined from 7.3% in 2014 to 6.6% in 2019 in the average total annual expense allotted for buying these foods.

The share of fish in the average total expenses increased from 3.7% in 2014 to 3.9% in 2019.

Eggs registered the 5th position with a share of 1.7% in the average total expenses both at the beginning and at the end of the studied period.

The share of vegetable oil declined from 2.5% in 2014 to 1.7% in 2019.

About 6% of the average total expenses is spent for buying fruits in 2019. Besides fish, vegetables and honey, potatoes registered an increased share in the average total expenses from 1.8% in 2014 to 2,1% in 2019. Finally, honey comes on the last position, its share also increased but from 0.5% in 2014 to 0.8% in 2019 (Table 3).

Table 3. Share of average annual expenses for purchasing each product category in the average annual total expenses spent by the population for buying agri-food products in 2019 versus 2014 (%)

	Cereals and other prod. in grains equiv.	Meat and meat prep.	Fish	Milk and dairy prod. in milk equiv. 3.5%	Eggs	Vegetal oil	Fruits	Potatoes	Vegetables	Honey
2014	18.8	7.3	3.7	7.3	1.7	2.5	6	1.8	7.1	0.5
2019	16.8	6.6	3.9	6.6	1.7	1.7	6	2.1	7.8	0.8
2019-2014 pp	-2.0	-0.7	+0.2	-0.7	0	-0.8	0	+0.3	+0.7	+0.3

Source: Own calculation based on the data from NIS, 2021.

3.4. The dependence of average annual expenses for purchasing agri-food products on the availability of these products for consumption of the population

The results in terms of linear regression equations and the values of the coefficient of determination are presented in Table 4.

They reflect in what measure the average annual expense for buying agri-food products depended on the availability for consumption of the population.

The values of the coefficient of determination in case of meat and meat preparations, fish and fruits reflected that over 90% of the variation in average annual expense per person for purchasing agri-food products was determined by the variation of the consumption per inhabitant and year.

In case of milk and dairy products in milk equivalent 3.5%, the variation caused by the independent factor accounted for 82% and in case of honey for 88.7% in the variation of the dependent factors, that is average annual expense.

In case of vegetables, consumption variation determined a change of 74.8% of the average annual expense.

Also, in case of cereals, the variation caused by the independent factor on the dependent factor accounted for 66.6%.

The lowest R square values were registered for vegetal oil, 0.265 and for eggs 0.520 showing that the variation of the average annual expenses for buying these products was caused only 26.5% and respectively 52% by the change in consumption per inhabitant, the differences being determined by other factors (Table 4).

Table 4. Linear regression equations and coefficients of determination reflecting the dependence of Y variable, average annual expenses for purchasing agri-food products on X variable, availability of agri-food products for the consumption of the population

	Linear regression equations	R ²
Cereals and other prod. in grains equivalent	$Y = -16.11x + 3,820.75$	0.666
Meat and meat preparations	$Y = 2.96 x - 15.78$	0.911
Fish	$Y = 15.94 x + 7.947$	0.945
Milk and dairy products in milk equivalent 3.5%	$Y = 4.67 x - 961.08$	0.822
Eggs	$Y = - 0.48 x + 170.41$	0.520
Vegetal oil	$Y = -3.99 x + 113.31$	0.365
Fruits	$Y = 1.93 x - 20.67$	0.901
Potatoes	$Y = -3.21 x + 356.82$	0.588
Vegetables	$Y = 3.59 x - 477.80$	0.748
Honey	$Y = 28.97 x + 6.88$	0.887

Source: Own calculation.

The correlation coefficients between consumption and expenses spent for buying agri-food products had higher values than 0.8 in case of fish, meat and meat preparations, fruits, honey, milk and dairy products in milk equivalent 3.5% and cereals and products of cereals origin in grains equivalent (Table 5).

In case of potatoes and eggs, the values of the correlation coefficients were $r = 0.767$ and, respectively $r = 0.721$, reflecting also positive relationships between the two indicators and enough high

Therefore, taking into consideration the interpretation of the values for correlation coefficient given by Colton (1974), for the agro-food products mentioned above which had the value of the correlation coefficient over 0.75 between the two variables, consumption and expenses per inhabitant per year, it is a very strong and positive relationship for $p < 0.5$.

Table 5. Coefficients of correlation (r) between availability of agri-food products for consumption (X) and average annual expenses of the population for purchasing agri-food products by category of product

Cereals and other prod. in grains equiv.	Meat and meat prep.	Fish	Milk and dairy prod. in milk equiv. 3.5%	Eggs	Vegetal oil	Fruits	Potatoes	Vegetables	Honey
0.816**	0.963***	0.972***	0.906***	0.721*	0.604	0.949***	0.767*	0.865**	0.942***

Source: Own calculation.

Vegetable oil had also a strong and positive coefficient of correlation between the two indicators, $r = 0.604$, but smaller compared to other products. In this case, the value of the coefficient of correlation ranging between 0.5 and 0.75, the relationship between consumption and expenses per inhabitant per year is a positive, but moderate one for $p < 0.5$ (Table 5).

Conclusions

- (1) This research proved that between average annual consumption of agro-food products per inhabitant and average annual expenses for purchasing this category of goods it is a close relationship of dependence.
- (2) Consumption depends first of all on production, an aspect which was analyzed in this study, but also on average consumer price of agri-food products, average income level per household and person, consumption patterns, health conditions, education level etc., aspects which could be approached in future studies.
- (3) In the period 2014-2019, production increased in case of the following groups of products: cereals +37.7%, meat (animal live weight at slaughter) +13.6%, fish +3.5%, vegetal oil +40%, fruits +14.6% and honey +50%, but production declined in case of milk -9.9%, eggs -16%, potatoes -25% and vegetables -8%.
- (4) In 2019 versus 2014, average annual consumption per inhabitant accounted for: 204.3 kg cereals (-10%), meat 77.7 kg (+27.5%), fish 7.8 kg (+59%), milk 252.2 kg (+3.2%), fruits 111.3 kg (+33.7%), vegetables 196.6 (+7.5%) and honey 0.7 kg (133%), but it declined in case of: eggs 241 pieces (-2%) and potatoes 92.3 kg (-9.4%).
- (5) In 2019, average annual total expenses for agri-food products per inhabitant accounted for Lei 3,338 being by +42.4% higher than in 2014.
- (6) In total annual expenses for purchasing agri-food products, the share of expense by group of product had an increasing tendency in the period 2014-2019 for almost all products, except cereals whose share declined. In 2019, the share of the products in the average annual total expenses was as follows: cereals 16.8%, vegetables 7.8%, meat 6.6%, fruits 6%, fish 3.9%, eggs 1.7%, vegetable oil 1.7% and honey 0.8%.
- (7) The close relationship of the dependence between consumption and expenses was confirmed by the linear regression equations and coefficient of determination whose values were over than 0.7 in almost all the agri-food products, except vegetal oil and eggs where it had smaller values reflecting that the variation of the expenses depends much more on other factors than consumption.
- (8) The values of the coefficients of correlations between consumption and expenses for buying agri-food products had higher values than 0.75 for almost all

the products reflecting a positive and strong relationship, except vegetal oil where it was found a moderate and positive correlation.

(9) As a final conclusion, in Romania average annual consumption of agri-food products per inhabitant increased and this has determined the growth of average annual expenses per person for purchasing this product. This reflects how food security is assured and also the improvement of the living standard of the population.

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TRENDS OF THE FOOD BALANCE AND FOOD CONSUMPTION IN OUR COUNTRY FOR THE PERIOD 2014-2019

Marian CONSTANTIN¹, Raluca NECULA (RĂDOI)², Iulian DRĂGHICI³

Abstract. *Food security is one of the most pressing issues facing mankind. in this context, the analysis of the food balance trend of each country is a necessity to notice the aspects that need to be improved in order to avoid imbalances that may arise between the elements of the food balance. the paper analyzes for the period 2014-2019 the trend of the main agri-food products in Romania, of the share they occupy in the average daily food consumption and of the place in the European union regarding the efforts of the population to cover the food expenses. following the analysis, significant increases in Romania's agri-food resources were found during the analyzed period, as well as increases in the import of agri-food products.*

Keywords: food balance, average daily consumption, food expenses

15. Introduction

This study approaches an important and well debated research topic, the trend of food balance and food consumption in Romania for the period before the pandemic crisis, 2014-2019. It was necessary such an analysis in order to establish the ways to improve and to correct the gaps in the food balance, close related also to the food security and food consumption.

In order to ensure the food self-sufficiency and the food security, both on short and long term, Romania must exploit the agricultural potential through a political frame more favourable and the increase of investments in the agricultural and rural development [3].

Consumption study is an important part of any market research. Consumption must be studied scientifically, in order to develop solid means of meeting its requirements and diversification possibilities. The Romanian consumer wants to eat healthy and cheap farm food products that meet their demands and preferences [7].

¹Prof. Ph.D., University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine in Bucharest, Romania, Corresponding Member of The Academy of the Romanian Scientists, (email: marianconstantin2014@yahoo.com)

²Lecturer Ph.D., University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine in Bucharest, (email: Raluca_nec@yahoo.com)

³Ph.D., University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine in Bucharest, (email: if07iul@gmail.com)

16. Materials and methods

In the present paper were used physical values rendered from the existing nominations according to the official statistical data (National Institute of Statistics Bulletins) for the period 2014-2019, which were processed according to the statistical-mathematical methodology [5].

As such, these annual data series were processed following appropriate indicators such as: food balance, average daily net food consumption.

Of particular note is the interpretive use along with average indicators and statistical indicators, following the deviations, the coefficient of variation (CV) and the annual rhythms by which the trends of the analyzed phenomenon are captured, concretely delimiting its trends [6].

The concentration of the individual values of the characteristics compared to the typical values through the deviations 2019/2014, were outlined by the coefficient of variation and the annual rhythms.

The balance of food resources and their use is carried out according to a single scheme for plant and animal production, highlighting two parts - resources (inputs) and uses (use of resources) [5].

Average net daily food consumption per capita, expressed in grams (CMZ) - quantities of products that can be used in full as food; is established according to the relation: $CMZ = CMN * kgc * 1,000/365$, where: kgc represents the coefficient of transformation into a consumable product (ex: boneless meat, pitted and peeled fruits, green peas, etc.) [1] [6].

17. Results and discussions

The whole issue was structurally represented by the level of resources and consumption of the main agri-food products, respectively the annual indicators of the analyzed period 2014-2019.

At national level according to the values in the tables that can be discussed as follows:

a) for cereals and cereal products according to *Table 1*, we have the following results:

- an average annual usable production of 24,993 thousand tons also resulted in an import of 2,721 thousand tons. It should be mentioned the variations that can be reflected by the deviation of the last year 2019 compared to 2014, the values being positive (8,303 thousand tons for usable production and 568 thousand tons for imports, are discussed by relative figures by comparing the two indicators representing 137.7% and 131.8% respectively). Next, the values of the coefficient

of variation (for usable production and import) is 20.0 and 29.1, respectively. Of all these variations, the annual rate is by 9.4%. At the usable production of 3.7% at import and 9.4% usable production, the known values also known as the increase rate reflect the percentage increase/decrease of the values from the analyzed data series.

Table 1. Food balance and daily food intake for **Cereals** and cereal products (tons of cereal grains)

Specification	MU	years						Average	2019 / vs 2014		CV	Annual rhythm
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MU	MU	%	%	%
Resources	Th. to	23500	22359	25239	29640	31757	32370	27477	8870.0	137.7	15.8	6.61
Usable production	Th. to	21714	18964	21424	26725	31112	30017	24993	8303.0	138.2	20	6.69
Import	Th. to	1785	3395	3815	2914	2063	2353	2721	568.0	131.8	29.1	5.68
applications	Th. to	23500	22359	25239	29640	20630	23530	17526	30.0	100.1	69.2	0.03
Export	Th. to	10177	9635	11937	11103	12066	14204	11520	4027.0	139.6	14.1	6.90
Internal availability for consumption	Th. to	13322	12724	13302	18537	21110	18166	16194	4844.0	136.4	21.8	6.40
Average daily consumption	per capita	1320.3	1349.4	1331.2	1327.4	1309.1	1304.2	1324	-16.1	98.8	1.2	-0.25

Eurostat, NIS, 2021, Food balances [2] [4] [5].

At the same agri-food product, the uses and exports with annual averages of 17,526 and 11,520 thousand tons show deviations of 30 thousand tons for uses and 4,027 thousand tons for export. The coefficients of variation of 69.2% and 14.1% have rates of 0.03% and 6.9% respectively. Thus, the values of all these indicators characterize the entire period.

b) for the agri-food product potatoes according to Table 2, the following results:

The analysis of the degree of homogeneity of the data presented in **Table 2** was calculated both according to the indicators of the central tendency to verify their representativeness as typical values of the respective series.

For the same product at the average daily food consumption expressed in calories, a relative uniformity of consumption is found annually. Related to this annual level, the coefficient of variation is 3%, and the annual rate is -1.73%.

Thus, it is found that for the **potato** product the annual rate is negative (with reference to resources, production used, uses and availability for export. There are positive values for the import of potatoes of 367 thousand tons per year, with an annual growth rate of 14.74 %.

Table 2 . Food balance and daily food consumption for the **Potatoes** product

Specification	MU	years						Average MU	2019 / vs 2014		CV %	Annual rhythm %
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019		MU	%		
Resources	Th.to	3788	290	3061	3462	3428	3162	2865	-626.0	83.5	44.9	-3.55
Usable production	Th.to	3519	2625	2690	3117	3023	2627	2934	-892.0	74.7	12.1	-5.68
Import applications	Th.to	269	274	372	345	405	535	367	266.0	198.9	26.8	14.74
Export	Th.to	3788	2899	3036	3415	3428	3162	3288	-626.0	83.5	9.8	-3.55
Internal availability for consumption	Th.to	32	30	26	47	43	38	36	6.0	118.8	22.4	3.50
Average daily consumption	Per capita	3766	2869	3036	3415	3385	3124	3266	-642.0	83.0	9.8	-3.67
		199.4	194.6	189	191.3	189	182.7	191	-16.7	91.6	3.0	-1.73

Eurostat, NIS, 2021, Food balances [2] [4] [5].

c) for the agri-food product leguminous grains according to **Table 3**, the following results:

Product leguminous grains is characterized according to **Table 4** by increasing values for all analyzed indicators.

Table 3. Nutrition balance and daily food intake of **Leguminous grains** (equivalent to grain cereals)

Specification	MU	years						Average MU	2019 / vs 2014		CV %	Annual rhythm %
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019		MU	%		
Resources	Th.to	97	101	13	367	233	275	181	178.0	283.5	73.2	23.17
Usable production	Th.to	71	76	99	302	191	236	163	165.0	332.4	58.7	27.15
Import applications	Th.to	26	26	28	65	41	39	38	13.0	150.0	40.0	8.45
Export	Th.to	97	101	128	367	233	275	200	178.0	283.5	54.8	23.17
Internal availability for consumption	Th.to	5	4	63	197	69	77	69	72.0	1540.0	101.8	72.78
Average daily consumption	Per capita	93	98	65	170	164	198	131	105.0	212.9	40.3	16.32
		28.6	26.7	17.3	20	33.9	33.3	27	4.7	116.4	25.6	3.09

Eurostat, NIS, 2021, Food balances [2] [4] [5].

There are positive growth rates for resources of 23.17%, imports of 8.45% and exports of 72.78%.

The level of the average daily consumption rate increased by 3%, during the studied period, from 28.6 calories/capita to 33.3 calories/capita.

d) for the agri-food product vegetables and vegetable products according to **Table 4**, the annual average of the same indicators highlights the increase of imports of 286 thousand tons in 2019, compared to 2014 (growth rate of 9.41% annually). During the same period, exports decreased by 19 thousand tons (annual rate of -5.59%).

Table 4. Food balance and daily food consumption for the product **Vegetables** and vegetable products (equivalent to fresh vegetables)

Specification	MU	years						Average	2019 / vs 2014		CV	Annual rhythm
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MU	MU	%	%	%
Resources	Th.to	3776	3700	3550	3751	3985	3800	3760	24.0	100.6	3.8	0.13
Usable production	Th.to	3272	3124	2881	3085	3214	3011	3098	-261.0	92.0	4.5	-1.65
Import applications	Th.to	504	5858	669	666	772	790	1543	286.0	156.7	137.1	9.41
Export	Th.to	3776	3709	3550	3751	3985	3800	3762	24.0	100.6	3.7	0.13
Internal availability for consumption	Th.to	76	60	44	55	62	57	59	-19.0	75.0	17.7	-5.59
Average daily consumption	Per capita	3700	3650	3506	3696	3924	3743	3703	43.0	101.2	3.7	0.23
		129.9	125.2	122.1	126.1	135.3	132.6	129	2.7	102.1	3.9	0.41

Eurostat, NIS, 2021, Food balances [2] [4] [5].

The average daily calories consumption of the product Vegetables and vegetable products was relatively stable of 129 average daily calories per capita, with a coefficient of variation of 3.9%.

e) For the agri-food product sugar, the trend of dietary consumption tends to decrease, from an economic and social point of view by interpreting the values of the indicators analyzed in Table 5, which show maintenance trends sometimes even by a slight increase.

The import indicator shows an increase in imports of 288 thousand tons in 2019 compared to 2014, with a very high annual growth rate of 18.34%, while exports decreased by 44 thousand tons, from 166 thousand tons to 122 thousand tons, respectively an annual rate of -5.97%.

Table 5. Food balance and daily food intake of **Sugar** and sugar products (equivalent to refined sugar)

Specification	MU	years						Average	2019 / vs 2014		CV	Annual rhythm
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MU	MU	%	%	%
Resources	Th.to	665	740	705	723	631	784	708	119.0	117.9	7.7	3.35
Usable production	Th.to	201	139	451	447	108	139	248	-62.0	69.2	64.2	-7.11
Import applications	Th.to	212	201	138	190	494	492	288	280.0	232.1	55.9	18.34
Export	Th.to	665	740	705	723	631	784	708	119.0	117.9	7.7	3.35
Internal availability for consumption	Th.to	166	123	138	125	111	122	131	-44.0	73.5	14.7	-5.97
Average daily consumption	Per capita	498	617	567	598	520	663	577	165.0	133.1	10.7	5.89
		237.2	287.5	284.3	269.7	285.2	288	275	50.8	121.4	7.2	3.96

Eurostat, NIS, 2021, Food balances [2] [4] [5].

The average food consumption varies annually between 237 calories/capita and 288 calories/capita, with a coefficient of variation of 7.2% and an annual growth rate of 3.96%.

f) for the agri-food product milk and milk products from the analysis of the indicators presented in **Table 6**, a consumption is highlighted that can be reproduced by the following:

- resources and availabilities can be considered stationary. In terms of resources, there is an increase of 1 thousand tons, and in terms of availability, a decrease of 4 thousand tons.
 - on import, there is an increase from 5 thousand tons in 2014 to 10 thousand tons in 2019 (the increase being 100%). The annual growth rate is 14.87%.
- Production for export increased by 0.5 million tons, respectively by an annual rate of 4.5%.

Table 6. Food balance and daily food consumption of **Milk** and milk products (in milk equivalent, 3.5% fat)

Specification	MU	years						Average	2019 / vs 2014			CV	Annual rhythm
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019		2015	2016	2017		
Resources	Th.to	62	62	62	62	63	63	62	1.0	101.6	0.8	0.32	
Usable production	Th.to	57	56	54	53	53	53	54	-4.0	93.0	3.2	-1.44	
Import applications	Th.to	5	6	8	9	10	10	8	5.0	200.0	26.2	14.87	
Export	Th.to	2	2	2	2.6	2.8	2.5	2	0.5	125.0	15.5	4.56	
Internal availability for consumption	Th.to	60	60	60	59	60	60	60	0.0	100.0	0.7	0.00	
Average daily consumption	Per capita	461.7	460.2	465.5	461.5	474	476.8	467	15.1	103.3	1.5	0.65	

Eurostat, NIS, 2021, Food balances [2] [4] [5].

The average daily consumption remained in very tight limits from 461.7 cal./capita in 2014 to 476.8 cal. /capita in 2019, with a coefficient of variation of 1.5%, for this period.

g) for the agri-food product eggs (thousand pcs), the increases shown by the values of the indicators in **Table 7** show amplifications in the dynamics of the years, at the import and export indicators. Thus, the import shows an increase of 123 thousand pcs, with an annual increase of 6.97%, and the export indicator an increase of 147 thousand pcs, with an annual increase of 10.24%.

Domestic availability for consumption has a declining trend, with an annual rate of -3.50.

Table 7. Food balance and daily food consumption for the **Egg** product (in mil pcs)

Specification	MU	years						Average	2019 / vs 2014		CV	Annual rhythm
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019		MU	%		
Resources	Mil. Pcs.	6943	6997	6585	6375	6061	5994	6493	-949.0	86.3	6.6	-2.90
Usable production	Mil. Pcs.	6636	6555	6182	5996	5713	5564	6108	-1072.0	83.8	7.1	-3.46
Import	Mil. Pcs.	307	382	403	379	348	430	375	123.0	140.1	11.5	6.97
applications	Mil. Pcs.	6943	6937	6333	6375	6061	5994	6441	-949.0	86.3	6.4	-2.90
Export	Mil. Pcs.	234	366	252	308	428	381	328	147.0	162.8	23.3	10.24
Internal availability for consumption	Mil. Pcs.	6709	6671	6333	6067	5633	5613	6171	-1096.0	83.7	7.9	-3.50
Average daily consumption	Per capita	57.6	61.4	62.6	59.7	55.2	56.4	59	-1.2	97.9	4.9	-0.42

Eurostat, NIS, 2021, Food balances [2] [4] [5]

At the same time, it is noted that the average daily food consumption of the egg product maintains a relatively constant level of 59 calories/capita, with a coefficient of variation of 4.9%.

h) for the agri-food product meat and meat products (in fresh meat equivalent) from the analysis of the indicators are presented in **Table 8**.

Table 8. Food balance and daily food consumption of **Meat** and meat products (in fresh meat equivalent)

Specification	MU	years						Average	2019 / vs 2014		CV	Annual rhythm
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019		MU	%		
Resources	Th. to	1282	1419	1463	1502	1609	1606	1480	324.0	125.3	8.3	4.61
Usable production	Th. to	908	989	1009	1012	1035	1046	1000	138.0	115.2	4.9	2.87
Import	Th. to	384	430	454	490	574	560	482	176.0	145.8	15.4	7.84
applications	Th. to	1292	1419	1463	1502	1609	1606	1482	314.0	124.3	8.1	4.45
Export	Th. to	126.7	134.1	153.8	164.5	170.5	162.8	152	36.1	128.5	11.7	5.14
Internal availability for consumption	Th. to	1165	1274	1309	1338	1438	1443	1328	278.0	123.9	7.9	4.37
Average daily consumption	Per capita	265.6	289.5	301.4	319.7	340.8	344.1	310	78.5	129.6	9.9	5.32

Eurostat, NIS, 2021, Food balances [2] [4] [5].

Resources through usable production as well as imports have increased, which means that the consumption requirements of the population are still growing. Thus, the production increased by 138 thousand tons (annual growth rate

of 2.87%), and the import increased by 176 thousand tons, respectively an annual rate of 7.84% increased by 152 thousand tons, respectively with a rate of 5.14%.

-At the same time, the average daily food consumption of the meat product is noticeable, which shows a high increase, from 265.6 calories/capita to 344.1 calories/capita, respectively of 78.5 calories/capita, with an annual growth rate of 5.32%.

i) for fish which is one of the foods that nutritionists recommend for a nutritionally balanced diet. Fish meat is an excellent source of omega-3 and omega-6 essential fatty acids, proteins, vitamins (A, B12, D, E) and minerals (potassium, iron, iodine, phosphorus, selenium) [9]. In a study, for the period 2014-2018, it is estimated that fish consumption increased to 30.7 g / day in 2014 to 52.5 g/day for men and 28.7 g/day to 46.1 g/day for women [8].

The analysis of the period 2014-2019, for the agri-food product **FISH (in fresh fish equivalent, Table 9)** shows the certain trends of an annual increase.

At all indicators of the coefficient of variation there are positive values which indicate a higher or sometimes smaller grouping around the average value, this coefficient being considered as the result of a sensitivity to the presence of extreme values.

Of note is the increase in imports of fish and fish products, from 87 thousand tons in 2014 to 140 thousand tons in 2019, with an increase of 53 thousand tons (160%), and an annual growth rate of 9.98 %.

Table 9. Food balance and daily food consumption of **Fish** and fish products (equivalent to fresh fish)

Specification	MU	years						Average	2019 / vs 2014		CV	Annual rhythm
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MU	MU	%	%	%
Resources	TH. to	102	114	119	128	135	163	127	61.0	159.8	16.6	9.83
Usable production	TH. to	15	20	2.3	26	2.3	24	22	9.0	160.0	17.7	9.86
Import	TH. to	87	95	96	103	112	140	106	53.0	160.9	17.9	9.98
applications	TH. to	102	114	119	128	135	163	127	61.0	159.8	16.6	9.83
Export	TH. to	3.6	4.1	3.3	5.2	6.2	11.9	6	8.3	330.6	56.2	27.01
Internal availability for consumption	TH. to	98	110	115	123	29	151	104	53.0	154.1	39.3	9.03
Average daily consumption	Per capita	9.4	10.6	11.3	12.2	12.9	15	12	5.6	159.6	16.4	9.80

Eurostat, NIS, 2021, Food balances [2] [4] [5].

At the same time, the average daily food consumption of fish and meat products is noticed, which has a high increase, from 9.4 calories/capita to 15 calories/capita, respectively of 5.6 calories/capita, with an annual rate of increase of 9.86%.

j) for the agri-food product vegetable and animal FATS (in tons), from the analysis of the indicators presented in **Table 10**, slightly increasing levels can be found during the analyzed period.

There is an increase in imports from 141 thousand tons in 2014 to 160 thousand tons in 2019 (average annual rate of 2.56%), while exports show an increase of 75 thousand tons (average annual rate of 9.94%).

Table 10. Nutrition balance and daily food intake of **vegetable and animal Fats** (tons)

Specification	MU	years						Average	2019 / vs 2014		CV	Annual rhythm
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MU	MU	%	%	%
Resources	Th. to	539	551	561	575	581	588	566	49.0	109.1	3.3	1.76
Usable production	Th. to	398	404	416	426	430	427	417	29.0	107.3	3.2	1.42
Import applications	Th. to	141	147	144	148	151	160	149	19.0	113.5	4.4	2.56
Export	Th. to	539	551	561	575	581	588	566	49.0	109.1	3.3	1.76
Internal availability for consumption	Th. to	66	57	70	70	79	106	75	40.0	160.6	22.7	9.94
Average daily consumption	Per capita	473	494	491	504	502	482	491	9.0	101.9	2.4	0.37
		453.4	477.7	482.3	488.2	480.6	481.9	477	28.5	106.3	2.6	1.23

Eurostat, NIS, 2021, Food balances [2] [4] [5].

At the same time, the average daily food consumption of vegetable and animal fats is noticeable, it remains around $f = 477$ calories/capita, with a coefficient of variation of 2.6%.

For the present paper considered a qualitative side, it was a comparative set *of the evolution of the caloric share of agri-food products in consumption and the value share of GDP in our country* for the period 2014-2019 through the elements that were shown in **Tables 11 and 12**.

Table 11. The evolution of the caloric share of food products in daily food consumption in our country, during 2014-2019

Specification	MU	years						Average	2019 / vs 2014		CV	Annual rhythm
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	MU	MU	%	%	%
Cereals	Cal/capita (%)	41.7	41.1	40.7	40.5	39.5	39.3	40	-2.4	94.2	2.3	-1.18
Potatoes	Cal/capita (%)	6.3	5.9	5.8	5.8	5.7	5.5	6	-0.8	87.3	4.6	-2.68
Leguminous grains	Cal/capita (%)	0.9	0.8	0.5	0.6	1	1	1	0.1	111.1	26.2	2.13
vegetables	Cal/capita (%)	4.1	3.8	3.7	3.8	4.1	4	4	-0.1	97.6	4.4	-0.49
Sugar, products sugar	Cal/capita (%)	7.5	8.8	8.7	8.2	8.6	8.7	8	1.2	116.0	5.9	3.01
Milk, dairy products	Cal/capita (%)	14.6	14	14.2	14.1	14.3	14.4	14	-0.2	98.6	1.5	-0.28
Eggs	Cal/capita (%)	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.8	1.7	1.7	2	-0.1	94.4	5.0	-1.14
Meat (without fish)	Cal/capita (%)	8.4	8.8	9.2	9.8	10.3	10.4	9	2.0	123.8	8.6	4.36
Over	Cal/capita (%)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.5	0	0.2	166.7	22.3	10.76
FATS	Cal/capita (%)	14.3	14.6	14.8	14.9	14.5	14.5	15	0.2	101.4	1.5	0.28
TOTAL	Cal/capita (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	x	x	x	x	x

Eurostat, NIS, 2021, Food balances [2] [4] [5].

Thus, regarding the analyzed products, they were analyzed, being represented by a trivalence nominated by: the structure of agri-food products, these being hierarchized in the following steps:

* cereals, milk and dairy products and fats that remain with the highest share in consumption (between 14% and 40%);

* vegetables, sugar and potatoes with weights between 4% and 8%;

* eggs, legumes and fish in which the weight level is delimited at the level of 1.8% and below 1%.

At the same time, the coefficient of variation remains high for leguminous grains and fish, for which the annual rate is between -2.7 and 8.8.).

The *evolution of the share of food expenditures in GDP* in some EU countries was also shown below, compared for the period 2014-2019, which shows the following (**Table 12**):

-it notes that the lowest level of food expenditure is recorded in countries such as Portugal, Ireland, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany; France, Luxembourg, Austria and Sweden which can be considered as national territories with high living standards,

- and countries where the share of food expenditures represents high levels such as Greece with 11.0%, Bulgaria with 11.2% and Romania with 14.7%, considered countries with low living standards.

Table 12. Evolution of the share of food expenditures in GDP, in some EU countries, during 2014-2019

Specification	MU	years						Average MU	2019 / vs 2014		CV %	Annual rhythm %
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019		MU	%		
EU27	%	6.47	6.37	6.32	6.26	6.24	6.2	6	-0.3	95.8	1.6	-0.85
Belgium	%	5.81	5.81	5.82	5.76	5.74	5.67	6	-0.1	97.6	1.0	-0.49
Bulgaria	%	11.76	11.61	11.46	11.17	11.05	10.42	11	-1.3	88.6	4.3	-2.39
Czech Republic	%	7.14	6.91	6.91	6.83	6.61	6.49	7	-0.6	90.9	3.4	-1.89
Germany	%	4.74	4.75	4.71	4.65	4.69	4.72	5	0.0	99.6	0.8	-0.08
Ireland	%	3.61	2.72	2.73	2.49	2.33	2.2	3	-1.4	60.9	18.7	-9.43
Greece	%	11.01	11.22	10.95	11.01	10.9	10.83	11	-0.2	98.4	1.2	-0.33
Spain	%	7.38	7.24	7.03	6.82	6.87	6.81	7	-0.6	92.3	3.4	-1.59
France	%	6.52	6.45	6.47	6.37	6.29	6.24	6	-0.3	95.7	1.7	-0.87
Italy	%	8.05	8.08	7.97	8.01	7.95	7.94	8	-0.1	98.6	0.7	-0.27
Luxembourg	%	2.72	2.66	2.67	2.62	2.6	2.58	3	-0.1	94.9	2.0	-1.05
Hungary	%	7.85	7.76	7.65	7.76	7.48	7.38	8	-0.5	94.0	2.4	-1.23
Austria	%	4.74	4.69	4.58	4.56	4.49	4.44	5	-0.3	93.7	2.5	-1.30
Poland	%	9.34	8.88	8.97	8.86	8.54	8.48	9	-0.9	90.8	3.5	-1.91
Portugal	%	11.16	11.03	10.89	10.71	10.5	10.28	11	-0.9	92.1	3.1	-1.63
Romania	%	15.35	14.73	15.01	14.85	15.15	13.32	15	-2.0	86.8	4.9	-2.80
Sweden	%	4.97	4.87	4.91	4.83	4.87	4.85	5	-0.1	97.6	1.0	-0.49

Source: Eurostat: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tec00009/default/table?lang=en> [2].

Conclusions

- (1) Throughout the period, Romania's agri-food resources show positive annual growth rates: cereals (6.61%), leguminous grains (23.17%), meat (4.61%), fish (9.83%) except for potato products (-3, 55%) and eggs (-2.9%).
- (2) The trend of import of agri-food products is increasing for cereals (5.68%), leguminous grains (8.45% $_$), vegetables (9.41%), sugar (18.34%), milk (14.87) , eggs (6.97%), meat (7.84%), fish (9.98%).
- (3) The export trend of agri-food products shows increases for cereal products (6.9%), leguminous grains (72.78%), eggs (10.24%), fish (27.01%) and decreases for vegetable products (-5, 59%), sugar (-5.97%).
- (4) The share of food products in the average daily consumption, expressed in horse/loc, for the period 2014-2019, has coefficients of variation up to 8.6% for most products, except for the grain legume product of 26.2% and the fish product and preparations of over 22.3%.
- (5) There are annual increases in the share of products: leguminous by 2.13%; for meat by 4.36% and for fish by 10.76%.
- (6) The share of food expenditure in GDP differs greatly from one country to another within the European Union. The lowest share is in Luxembourg of 2.6%, Ireland 2.7%, Austria 4.6%, and at the opposite pole Greece with 11.0%, Bulgaria with 11.2% and Romania with 14.7%.

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THE INFLUENCE OF DAM'S BIOMETRICS MEASUREMENTS ON DYSTOCIA INCIDENCE IN BROWN BREED-THE LOSSES CAUSED BY DYSTOCIA IN CALF'S GROWTH PERFORMANCE

Radu Ionel NEAMȚ¹, Silviu Ilie SĂPLĂCAN², Ramona LILE³

Abstract. *The aim of the current study was to assess the influence of the dam's biometrics measurements on dystocia incidence in Brown cows. The second goal was to assess the loss caused by dystocia calving in calf growth performances. A total of 1440 records from 360 cows was collected between 2012 - 2020 and used to study the potential influencing factors. Data were analyzed used Statistica software. Biometrics measurements were expressed as least squares means (\pm standard error) used the Main Effect ANOVA protocol. A factorial regression model was employed to explain the influence level of studied factors. The average rate of dystocia in herd was 12.77%. Significant differences ($p \leq 0.01$) were calculated between body weights of eutocyal compared with dystocial calves (32.73 ± 0.51 kg vs. 38.12 ± 0.22 kg). Small size of dam's pelvic size facilitated occurrence of dystocia in calving. Significance differences ($p \leq 0.01$) were recorded for cows body weight (621.3 ± 7.22 vs. 649.18 ± 7.21 kg related to dystocia vs eutocya calving), rump length (52.13 ± 0.18 vs. 49.87 ± 1.24 , $p \leq 0.01$), width at hips (53.24 ± 0.48 cm vs. 51.17 ± 0.09 cm, $p \leq 0.01$) and width at ischia (36.16 ± 0.17 cm vs 32.97 ± 0.28 cm, $p \leq 0.001$). The dystocia calf recorded a 12.36% loss in body weight compared to eutocya ones, at 90 days of age. The current study could provide valuable knowledge regarding the relationship between the specificity of the Brown breed for dams-calf related factors, in terms of risk of dystocia incidence and also in calf growth rate.*

Keywords: Brown breed, dam-calf related factors, dystocia incidence, growth rate, risk of dystocia

1. Introduction

The term dystocia originates from the Greek language, composed of the terms 'dys', meaning difficult, and 'tokos' meaning birth. Generally, dystocia is defined as a difficult and prolonged calving. There are many definitions and scales in order to assess birth difficulty. Dystocia widely ranges from needed veterinary assistance [25] to difficult and very difficult birth [18] or hard pull and surgical

¹Senior Researcher Ph.D., Research and Development Station for Bovine, 310059, Arad, Romania, (email: neamtr@yahoo.com)

²Lecturer Ph.D. Aurel Vlaicu University, Faculty of Economics, 310032, Arad, Romania (silviusaplacan@yahoo.com)

³Associate Professor Ph.D., Aurel Vlaicu University, Faculty of Economics, 310032, Arad, Romania, (email: ramona.lile@uav.ro)

intervention [22]. According to the degree of needed assistance, a 5-point scale defined as 1 = unassisted, 2 = slight assistance, 3 = considerable assistance, 4 = considerable force needed and 5 = caesarian, was used by Hossein-Zadeh et al. (2010) to assess birth difficulty [36]. A realistic definition of difficult calving has been offered by Berry D.P. et al. (2007), characterized as “births requiring more attention than usual [5]. Worldwide, the incidence of dystocia range between 2-22% [3]. Different difficulty degree could affect 10% [2] and up to 50% of calving [28] despite lower percentages recorded in other studies, ranging between 4.1% [41], 3-5% [23] or even 1.9% [55].

There are various factors that could cause dystocia such as genetic, management and environmental related factors [2]. Dystocia risk increased proportionally with calves' birth weight due to a strong and negative correlation between these two parameters [56]. A significant influence in dystocia occurrence is represented by a combo between calves' body weight and dams' pelvic area size, where the latter is involved in parturition. Dams' pelvic area size defines the oversized calves. Dystocia negatively affects the production, reproduction and animal welfare. Difficult calving leads to an increased percentage of death in calves. In this respect, Murray et al. (2015) found that 15.9% of calves died up to weaning and 8.1% of calves died during the parturition or within the first 48 hours [47]. Survival of calves presented a decreased vitality, which induced a lower capacity to perform with significant repercussions on subsequent efficiency, physiology and behaviour. A negative long-term effect was recorded by Henderson et al. (2004) on adult age of calves that experienced dystocia regarding production and reproductive performances [30]. Quantifying the milk production decrease, Bicalho et al. (2007) recorded a 0.8 kg milk/day loss, which was maintained throughout lactation [6] due to a higher genetic correlation (0.23-0.34) according to Eaglen et al. 2013 [16]. The occurrence of dystocia decreases reproductive performances, negatively affecting all related traits. Dystocia led to an increase in number of services, a prolonged voluntary waiting period and, implicitly, a prolonged service period. A study conducted by Tenhagen et al. (2007) highlighted a decreased rate of conception until 200 DIM, thus increasing service period for cows that experienced dystocia [57]. Generally, occurrence of dystocia in farms led to significant losses at all levels. Stillbirths caused by difficult labor accounted for \$125 million/year losses, according to Meyer et al. (2001) [46]. Dystocia accounted for 41% of losses due to production costs, 34% of losses due to reproductive decreased performances costs and 25% of losses due to of morbidity or mortality in herd's costs. Mee (2008) citing Oltenacu et al., (1988) reported that the impact of dystocia reached four times greater costs than its treatment [44]. Numerous attempts have been made in order to decrease incidence of difficult calving and associated mortality in herds. The heritability of dystocia has been studied for a long time now. A moderate coefficient (0.17) was recently

calculated by Gabriela Stefani et al. (2021), indicating that dystocia incidence could be partly reduced through selection [54]. An early previous study conducted by Thompson et al., (1984) recorded a moderate-high heritability coefficient (0.24) by regression of dam to daughter [58]. These results were in contradiction with other authors' results [11, 35] which recorded a very low heritability for this trait, ranging from 0.01 to 0.09. In general, heritability of dystocia is considered relatively high, given the significant effects of various non-genetic influential factors [61].

On the other hand, calf-related traits which exert influence on the calving ease are characterized by highly heritability. In this respect, numerous studies were conducted in order to set up values for the heritability coefficients since several decades. Studies aimed to predict the incidence of dystocia have been based prior to selection on the involved calves' related traits such as body dimensions or body weight at birth. These traits proved to be characterized by a high heritability. In this respect, an early study conducted by Price and Wiltbank (1978) [51] found significant heritability for calves' body length (0.35), width at hip (0.42) or body weight (0.28), results also confirmed by Holm et al. (2014) who recorded an even higher heritability (0.44) for calves' body weight [34].

In order to predict the risk of dystocia occurrence, both internal and external pelvimetry constituted a viable attempt, beginning to widely use in the cattle industry [34]. In general, external pelvimetry is an easy and non-invasive way to measure the pelvic area and can be used in practice due to the strong and positive correlations calculated in relation to internal pelvimetry [52]. The pelvimetry was considered as a method of predicting the risk of dystocia all the more so as is responsible for 5-10% of the variation in dystocia [42]. The average pelvis growth rate reaches 0.27 cm² per day up to two years of age and this fixed correction factor can be used to adjust pelvic area based on the age at which measurements are obtained. This value are considered as an adjustment coefficient in order to predict the pelvic area at adult age, based on the next formula:

$$365 \text{ Days Pelvic Area} = \text{Actual Pelvic Area (cm}^2\text{)} + [0.27(365 - \text{age in days})] \text{ [27]}$$

The numerous attempts in order to reduce the incidence of dystocia in the herds have also been based on the high heritability of the pelvic area, which facilitates direct selection for this trait. Concerns about the heritability of the pelvic area have long been the subject of intense research in numerous previous studies. In this sense, most studies found a highly heritability range 0.36-0.92 with an average value around 0.61 [13]. By selecting both bulls and heifers for pelvic size, a herd of cows with large pelvic areas could be developed which led to a decreased incidence of difficult calving.

Concluding, the pelvimetry could be a tool capable to predict the risk of dystocia occurrence and should be used in order to minimize the incidence and the negative effects of its in herds. Also, heritability of dystocia and calves body measurements should be integrating in breeding programs as an attempt to decrease the incidence of dystocia.

2. Materials and Methods

Location: The study was carried out in livestock biobase from Research and Development Station for Bovine Arad, Romania (location: 46° 10' 36" N, 21° 18' 4" E, 107 m altitude, 582 mm annual average rainfall 21°C/-1°C average of temperature corresponding seasons summer/winter). Geographically, the experiments were carried out in the Western Plain of Romania.

The confinement system: The confinement system applied in farm is a semi-intensive system type characterized by moderate gains rate for the categories of youth (500-750 g/day) and moderate productive values for dairy cows (5,088-6,200 kg/lactation). Newborn calves are separated from their dams within first 20 minutes after birth, kept in individual pens up to seven days of age, located in space intended of maternity. Between 8-90 days, calves are kept in individual hutch on straw bed with free access to the resting area (1.8 m²/head) and moving area (2.3 m²/head). The administration of dairy diet is made in the first three days with maternal colostrum and the next four days with raw milk from his own dam. From the eighth day, raw milk is administered from collector tank. The administration of dairy diet is made in two daily portions, every 12 hours (6 am and 18 pm). In parallel, starting from the 4th day of life, calves receive water, alfa-alfa hay and concentrated forage administered ad libitum until day 60, after which the access is restricted for concentrated forage. Data regarding the calves' body weight were collected within first hour of age.

All cows were included in the Official Performance and Recording Scheme. Cows were milked twice per day (starting at 5:00 and 17:00) in a "herringbone" milking parlour (2 by 14 units). The milking parlour was equipped with AfiMilk 3.076 A-DU software (Afikim, Israel). Furthermore, all cows were fitted with AfiTag pedometers (Afikim, Israel) for production traits, oestrous and specific diseases detection. Production and milk quality data (milk yield, fat yield and percentage, protein yield and percentage) were collected from the results of the official performance recordings, according to the standardized International Committee for Animal Recording (ICAR) guidelines (2012), and also with the proprietary recording system AfiMilk 3.076 A-DU software (Afikim, Israel). Data regarding reproductive performance, type of calving, calving ease and stillborn were recorded by the stockholders in own recording data set. Data regarding cow's body weight were recorded within the last 72 hours before probable date of

calving. Cow's biometric measurements were performed using a compass for external pelvimetry, based on the following lengths, according to Hohnholz et al. (2019) [33].

Table 1. Definitions of dams' external pelvic measurements

Parameter	Unit	Definition
Rump length	cm	Distance between the cranial edge of the tuber coxae and the caudal edge of the tuber ischiadicum
Width at the hips	cm	Distance between the lateral edges of the tuber coxae
Width at the ischia	cm	Distance between the lateral edges of the tuber ischiadicum

Cows included in the current study were managed under a loose system with zero grazing and were between 1st and 4th lactation, with age and parity balanced within the herd. Cows had a space allowance of 9 m² in the resting area and free access to shadow, water and feeding zone. They received a daily feed ration made of 15 kg of fresh cut alfalfa, 15 kg of green fodder, 12 kg corn silage, 6 kg of alfalfa hay and 4 kg of concentrates starting from spring until late autumn, and a ration made of 15 kg alfalfa, 25 kg of corn silages, 6 kg of alfalfa hay and 5 kg of concentrates during winter. Cows were fed twice per day and had a feeding space allowance of 70-75 cm/head. They were housed in groups of 70 animals, according to their productivity.

Use of animals and the procedures performed in this study were approved by the Scientific and Ethics Committee of the Research and Development Station for Bovine Arad of the Academy for Agricultural and Forestry Sciences, Decision no. 51 issued on November 11, 2015. Also, the research activities were performed in accordance with the European Union's Directive for animal experimentation (Directive 2010/63/EU).

Data recording:

A data set of 1,440 recording from 360 lactations collected between 2012 and 2020, was analyzed for estimation of the effects of the calves and dams biometric related traits on incidence of dystocia. Statistical processing and data interpretation process aimed: a) identifying and assessing the influential level of dam's biometric traits on calving ease; b) assessing the influence of studied factors on dystocia incidence. The incidence of dystocia was investigated

according to a) calves' birth weight; b) dams' body weight; c) dams' rump length; d) dams' width at hips and e) dams' width at ischia.

Data were cleaned by eliminating human recording errors (outliers), redundant entries and incomplete observations. Data from cows with abortions or stillborn were discarded. Also, cows with no information for studied traits. Grubbs' test (Grubbs, 1969) was performed in order to detect outliers in a univariate data set that follows an approximately normal distribution [27].

$$G = \frac{\bar{y} - y_{min}}{s} \qquad G = \frac{\bar{y} - y_{max}}{s}$$

where: \bar{y} =sample mean; s =standard deviation; y_{min} =minimum value; y_{max} =maximum value (for individuals measurements)

When suspecting more than one outlier, the Tietjen-Moore test was used to identify and reject them (Tietjen and Moore, 1972) [59].

$$L_k = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-k} (y_i - \bar{y}_k)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{n-k} (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

where: k =exactly k outliers in the data set; n =number of data points sorted from smallest to largest; y_i =the i th largest data value; \bar{y} =mean of the full sample; \bar{y}_k =sample mean with largest k point deleted.

The effect of studied factors on calving ease was assessed using a factorial ANOVA protocol. Differences were tested using Tukey test.

$$DI = CBW_i + DBW_j + RL_k + WI_l + e_{ijkl}$$

where: DI is the dystocia incidence; $YCBW$ =effect of calves body weight at birth; DBW =effect of dams body weight at calving; RL = effect of dams rump length; Wh = effect of dams width at hips; WIs = effect of dams width at ischia.

The analyzed data were expressed as least square means and standard error of mean. Incidence of dystocia were recorded according to biometric factors in order to set up "alarm" thresholds for better designing of the optimal prediction of dystocia occurrence risk protocol. All the statistical inferences were carried out using the software package Statistica (StatSoft Inc., Tulsa, OK USA) [31]. Decisions about the acceptance or rejection of statistical hypothesis have been made at the 0.05 level of significance. A factorial regression model was performed in order to evaluate the influence of studied factors on incidence of dystocia.

$$Y = a + b \dots x \text{ NGf}$$

where: Y is dystocia incidence percentage and NGf are the non-genetic influential factors included in the study.

To determine the effects of non-genetic factors, the traits of interest would be set up as the dependent variables and the dystocia incidence as an independent variable in the model. To determine how influential factors affect the incidence of dystocia, the opposite is done: the dystocia incidence becomes the dependent variable and the influential factors included in the study are the independent variables of interest.

3. Results and discussions

Analyses of data presented in table 1 showed significant differences between studied parameters due to the influential factors. Analyses regarding the incidence of dystocia in herd, highlighted a share of 12.77% from total registered calving.

Table 2. Least square means (\pm standard error) for calves' body weight at birth and dams' biometric measurements according to calving ease

Calving easy	N	Calves' body weight at birth (kg)	Calves' body weight at 90 days of age (kg)	Dams' body weight (kg)	Dams' Rump length (cm)	Dams' Width at hips (cm)	Dams' Width at ischia (cm)
Eutocya	314 ^a	32.73 \pm 0.51 ^a	100.53 \pm 1.51 ^a	649.18 \pm 7.21 ^a	52.13 \pm 0.18 ^a	53.24 \pm 0.48 ^a	36.16 \pm 0.17 ^a
Dystocia	46 ^b	38.12 \pm 0.22 ^b	88.46 \pm 0.93 ^b	621.37 \pm 7.22 ^b	49.87 \pm 1.24 ^b	51.17 \pm 0.09 ^b	32.97 \pm 0.28 ^b

a,b Column means with different superscripts differ significantly at $p \leq 0.05$

Calves body weight at birth presented significance differences ($p \leq 0.01$, $F=9.33$) between eutocyal and dystocial calves. Cows with dystocia births proved to be significantly narrower compared to those with eutocyal calving. In this respect, significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$, $F=18.24$) for cows' body measurements were recorded explaining the interaction between cows' body weight, cows' pelvic area and calving ease (Table 2).

Cow body weight was highly correlated with the pelvic area traits (rump length, width at the hips, width at the ischia), $r=0.2-0.8$. Size of pelvic area alongside calves' birth weight limits the calving ease with severe impact on new born calves' viability.

Cows body weight according to calving ease, had significant differences ($p \leq 0.01$, $F=6.16$) between cows with eutocya vs. those with dystocia calving. Significant differences of 2.26 \pm 0.06 ($p \leq 0.01$, $F=9.23$), 2.07 \pm 0.39 ($p \leq 0.01$, $F=8.87$) and 3.19 \pm 0.27 ($p \leq 0.001$, $F=6.37$) cm were recorded for rump length, width at hips and width at ischia between cows that experienced eutocya compared to those with dystocia.

Calves growth performance was significant influenced by calving ease. A 12.36% loss was recorded according to this particularly parameter.

Table 3. Regression model for estimate of variables effects on calving ease

Influential factors	b*	Std. Err. Of b*	t test	P values
Intercept	-	-	0.56022	0.051578
Calves body weight at birth	0.034	0.011	-2.46520	0.0234
Calves body weight at 90 days	0,012	0,014	-3,1244	0,001
Dams body weight at calving	0.094	0.021	0.045604	0.03486
Dams' Rump length (cm)	0.062	0.017	0.05265	0.03957
Dams' Width at hips	-0.051	0.08	-0.05813	0.019800
Dams' Width at ischia	-0.0013	0.014	6.12091	0.00002

The factorial regression model of the factors influencing the calving ease highlighted a significant interaction ($P < 0.01$), $r = 0.40865347$. The validity of the test was confirmed by the $F = 11.427$. The factorial regression model has shown that calving ease was significantly influenced by the calf birth weight ($p \leq 0.01$), dam's body weight ($p \leq 0.01$), rump length ($p \leq 0.01$), width at the hips ($p \leq 0.01$) and most especially by the width at Ischia ($p < 0.001$).

Difficult calving significant and negative influenced the calf's growth performances in 0-90 days of age interval. Significant differences ($p \leq 0.001$) were recorded in this respect related to calves body weights at 90 days of age (100.53 ± 1.51 vs. 88.46 ± 0.93 kg for eutocya and dystocia calving).

Table 4. Least square means (\pm standard error) for calves' body weight at birth and 90 days of age according to calving ease

Parameters	Calf's body weight at birth (kg)	Calf's body weight at 90 days of age (kg)
Eutocya calves	32.73 ± 0.51^a	100.53 ± 1.51^a
Distocya calves	38.12 ± 0.22^b	88.46 ± 0.93^b

a,b Column means with different superscripts differ significantly at $p \leq 0.05$

Dystocia incidence:

Dystocia causes huge loss in farms. It cannot be predicted, but the incidence can be reduced by management measures if the influential factors are identified. That could be realize through ensuring a comfortable calving area, provide optimal assistance at calving and most importantly, through selection of sires and cows for calving ease (based on an adequate pelvic size), which never been done before in this industry. The calving alongside to the weaning constitutes one of the major stressor on cows' biorhythm. There are vary internal and external influential

factors that could transform the physiological birth into a disturbing element of both dam and calf welfare condition due to occurrence of difficulty in calving process. The inclusion of vary categories of factors in a case study, may determine their involvement related to difficult degree of calving but it does not allow obtaining an exhaustive result in this sense due to dilution of outcomes. The current study aimed analysis of the biometric factors with impact on dystocia incidence in order to establish the effect of the pelvic area on its occurrence. The current incidence of dystocia reached 12.77% in herd. At the first sight this value is in accordance with others results founded worldwide. There are few studies aimed the tendency of dystocia incidence but all of these recognize an increasing trend in all breeds and crossbred [7, 11].

Generally, a higher incidence was observed in dairy compared to beef breed. This statement was proved over the time. In this respect, Hohnholz et al. (2019) [33] found a 3.4% incidence in beef cows which is consistent with an incidence of 5.6% associated to Italian beef breed and recorded by De Amicis et al. (2018) [12] while Steinbock (2006) [55], Hansen et al. (2004) [28] or Mc Clintock (2004) [41] found a slightly increased incidence in Swedisk, Danisk and Australian Jersey crossbreed with Holstein due to “Holsteinization process”. Concluding, an increased proportion of Holstein genes lead to an increased incidence of dystocia, according to numerous studies performed in this sense [13]. Not at least, Mee J.F. et al. (2011) found a huge proportion of needed assistance calving (28-40%) out of 5-9.3% severe dystocia in Holstein [43]. Manual correction could be performed in more than 95% difficult calving, reducing both calves (up to 25%) and dams (up to 11%) mortality [12] compared to those unassisted dystocia calving which tend to increase mortality to over 37% [39]. The incidence of dystocia in primiparous was quantified to be 10-50 % whereas in multiparous the incidence of dystocia ranged between 4-30% [1, 60]. Also, Grohn et al. (1990) reported that the risk of dystocia increased with increasing parity [26]. Conversely, Yildiz H. et al. (2011) found no significant differences related to dystocia incidence according to parity [65].

A customized assessment of dystocia incidence can be developed for each farm depending by the concrete factors that characterize the environment, the general management, the available resources, and especially the individuality of the animals rearing.

Calves' body weight at birth

Calves' growth is largely controlled by various and numerous factors. Body weight at birth (BWB) is strongly correlated with the foetal growth rate, being an important factor in the survivability, performance efficiency and welfare condition of both calves and dams, the latter based most often on calving ease. The main

influential factor in calving ease still remains the foetal-maternal disproportion, especially in primiparous dams. Such disproportion leads to a higher pre- or intrapartum mortality, within 48 hours after calving [33]. Calves' body weight is strongly influenced by genetic factors such as breed and also by non-genetic influential factors such as year or season of calving, dam's parity, calves sex, feeding management in late gestation, as well as by twinning. Calves' body weight at birth is a significant influential factor in calving ease. Increase of body weight at birth with 1 kg could increase the risk of dystocia by up to 0.23% [48].

Conversely, Johanson and Berger (2003) recorded that for 1 kg increased body weight there was a 13% increase in risk of dystocia [37]. Also, in the same study, an increased risk of dystocia ranging between 2.1-9.6% was associated to an increase in body weight ranging between 29-52 kg. Similar results were recorded by Berry et al (2007), who estimated a 15% increased risk of difficult calving for calves' body weight at birth ranging between 20-50 kg [5]. Conversely, Eckterkamp et al. (1999, 2007) found no significant difference regarding the calves' body weight at birth in eutocious or dystocious calving [19, 20]. A possible explanation could be the direct correlation between the surface of the pelvic area and calving ease. In this case, the width at the ischia plays a major role in calving. The calf's body weight at birth doesn't seem to be the limiting factor related to calving ease. The strong correlation between the calf's body weight at birth and width at ischia seems to be the limiting factor.

The current research found a significant difference related to calves' body weight at birth according to gender, males being heavier on average than females. These results are in accordance with the previous findings of Dkahal K. et al. (2013) and Kwanghyun C. et al. (2021) [14, 9].

In addition, calves' body weight at birth proved to be significantly influenced by different factors. Olson et al. (2009) and found significant differences according to twinning, also a 3.86 higher risk of dystocia in twinning [50]. The season of calving could influence the calves' body weight at birth. The results are inconsistent in this sense in previous studies. Wells et al. (1996) found higher body weight at birth for calves delivered in winter, implying a higher risk of dystocia [63]. Similar results were recorded by Cho et al. (2021) [9].

Generally, body weight at birth is higher in winter due to the confinement system and the weather, which does not allow access to pasture in order to facilitate energy consumption as it is redirected to the foetal development and feeding system which does not include the green forage but only high nutritional density feeds. Related to this issue, the previous results obtained proved to be consistent in this respect [43, 56]. Different body weight at birth observations were recorded according to dams' breed and under crossbreeding effects, inducing different

incidence of difficult calving. In this sense, Olson et al. (2009) recorded heavier calves in Holstein compared to Jersey or in Jersey x Holstein compared to Holstein x Jersey [50].

Dam's pelvic area

Significant differences were associated with dam's body measurements according to calving ease. Generally, a higher incidence of dystocia was recorded for dams with lower body weight and lower surface of pelvic area. Our findings were in accordance with those recorded in a study conducted by Bures et al. (2008), which found larger measurements for dam's body weight and pelvic dimensions in eutocya compared to dystocia in cows [7]. Dam's body weight did not directly affect calving ease but it is a pretty good indicator for the risk of dystocia due to a strong correlation with the pelvic area ($R=0.8$) [24]. A higher impact exerts dystocia in dam's body weight after calving [5]. However, studies conducted over the years have shown that a higher dam's body weight could significantly reduce the risk of dystocia occurrence [32, 45].

The pelvic area proved to be a limitative factor in calving ease. Even if it only has the capacity to increase up to 10-15% at the calving, its original size still remains a tool for predicting the risk of dystocious calving [45]. In this respect, a greater area generally leads to an easier calving. Johanson and Berger (2003) recorded a decreased incidence of dystocia of up to 11% due to an increased pelvic area by 1 dm² [37]. The association between the pelvic area and the calf's body weight at birth proved to be the combination with the maximum impact on calving ease. Numerous studies aimed the ratio between these two factors, proving that the pelvic area alone determines only 10% of dystocia phenotypic variance [49].

Losses caused by dystocia calving

In the current research, a significant impact of calving ease was recorded related to calves' viability. The eutocious calving allows setting up a metabolic and physiological balance that facilitates phenotypic outsourcing of hereditary dowry in terms of growth performances. From this point of view, significant differences related to calf's body weight at 90 days of age were recorded. Previous results are inconsistent. As such, several studies found no significant effects of dystocia in growth processes [4, 8, 29, 40]. Other studies found opposing results [15, 64]. A possible cause could be the fact that the calves from dystocious births die during the first days after calving. Also, some studies considered that moderate dystocia has no long-term effects on animal performances. Conversely, there are numerous studies that have found otherwise [17].

In our study, a long-term effect of dystocia was recorded in terms of body weight at 90 days of age, the losses reaching 12.36%. Increasing losses and delays in terms of body weight are based on a decreased calf's viability. Generally,

dystocious calving induces a higher cortisol level which reflects a response of hypothalamic-adrenal axis in order to prepare and allow adaptation to a new extrauterine environment [10]. Also, calves that experienced a difficult calving recorded lower levels of immunoglobulin intake and its passive transfer (50% cases compared to 20% in eutocya). A failure in passive transfer leads to a decreased protection against specific diseases [62].

Severe dystocia could lead to a hypoxic state in calves with negative effects in immunoglobulin absorption. Lower immunoglobulin absorption was generally considered as an effect of lower vigor of calves and it is often associated to a significant delay in colostrum consumption and lower amount of colostrum intake. In conclusion, lower viability in dystocia calves could lead to a negative expression of performance.

Conclusions

- (1) The current research highlights connections between calving ease and some influential factors thereof.
- (2) Also, the effects of dystocia calving in calf's performances up to weaning. Calves welfare condition could be assessed based on their performance. In this sense the calf's welfare condition is directly influenced by the calving ease.
- (3) The higher calf's body weight at birth influenced negatively calving ease.
- (4) The dimensions of pelvic area are influential factors on calving ease especially the ratio between calf's size and dam's measurements.
- (5) Ensuring good management practices in calving could be a viable solution in obtaining viable calves which perform efficiently.

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SMALL MECHANIZATION - AN ALTERNATIVE FOR INDIVIDUAL MOUNTAIN FARMS

Tudor Adrian ENE¹, Vasile MOCANU²

Abstract. *Regardless of the main concern of the inhabitants of the mountain area, the mechanization of the works from their own household has a special importance in the development and efficiency of the activity by achieving high working capacities, shortening execution times, reducing the necessary physical effort, diminishing the necessary labour force, promoting a modern ecological activity. Only mechanization allows the achievement of superior work capacities with a reduced consumption of labour and physical effort. In this paper are presented some new machines, designed and made for the mechanization of some technological links, in aggregate with low power tractors.*

Keywords: mechanization, grassland, individual mountain farms, management, technological solutions

1. Introduction

In the mountainous area, on the agricultural surfaces, a series of restrictive factors on the production act, such as: the slope and the deficient orography of the land with small and irregular surfaces; climate (due to high altitude); low fertility; skeleton and rock on the surface; surface erosion; deep erosion and landslides; high acidity; invasion with worthless vegetation. Due to the action of these limiting factors, the agricultural yields obtained are lower than those obtained in other more favorable areas of the lowland-plains regions.

From the surface of meadows in our country, approx. 4.9 million hectares, over 2.94 million hectares (60 %) are located in hilly and mountainous areas.

Concerning to conditions in which the farm is located, the mechanization of agricultural works is of particular importance for: high work capacity; reducing the necessary physical effort; decreasing the need for labor per production unit; and increasing the economic efficiency of the farm etc.

Today it is inconceivable that a farmer in the mountain area can live only on the income from his own activity without benefiting from a high degree of farming mechanization. Only mechanization allows for higher work efficiency with reduced labor and physical effort.

¹PhD, Eng., Junior Researcher, Research and Development Institute for Grassland Braşov, Romania, (e-mail: tudorene@yahoo.com).

²Prof., PhD, Eng., Senior Researcher, Research and Development Institute for Grassland Braşov, Romania, (e-mail: vasmocanu@yahoo.com).

In many cases, even in a high degree of mechanization, the income per unit area differs depending on the topography of the land because:

- production decreases with increasing slope;
- the cost of the works increases proportionally with the increase of the slope (on the one hand due to the work capacity, which decreases with the increase of the slope, and on the other hand due to the higher afferent cost of the machines specific to work on sloping lands).

The influence of the land slope on the mechanization of agricultural works is of high importance for building new machines and equipments destined to be used in grasslands farming.

The slope of the land has a major influence on the possibilities of grassland farming mechanization because over 66.5 % of their surface is located on lands with a slope of over 8 % (4.57 °) [8].

As the number and intensity of agricultural work on hayfields is much higher than on pastures, Table 1 shows the distribution of this area according to the slope of the land. It is observed that 68.9 % of the surface of permanent hayfields is located on slopes greater than 8 % (4.57 °).

Table 1. Distribution of permanent hayfields by slope [8]

No.	Slope of the land		% of total hay area
	%	°	%
1	< 2	< 1.15	20.1
2	2 ... 5	1.15 ... 2.86	4.7
3	5 ... 8	2.86 ... 4.57	6.3
4	8 ... 12	4.57 ... 6.84	11.7
5	12 ... 18	6.84 ... 10.20	17.7
6	18 ... 25	10.20 ... 14.00	20.8
7	25 ... 50	14.00 ... 26.56	15.0
8	> 50	> 26.56	3.7

The slope of the land influences the farming mechanization due to the additional, disruptive forces it generates. Thus, the slope of the land produces a series of technical and functional problems when working with specific machines on meadows, which have a negative effect on [2, 3, 4, 5]: quality of work; work capacity; safety in operation of the aggregates; the required actuating power; the condition of the vegetal carpet of the meadow; and costs on energy and materials.

Agricultural machinery system represents the totality of machines, machinery and equipment intended for carrying out agricultural works.

Specific machine system: machinery, equipment and machinery necessary for the mechanization of agricultural work in a particular field.

Depending on the type of agricultural work, the machine system specific to the mechanization of meadow farming is divided into the following categories:

- a) Equipment and machinery for grassland maintenance works (Figure 1);
- b) Equipment and machinery for grassland improvement works:
 - b1) improvement works by surface methods (Figure 2);
 - b2) improvement works by radical methods (Figure 3).

Fig. 1. Specific equipment and machinery for grassland maintenance works.

Fig. 2. Specific equipment and machinery for grassland improving by surface methods.

Fig. 3. Specific equipment and machinery for grassland improvement by radical methods.

In this context, the purpose of the paper was to pay attention to the creation of an agricultural machinery system which has to respond to the needs of the farmers, research and development stations, parks and recreational areas situated in the mountain areas of Romania.

This new agricultural machinery system is useful for working the land using small mechanization adapted to small surfaces and various slopes.

2. Materials and Methods

In this research work, new agricultural machinery for small mechanization was designed, realized and tested within Research-Development Institute for Grassland Braşov, Romania.

The machines, machinery and equipments were built in such a way to be suitable for individual farms, experimental fields, parks and recreational areas in the mountain zone etc.

The study presents the following experimental models: the equipment Type EP-4 for hoeing the experimental fields, a Fixed-tooth harrow, type GCF 2.0, a Plow, type PP-1-20, a Sowing machine, type MS 7, and a Sowing machine, type MS 9, regarding their image and technical characteristics.

The concept, design, execution and tests of the experimental models were achieved by the researchers whose expertise is in the field of mechanization.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Experimental field hoeing equipment, type EP 4

The equipment for hoeing the experimental fields, type EP 4 (Figure 4), mobilizes the soil between the rows of seed plots (grasses and perennial legumes of grassland) or other crops, performing weed eradication and works necessary for the maintenance technology.

Fig. 4. Work aspects of the experimental model for field hoeing, type EP 4

Table 2. Main technical characteristics of the Experimental field hoeing equipment, type EP 4 [1]

No.	Characteristics	Specifications
1	Equipment type	carried
2	Energy source	9.5 ... 22 kW (13 ... 30 HP)
3	Operating width	2.4 m
4	Number of operating sections: - L-shaped knives - arrow knives	4 pcs 8 pcs (4 left + 4 right) 4 pcs
5	Overall dimensions: - length: - width: - height:	1,100 mm 2,620 mm 1,350 mm
6	Equipment weight	120 kg

The EP 4 experimental model is a type of agricultural equipment carried by the three-point linkage mechanism (category I) of the drive tractor. It consists of the following main parts: the assembled frame; four independent sections; active organs; two operating wheels.

The section articulated mounting on the frame, through of the parallelogram mechanism, allows copying the ground unevenness (in vertical-longitudinal plane and in vertical- transversal plane) without changing the angle of attack of the operating organs.

3.2. Fixed-tooth harrow, type GCF 2.0

Fixed-tooth harrow, type GCF 2.0 (Fig. 5), is used to aerate the meadows in early spring, as well as to clean/spread the manure after the end of each grazing cycle.

This is an agricultural machine of the carried type on the three-point linkage mechanism of the drive tractors.

Fig. 5. Aspect of the experimental fixed angle harrow model, type GCF 2.0

The main components of the fixed-tooth harrow are: assembled frame; field of harrows with fixed fangs; harrow support chains.

Table 3 shows the main technical characteristics of the experimental fixed-tooth harrow model, type GCF 2.0.

Table 3. Main technical characteristics of the experimental fixed-tooth harrow model, type GCF 2.0

No.	Characteristics	Specifications
1	Energy source	Wheel tractors of 9.5...22 kW (13...30 HP);
2	Operating width	2.0 m;
3	Number of toothed harrows	2 pcs;
	• number of teeth / harrow field:	25 pcs;
	• total teeth number:	50 pcs;
	• the distance between two consecutive teeth	40 mm;
4	Overall dimensions	
	- length:	1,250 mm;
	- width:	2,100 mm;
	- height:	1,000 mm;
5	Weight	80 kg

3.3. Plow, type PP-1-20

The plow, type PP-1-20, is used for cultivating the soil in furrows, crushing and overturning them to a certain depth in the arable layer of the soil on arable land, respectively on the crop areas, perennial and grassland fodder plants to be improved by complete restoration (Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Aspect of the experimental carried plow model, type PP-1-20

The plow is an agricultural machine of the carried type on the three-point linkage mechanism of the drive tractor.

The main components of the plow are: assembled frame and a working body consisting of a operating device with a corman.

Table 4 shows the main technical characteristics of the experimental carried plow model, type PP-1-20.

Table 4. Technical characteristics of the experimental carried plow model, type PP-1-20

No.	Characteristics	Specifications
1.	Energy source	Wheel tractor of 9.5...22 kW (13...30 HP);
2.	Operating width	20 cm;
3.	Operating deep	20 cm;
4.	Overall dimensions	
	- length:	1,100 mm;
	- width:	600 mm;
	- height:	500 mm;
5.	Weight	30 kg

3.4. Sowing machine, type MS 7

The machine (Figure 7) is used for sowing grassland fodder plants on relatively small areas, in experimental fields, in parks, in recreational areas etc.

In addition to sowing, it also performs rolling before sowing.

The experimental sowing machine, MS 7, is a self-propelled agricultural machine. It has a single-cylinder spark-ignition heat engine that develops 2.57 kW (3.5 HP). From this, through the centrifugal clutch, the snail-wheel drive, the PTO shaft and a chain drive, the movement reaches the roller, through which the car is propelled. The seed metering devices are also driven by a chain drive and the agitators by a two-wheel drive.

The main components of the machine are: assembled frame; seed hopper; sowing equipment; the mechanism for transmitting motion to the dosing apparatus and agitators; heat engine; roller; support wheel; horns for handling the machine.

Fig. 7. Sowing machine, type MS 7:

a. Aspect of the experimental model;

b. Work aspect.

Table 5 shows the main technical characteristics of the experimental sowing machine model, type MS 7.

Table 5. Technical characteristics of the experimental sowing machine model, type MS 7 [7]

No.	Characteristics	Specifications
1.	Operating engine	
	- type	single-cylinder
	- power	2.57 kW (3.5 HP);
2.	Operating width	87.5 cm;
3.	Number of coulters	7 pcs;
4.	Inter-row distance	12.5 cm;
5.	Sowing deep	0.5...4.0 cm;
6.	Type of metering devices	fluted cylinders;
7.	Type of coulters	simple cultural;
8.	Seed box volume	25 l;
9.	Overall dimensions	
	- length:	1,540 mm;
	- width:	1,040 mm;
	- height:	1,090 mm;
10.	Weight	140 kg

3.5. Sowing machine, type MS 9

The machine is intended for sowing grassland fodder plants or other crops on relatively small plots, individual farms, experimental fields, parks, recreational areas etc. (Figure 8).

Fig. 7. Aspect of the experimental sowing machine model, type MS 9

The sowing machine, type MS 9, is agricultural machinery carried on the three-point linkage mechanism of the drive tractors.

The main components of the seed drill are: assembled frame; seed box; sowing equipment; the mechanism for transmitting the motion to the metering apparatus and agitators and ring harrow to cover sown seeds. The power source is an all-wheel drive articulated tractor of 9.5 kW (13 HP).

During the aggregate operating time, the sowing equipment distributes, through the pipes and the cultural coulters, the desired species or seed mixture, and a harrow with metal rings covers with cultivated soil the sown seeds.

The drive of the seed metering devices is done from the wheel of the seed drill, by means of a chain transmission, and of the agitators by means of a cam mechanism.

By using cylindrical fluted seed distributors changing the active length of the grooved distributors, corroborated with the adjustment of the movable bottoms, different sowing rates can be achieved.

Table 6 shows the main technical characteristics of the experimental sowing machine model, type MS 9.

Table 6. Technical characteristics of the experimental sowing machine model, type MS 9 [6]

<i>No.</i>	<i>Characteristics</i>	<i>Specifications</i>
1.	Energy source	Wheel tractors of 9.5...25.7 kW (13...35 HP);
2.	Operating width	112.5 cm;
3.	Number of coulters	9 pcs
4.	Inter-row distance	12.5/25.0/50.0 cm;
5.	Sowing deep	0.5...4.0 cm
6.	Type of metering devices	fluted cylinders
7.	Type of coulters	simple cultural;
8.	Seed box volume	100 l;
9.	Overall dimensions	
	- length:	950 mm;
	- width:	1,555 mm;
	- height:	850 mm;
10.	Weight	160 kg.

Conclusions

- (1) The experimental models presented in the paper are suitable for individual farms in the mountain area.
- (2) They have small dimensions and weight, being an advantage both for performing the agricultural works executed in the slope conditions and from the point of view of the environment protection through a lower compaction of the soil.
- (3) They perform work indices corresponding to the specific agrotechnical requirements of the farming works.
- (4) They require relatively smaller energy sources, which are relatively cheaper and more easily accessible from a financial point of view.

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THE INVOLVEMENT OF DEUTERIUM PRESENCE IN THE *Drosophila melanogaster* EVOLUTION I. EFFECTS OF DEUTERIUM CONCENTRATIONS UPON THE *White* (w^{1118}) GENOTYPE

Gallia BUTNARU^{1*}, Ioan SARAC², Sorina POPESCU³,
Gheorghe TITESCU⁴, Diana COSTINEL⁵

Abstract: To determine the action of different deuterium concentrations on the phenotype of *drosophila* individuals, the w^{1118} genotype was used over 5 generations. D concentrations ranged from 30ppm up to 24.22% [1%= 1,000ppm], creating 6 gradients. The observation has been done at: female prolificacy, larvae motility, pupation height, number of female and male adults and finally sex ratio was establish. The obtained data were statistically processed. Generally the low percent of D (30ppm) improved the average lifespan of descendants and had a favorable effect on all their developmental traits. Compared to the control (140ppm) the reaction of the individuals was divided into 3 groups: - significantly better than it when the amount of D was small (30ppm); - significantly lower if the concentration of D was high (24.22%) and - higher than the control, but without statistical assurance, at all other concentrations. If in larvae and adults the amount of D was unexpectedly high in the DNA the amount of D remained at the natural state as in control.

Keywords: Deuterium, *Drosophila melanogaster* w^{1118} genotype, phenotype reaction.

1. Introduction

Environmental factors as well as hydrogen isotopes can significantly affect the organism biological parameters [18]. The water is an interchangeable mixture of hydrogen and oxygen isopologues. The hydrogen-related isotopologues are: *light water* or *normal water* (H_2O), *semi-heavy water* (HDO), *heavy water* (D_2O), and *super-heavy water* or *tritiated water* (T_2O) [25]. The oxygen isotopologues of water are light and heavy ^{16}O and ^{17}O & ^{18}O respectively [10]. Their peculiarities are used as marker for authenticity of food and other economic purposes [9]. The ratio of D/H in water shows substantial geographical variation, which could affect the plants and animal's evolution [4]. The spatial isotopic distribution in tap

¹Prof. Emeritus Senior Researcher Ph.D. Eng., Banat University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine "King Michael I of Romania" from Timisoara, Romania, Full member of Academy of Romanian Scientists, (e-mail: galliab@yahoo.com) *.

²Assoc. Prof. Ph.D., Banat University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine "King Mihai I of Romania" from Timișoara, Romania (e-mail: ionutsarac@yahoo.com)

³Prof. Ph.D., Banat University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine "King Mihai I of Romania" from Timișoara, Romania (e-mail: biotehnologii_usab@yahoo.com)

⁴Researcher, Ph.D., National Research and Development Institute for Cryogenic and Isotopic Technologies - ICSI Râmnicu Valcea, Romania (e-mail:titescu@icsi.ro)

⁵ Researcher, Ph.D. Physicist, National Institute of Research and Development for Technology Cryogenics and Isotopic Technologies – ICSI Râmnicu Vâlcea (e-mail: diana.costinal@icsi.ro)

waters reflects the regional variation of isotopes in the local environment [3], with considerable variation in Timisoara during seasons. The D as well as other stable isotopes are influenced by latitude, humidity, and the seasonal temperature [15, 27].

The importance of isotopologues is given by numerous studies in different fields: in the nature and the urban environment [13], from precipitation [8] solid part of water [31] in vapors [1] in organisms [17] in methods of work [33] animals and human health [26].

The isotopic signature of water changes through phase transitions in the atmospheric water cycle and temperature [7]. In our 2011 determinations we found that the amount of D in the laboratory drinking water was almost constant in the spring months (12.04/142.3ppm; 04.05/142.7ppm; 09.05/142.4ppm) and lower in July (29.07/140.7ppm). Distilled water had a content of 139.4ppm D. Under natural conditions D stabilizes rapidly from low or high concentrations to the value specific to the geographical area.

There are only a few works about the D involved in the drosophila lifespan, fertility and the D content in the descendants [12 30]. However, it is unclear whether D content has an impact in the drosophila's phenotype and whether it might alter it.

Studying the ontogeny fertility and variability of drosophila is helpful to understand the effect of the D amount changes in our life quality.

In our experiment the Control was the normal/light water ($H_2^{16}O$).

Stable isotopologues of water have slightly different physical and chemical properties which require a different latent energy for the operation of the aqueous phase. Both have preferential characteristics: evaporation and condensation at light and heavy water respectively (Table 2).

Main goal: To point out the modifying influence of D upon drosophila phenotype w^{1118} .

2. Materials and Methods

The biological material: *D. melanogaster* is an appreciated model for knowing human behavior and especially in neurodegenerative studies [14]. *Drosophila melanogaster* L. is a model organism for genetic studies, being used for testing drugs, food, toxins, pollution, and human degenerative illnesses. Approximately 60% of human genes are identical to those of drosophila: 1) the main signaling pathways and molecular mechanisms are conserved in both organisms; 2) many

aspects of development and behavior are similar to both kingdoms. For her easily altered particularities the mutant w^{1118} genotype of *D. melanogaster* was used. The short lifespan (8.5 days at 25°C), a good viability the ease of maintenance, made this a perfect for our study. The population was maintained on life cycles on standard environment at 25°C, humidity 65-70% (provided by drip with mixture of D) and constant lighting since 1990. Generations of "deuterated" offspring were obtained by passing individuals from G0 (normal environment) on the prepared medium in variants with variable amounts of D. The fundament of this experiment consisted in the presumption that D accumulation in the offspring's is linked with the amount of D from their growth media. Each generation, G1 - G5, was generated by parental forms (♀3: ♂3) from offspring raised successively in the specific concentration of D. Parents were eliminated 72 hours after the start of each experiment.

Deuterium administration. The virgin individuals "head of generation" were raised on the culture medium with D in variable quantity. It was the same standard food, but D replaced H₂O (145ppm) to create the following deuteration treatments: low amount: deuterium-depleted water (30ppm) and semy-heavy water (500ppm, 2.07%, 13.26%, and 22.5%, 96.89%). The different amount of D in the growth medium was obtained by volumetric mixture between 30ppm and 96.98% (Table 1).

Table 1. Experimental variants D content in ppm and %.

No.	Variants	D content		Water category
		ppm	%	
1	V1	140	0.0140	Light water ¹⁹
2	V2	30	0.0030	Deuterium depleted water
3	V3	500	0.0500	Semi heavy water
4	V4	20.700	2.0700	Semi heavy water
5	V5	132,622	13.2622	Semi heavy water
6	V6	242,200	24.2200	Semi heavy water

The ingredients of the culture medium were processed into mixtures with D in the concentrations mentioned above. We consider that in the case of our experiment the contribution of D to the subjects is made by ingestion but also by respiration. Successive generations, marked with "G1", "G2", up to "G5", were quantified in 3 repetitions.

The differences among the parameters of different waters are useful in understanding food ingestion, maggots' motility and last but not least the flies better fodder preparation.

During the hatching period within 24 hours adult flies of both sexes were collected and counted.

Table 2. Physical properties of isotopologues of water used for our purposes

Proprieties	Normal water (140ppm)	DDW	Semi heavy water	Heavy water
Boiling point (°C)	100.0 ²⁰	100.0 ²²	100.7 ²¹	101.4 ²⁰
pH	7.0 ²⁰	7.0	7.27 ²¹	7.44 ²⁰
Density (g/ml)	0.998 ²⁰	0.995 ²²	1.05 ²¹	1.11 ²⁰

The following parameters were evaluated.

- 1) D amount in different ontogenesis phases and in DNA;
- 2) The locomotors ability of larvae and adults to adapt to the different deuterium content in the;
- 3) Prolificacy and sensitivity of females/males to different concentrations of deuterium;
- 4) Molecular investigation at the adults (the second part of this investigation).

A total of 9,112 flies were observed in studies of the relationship between w¹¹¹⁸ genotype and D amount.

The present paper refers to the phenotypic responses of the offspring of the w¹¹¹⁸ line at the D variation in their environment.

3. Results and Discussions

The chapter material and working method showed how the series of descendants were obtained (G1-G5).

Depending on the applied environmental factors, the *Drosophila*'s lifespan will be influenced in different ways. In *Drosophila*, morphological and behavioral traits are influenced by environment favorable or harmful factors. This presumably is caused by an increase/decrease in the rate of physiological and metabolic processes [28].

Variation of D in different lifespan phases and in DNA

In order to know how D accumulates in adults and to see if the cell has the capacity to filter and stop the various "noxious substances/D", the content of D in the adults of the 5th generation and the DNA extracted from them was determined (Table 3).

The 5th larvae generation had a less content compared to the growth media (142.86 ± 9.4 < 145ppm). Unexpected was the high amount of D into the larvae formed in 30ppm medium (125.52 ± 8.3 > 30ppm).

Table 3. D contents of larvae, imago and DNA at w^{1118} genotype the 5th generation grown successively on different concentrations of D*
 (1% = 10.000ppm)

Variants: types of water	The D content			
	of growth medium	in larvae (ppm)	in adults (ppm and %)	DNA samples (ppm)
Light	145ppm	142.86 ± 9.4	151.2±3.0ppm	141.5±3.0
Deuterium depleted (DDW)	30ppm	125.52 ± 8.3	4.678±0.094%	141.8 ±3.0
Semi-heavy	500ppm	No results	244.5±5.0ppm	141.7±3.0
Semi-heavy	24.22%	No results	8.615±0.172 %	142.3±3.0

The reported uncertainty is calculated using a magnification factor $k = 2$, which corresponds to a confidence level of approximately 95%.

Comparing the D content of their growth medium with larvae it can be considered that the body's cells have the ability to filter non-specific "products" and to maintain the organism at the normal evolutionary parameters; it means larval have the ability to adapt their cells to D amount from the environment for their benefit.

In adults, the D content was extremely high compared to their growth environment and that of the larvae. Also it is incomprehensible why there is a bioaccumulation of D in adults who came from a growth medium with a low D content (30ppm). We assume that the accumulation of D in adults indicates its storage in the exoskeleton structure by replacing H or by accumulation in its transformed cells, tissue in which the water is almost non-existent. It is also possible that the structure of the exoskeleton chooses for stronger bonds than those of H. By similarity we mention Magozzi's studies made on vertebrates which pointed out in the absence of isotopic variation in the environment the ^2H and ^{18}O values of keratin vary dependent on the artificial habitat created [19]. A similar process of different elements accumulation in chitine was described by Boden et al. [2].

In nuclear DNA extracted from adults, the D content was lower compared to the larval and of adults' cells, with values close to a "natural" amount (141.5±3ppm). There are no differences between the D content in DNA molecules and in the culture medium. Regardless of whether the entire life cycle took place in environments with D in a similar amount as in nature (145ppm) or in the presence of an excessively low or excessively high content (30ppm respectively 24.22%), in the DNA was not accumulated D. In comparison to control in the nuclear DNA of deuterated-adults the deuterium amount increased slightly varying 0.3ppm/30ppm; 0.2ppm /500ppm and 0.8ppm/24.22% D. It was 142.3ppm into DNA of adults grew in the highest concentration of D (24.22%).

Survival index (SI) it is a sum of reactions from different stages of development of individuals, to the “death” that can be used to estimate the body's response to different environmental conditions. From the many traits that condition the survival rate, we chose those that were considered more eloquent.

The ontogenetic evolution In the developmental stage of drosophila's are two distinct stages of morphogenesis: larval stages and metamorphosis into adults. These two stages of development are related to the embryonic stage, which is a component of other ontogenetic pathways [21]. During the drosophila development, the environment acts as a timer in the body growth (genetically determined), and in the duration of its progress (plasticity of the phenotype). Among larval stage at the D variants and control no significant differences were established. The pupae and adult stages were shorter than the control. According to the control the life span was more accelerated till 2.07% when it was short. From 13.26% showed a return process, being almost to the normal. It is intriguing how the first hatched adults were female and the last hatched were male. Such a finding contradicts the observations made by us in other conditions.

The lifespan of *Drosophila suzukii* (Matsumura) was the most similar to our experiment. In *D. suzukii* the ontogenetic cycle included first instars larvae (3-7 days) pupation (4-15 days) and adult (20-30 days)[11]. Comparing the results obtained in our experiment (Table 4) with the lifespan of *D. suzukii* we found that in the larvae stage appeared the most significant changes. The pupae stage was likely to *S. suzukii*. The life span was longer only at the control.

Table 4. The period of time for each ontogenetic stage (days)

D content	The larvae stage				Pupae stage	Hacking the:				Life span duration
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	total		the first adult		the last adult		
						days	Gender*	after	Gender*	
145ppm	2	1	8	11	15	10	Female	4 (14)	Male	40
30ppm	1	1	8	10	10	7	Female	3 (10)	Male	30
500ppm	2	1	8	11	9	5	Female	1 (6)	Male	26
2.07%	1	2	4	7	10	5	Female	1 (6)	Male	23
13.26%	1	2	5	8	9	7	Female	1 (8)	Male	25
24.22%	2	2	8	12	12	9	Female	1 (10)	Female	34

* The first and the last hatched descendant

The locomotors activity During the 2-3 days after leaving the culture medium, the motility of the larvae was gradual. In all variants the migration was progressive; sometimes even the larvae climbed above the point of insertion of the pupae, after which they descended. Such behavior has not been mentioned and we cannot explain it. Compared to the control, the motility of the larvae was more active and

the insertion height of the pupae was higher at the 30ppm variant (Figure 1; $x_{G1-G5}=4.66\pm0.14$ cm).

The highest extra amount of D (24.22%) the motility of the larvae and the pupae fixation was reduced with 20% ($x_{G1-G5}=2.88\pm0.50$ cm). The height of pupation was relatively the same in the variants in which D was low or in excess.

Under the investigated conditions, larvae locomotors activity varied much in the first generations (G1-G2). The larvae accommodation to the unusual medium started from G3. From G4 a stability process took place, the pupation highest was similar between D variants.

Taken in account the general average/generation it is revealed a pronounced differences between the insertion height of the pupae of G1-G3 ($x_{G1}=3.74\pm0.36$, $x_{G2}=3.74\pm0.27$, $x_{G3}=3.71\pm0.43$ cm). From G4 the highest of pupation is up 4 and 5 cm ($x_{G4}=4.08\pm0.40$ and $x_{G5}=5.97\pm0.19$ cm).

The particular behavior of offspring revealed a favorable influence of excess of D.

Comparing the reaction values of line w^{1118} with other 3 lines and 3 local (wild) populations it was found that the pupation height was the highest at a concentration of 30ppm (4.5 cm and 4.27 cm respectively) and the lowest at the concentration of 24.22% (2.66 cm and 3.35 cm, respectively). Overall, the reaction of wild genotypes was slightly superior to drosophila lines (3.94 cm < 3.67 cm) but without signification ($d=0.27$ cm).

Figure 1. Larval motility and height of pupation for different concentrations of deuterium

Population size was closely correlated with the concentration of D in the culture medium. The negative effect of D was revealed at the concentration of 2.29% at which the lethality index was 50%.

The evolution of the size of the populations from the five successive and different generations (Figure 2) highlighted: high variability within each variant; random increase up to G3; from G3 a tendency of “accommodation” of the offspring to the increased concentrations of D were observed; In G4, the individuals show a significant tolerance to the presence of D in the culture medium.

The selected traits appears to be suitable for the study of such interactions, since we assume that they are extremely sensitive to a myriad of environmental factors, ranging from D to temperature or radiation [34, 5].

Gender and D amount: gender specific survivorship and mortality rates pointed out a better survivorship and lower mortality for female compared to males at ages up to 24 h after emergence. As observed in previous studies of *Drosophila* and at other organisms [24, 23], age-specific mortality rates is increased for females [22].

Unlike other *Drosophila* population and genotypes we worked with all variants of the w¹¹¹⁸ line, the first offspring were female and the last were male; with one exception, the concentration of 24.22% (Table 4).

Figure 2. The population size at drosophila w¹¹¹⁸ genotypes of different generations formed into environment with variable concentrations of D

Figure 3. Proportion of females and males in populations of different generations formed into environment with variable concentrations of D

There are no data to show that the w^{1118} genotype has another way of ranking the genders.

The average proportion of females and males in the population of all generations was in favor of XX sex ($52.07 + 0.66 > 47.93 + 0.66\%$; Figure 3).

Compared to Control, in all variants the number of females was lower and, only at the concentration of 13.2622% their number was higher.

As shown in Table 4 and Figure 3, the mean life span of females was higher compared to the males by 4%, as is no typical in mixed-sex populations [16, 29].

To date, there are no studies evaluating the effect of D on drosophila

Repeating the study to other genotypes (local populations or standard lines of drosophila) it was determined similar effects of D on their life cycle and behavior.

Since mortality was slightly affected by D means that different generation descendants may display a reaction norm for lifespan.

D had an effect of accelerating the metabolism of different ontogenetic stages, which ultimately led to the shortening of life span without affecting the phenotypic architecture of individuals. Of the thousands of adults observed, no cases of Petit or other phenotypic defects were found as observed in other experiments.

The D amount in the nuclear DNA of individuals grown at concentration 24.22% increased relatively insignificant compared to the D content of the medium and of adults. Against to the control the content of D "stored" in the nuclear DNA of adults raised insignificant ($d_{30\text{ppm-C}}=+0.2\text{ppm}$ and $d_{24.22\%-C}=+0.8\text{ppm}$).

The actual causes of deuterium-environment-organism interactions remain unknown for most drosophila genotypes, but may reflect significant changes in their physiological determinants and we presume that the genetic background was not affected.

The distinction is important, because the theory of evolution is entirely dependent upon the assumption of genetic variants that have individual-specific effects on survival [20, 32, 6].

The drosophila's behavior could be used to quantify the D involvement at other organisms, comparing their patterns and of specie-specificities in the presence of D excess.

Conclusions

(1) Low percentages of D added to the regular diet of *D. melanogaster* improved mean life span without an effect on fecundity.

- (2) However, D had an adverse effect on development time and showed toxicity as the dose was increased.
- (3) Compared to the control (0.0140%) the motility of the individuals was separated into 3 groups:
- significantly superior to the control when the amount of D was small (30ppm);
 - significantly lower if the concentration was high (24.22%) and
 - higher than the control, but without statistical assurance, at all other concentrations.
- (4) Regardless of generation, the large amount of D significantly reduced the motility of larvae (24.22%).
- (5) The proportion of the two sexes in "naturalized" populations to the excess D in their living environment was not changed.
- (6) The most significant result of this study is that the body/cell has the ability to maintain its DNA almost intact.
- (7) Thus, in *Drosophila melanogaster*, even if D increases greatly in their living environment it has itself a limited influence to cause significant increase of damages.

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